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THE EFFECT OF SOME HERBICIDES UPON WEEDS FROM THE SUNFLOWER CULTURE

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Abstract

The paper presents the experimental results obtained in the year 2019 regarding the individual effect of five weed killers, used for the control of weeds at the sunflowers crops, as well as that action in association with two other herbicides: Sencor applied in a quantity of 0,4 kg/ha and Gesagrade 50 applied in a quantity of 3 kg/ha.

As concerns the effect of the individual application of each weed killer, on the first place we can put Alachlor with an average production increase of 6,95 q/ha or by Treflan with an average production increase of 6,80 q/ha, or 33,0% as compared to the witness.

The weed control by use of herbicides, is a very effective method, this way eliminating the hand hard work used for maintaining the growing.

Key words: herbicide, weeds, sunflower, individual effect, association, production, dosage.

INTRODUCTION

The increase of the mechanization and amendments, the increase of the production potential of the less productive soil, the application of the herbicides and pesticide the use of new types with a higher biological value, all these represent important factors for a permanent growth of the agricultural production.

In the field of modern agriculture, capable of economic efficiency, produced with a lower price and a higher productive level, together with some other ways of billing the weeds, the herbicides play an important and irreplaceable part until now

Taking into account the urgent necessity of using the herbicide in controlling the weeds in the agricultural crop, and on the other hand, the fact that these are toxic substances; it is necessary for people to know well their properties the usage rules and the work security technique.

Weeds chemical control is a main element in the modern technology of the sunflower growing which amplifies extremely quickly because of the increase in number of the herbicides and their diversity as well as by the advance of the sunflower growing on larger and larger surfaces.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the experiment of weeds control at the sunflower growing by was of herbicides, taken in the year 2019 in Oradea region, we followed the individual effect of 5 herbicides, as well as their action when associated to some other herbicides, Sencor applied in 0,4 kg/ha dosage and Gesagrade 50 , 3 kg/ha.

The variants studied as follows: No herbicide witness and twice hand hoeing; Treflan 4l/ha; Treflan + Sencor 4l/ha + 0,4kg/ha; Treflan + Gesagrade 50 4l/ha + 3kg/ha; Eradicane 4 l/ha; Eradicane + Sencor 4l/ha + 0,4kg/ha; Eradicane + Gesagrade 50 4l/ha + 3kg /ha; Dual 500 4l/ha; Dual 500 + Sencor 4l/ha + 0,4kg/ha; Dual 500 + Gesagrade 50 4l/ha + 3kg/ha; Alachlor 7l/ha; Alachlor + Sencor 7l/ha + 0,4kg/ha; Alachlor + Gesagrade 50 7l/ha + 3kg/ha; Frontier 2l/ha; Frontier + Sencor 2l/ha + 0,4kg/ha; Frontier + Gesagrade 50 2l/ha + 3kg/ha.

The experiment was placed following the method of randomized blocks, in 4 repetitions. The hybrid used was select, which was sed on the 10th of April, with a thickness of 40.000 plants/ha and harvesting was made during the first decade of September.

The forerunner plant was the autumn barley.

The preparing stage of the field for the experiment comprised the following: autumn ploughing, preparing the germination bed starting up the growing of the plant, booking after the crops, harvesting.

RESULTS AND DISCUSIONS

The results obtained in 2019 are presented in table no 1, table no 2.

The chemical control of the weeds represents a main element of the modern technology of sunflower growing which increase rapidly, because of the increase of the number of herbicides and their diversification, and the impetus that the sunflower growing on larges surfaces has shown.

For the actual experiment, in 2019, there were used 5 herbicides (Treflan, Eradicane, Dual, Alachlor and Frontier), as an individual effect and their action in association with Sencor and Gesagrade 50, a dosage of 0,4 kg/ha for Sencor and 3 kg/ha for Gesagrade 50. The administration of the herbicides was made when preparing the germination bed.

The research proved a high level of phytotoxicity for the Sencor product with 0,4 kg/ha dosage, for all the variants the use of this herbicide produced the destruction of 70/ of the sunflower plants.

It can also be noticed the phytotoxicity of the Gesagrade 50 product, 3 kg/ha, in the year 2019. for the lots where Gesagrade 50 was used, the sunflower plants were yellowish when beginning to grow. This phenomenon appeared more often at the lots treated with Dual 500+, Gesagrade 50 and Frontier + Gesagrade 50.

As a result of the application of these herbicides, the level of weeds turned very low, even succeeding a level of 96% weed controlling for some lots. The use of Alachlor and Gesagrade 50 was the most useful and the application of Treflan and Gesagrade 50 destroyed the weeds in a proportion of 93%.

Taking into consideration the herbicides applied without anything else, the best effect was proved by Alachlor, followed by Treflan and Eradicane.

Table 1.

The production of sunflower, with variants and repetitions, during the experiment with herbicides in 2019

Variant	Repetition				Average
	I	II	III	IV	
1.	22.0	21.5	21.0	21.6	86.1
2.	27.2	27.0	27.5	27.3	109.0
3.	-	-	-	-	-
4.	28.0	27.3	27.5	28.8	11.6
5.	27.0	26.5	27.2	27.4	108.1
6.	-	-	-	-	-
7.	28.0	27.0	27.4	28.0	110.4
8.	26.0	26.0	25.0	26.2	103.2
9.	-	-	-	-	-
10..	26.9	26.5	26.0	27.0	106.4
11.	29.0	29.0	28.0	28.7	114.7
12.	-	-	-	-	-
13.	28.5	28.0	28.4	28.5	113.4
14.	26.1	27.0	27.5	27.0	107.6
15.	-	-	-	-	-
16.	26.0	26.5	25.8	26.3	104.6
Average	294.7	292.3	291.3	296.8	1175.1

The treatment with Dual 500 and Frontier showed a 75% higher degree of weed controlling. At this treatment, the production increase was smaller, that is 4,27 g/ha for Dual 500 and 5,36 g/ha for Frontier.

With the exception of the variant treated with Sencor, all the other herbicides used, alone or mixed with Gesagrade 50, were effective for weed

controlling and assured better crops than the witness variant which was hold twice, by hand.

During vegetation, the variants treated with weed killers showed better development, quickly covering the soil after rising, not being disturbed by the weeds.

However, the behaviour of the weeds was different. In the experimental lots treated with Treflan, the following weed appeared. *Rubus caesius* (blackberry bush), *Cirsium arvense* (horse thistle), *Cynodon dactylon* (couch grass), *Matricaria inodora* (camomile) from the perennial plants and from the yearly ones: *Polygonum aviculare* (knot grass), *Amaranthus retroflexus* (amaranth), *Sinapsis arvensis* (wild mustard), *Capsela bursa pastoris* (shepherd's purse), *Viola arvensis* (three spotted brothers), *Xanthium strumarium* (mouse ear).

For the lots treated with Eradicane there were present the same weeds but some of them were more numerous, especially the *Cirsium arvense* (horse thistle).

For the lots treated with Dual 500 and frontier, all the types of weeds existing on the lots treated with Treflan appeared, but more frequently.

The treatment with Alachlor proved the best effect. On these lots, the weeds almost disappeared with the exception of *Rubus caesius*, which was present with the same rate as in the lots treated with Sencor. The presence of weeds was very small, only *Rubus caesius* appeared, very late and in a very small percentage. On these lots there was also present the phytotoxicity upon the sunflower, together with the one upon the weeds, about 70% of the plants dying, compromising the growing.

Analyzing the data in Table no.2, it can be noticed that the variant treated with Alachlor, 7 l/ha dosage of commercial product gave the biggest production of sunflower 28.67 g/ha with an extra quantity of 7.41 g/ha, that is 33,1% more than herbicides but it was treated as usual, with two hoeing by hand.

The second in terms of production quantity is the variant treated with Alachlor + Gesagrade 50.7 l/ha + 3 kg/ha, obtaining 28.35 g/ha, and compared to the witness representing a bigger quantity with an extra of 31.6%, that is 6.82 g/ha.

The result is that, by combining Alachlor with the second, herbicide Gesagrade 50, the production does not increase, compared to the production obtained, only at the treatment with Alachlor, but it decreases with 0,32 g/ha.

On the lots treated with Alachlor combined with Gesagrade 50, applied 7 l/ha + 3 kg/ha a dosage, even if there were few weeds the degree

of weed destruction going up to 96% related to a smaller production, and a phytotoxic effect appeared at the sunflower plants, because of the Gesagrade 50, 3 kg/ha dosage, for the conditions of the year 2019.

Table 2

The production results obtained for the sunflower in the experiment with herbicides, applied alone and in association, in the year 2019

No.	Herbicides applied	Herbicide dosage applied per ha	Production (q/ha)	%	Difference (q/ha)	Significance	Phytotoxicity (%)	Degree of weed control (%)
1.	Witness with no herbicide	Application of two hosing by hand	20,6	100	-	-	-	-
2.	Treflan	4 l	27.40	133.0	6.80	xxx	-	85
3.	Treflan + Sencor	4 l+0.4 kg	-	-	-	-	70	98
4.	Treflan + Gesagrade 50	4l + 3 kg	27.95	135.7	7.35	xxx	-	94
5.	Eradicane	4 l	26.10	126.7	5.50	xxx	-	80
6.	Eradicane + Sencor	4 l + 0.4 kg	-	-	-	-	70	98
7.	Eradicane + Gesagrade 50	4 l + 3 kg	26.70	129.6	6.10	xxx	-	90
8.	Dual 500	4 l	25.30	125.8	4.70	xxx	-	73
9.	Dual 500 + Sencor	4 l + 0.4 kg	-	-	-	-	70	98
10.	Dual 500 + Gesagrade 50	4 l + 3 kg	26.30	127.7	5.70	xxx	-	86
11.	Alachlor	7 l	27.55	133.7	6.95	xxx	-	86
12.	Alachlor + Sencor	7 l + 0.4 kg	-	-	-	-	70	98
13.	Alachlor + Gesagrade	7 l + 3 kg	27.90	135.4	7.30	xxx	-	94
14.	Frontier	2 l	25.80	125.2	5.20	xxx	-	77
15.	Frontier + Sencor	2 l + 0.4 kg	-	-	-	-	70	98
16.	Frontier + Gesagrade 50	2 l + 3 kg	26.4	126.4	5.44	xxx	-	86
Average			26.15					
Difference					5.55			
%				126.9				
Significance			xxx					

LSD 5% = 0.45 q/ha LSD 1% = 0.62 q/ha LSD 0.1% = 0.83 q/ha

The variant treated with Treflan 4 l/ha dosage, produced an average sunflower crops of 27.24 g/ha seeds, this representing a percentage of 26.5%, or an extra quantity of 26.5%, or compared to the witness variant.

For the variant treated with Treflan combined with Gesagrade 50, 4l/ha and 3 kg/ha a dosage, the production was 27.90 g/ha, with an extra quantity of 6.37 g/ha, that is 29.6% more than the witness variant.

The increase benefit of the production for the variant treated with Treflan combined with Gesagrade 50, compared to the one treated only with Treflan, is 0.66 g/ha sunflower seeds. These results make us notice that the efficiency of Gesagrade 50 3 kg/ha dosage combined with Treflan is not so high, even if the degree of weed control is 93%, following the lots treated with Alachlor + Gesagrade 50, where the weed control was 96%.

Analyzing the next part of Table no. 2 it can be noticed that the Eradicane product shows a good behaviour in weed controlling for sunflower growing. For the lots treated with Eradicane 4 l/ha a dosage the average production was 27.03 g/ha, that is an extra quantity of 5.50 g/ha seeds, 25,5% more than the one of the witness.

When Eradicane is mixed with Gesagrade 50.4 l/ha + 3 kg/ha a dosage, the average production was 27.6 g/ha, representing an extra quantity of 6.07 g/ha or 28,1% compared to the witness.

The increase benefit of the production obtained for the variant treated with Eradicane mixed with Gesagrade 50 compared to the one treated only with Eradicane, is only 0.57 g/ha sunflower seeds. As concerns the weed controlling level, this combination of Eradicane and Gesagrade 50 destroyed 90% of the weeds compared to 80% of them, when only Eradicane was used.

The treatment with Dual 500 and Frontier gave smaller production of sunflower an a hectare, but, compared to the witness, the production is good.

The results presented above prove that, in case the herbicide chose can not be found it is better to use any of the analyzed herbicide than to have the soil with no weed killer or work it by hand or mechanically.

CONCLUSIONS

Following the examination and the data obtained, concerning the efficiency of the 5 herbicides used, for weed controlling at the sunflower growing, applied alone and in combination with Sencor 0.4 kg/ha a dosage and Gesagrade 50 3 kg/ha a dosage there can be pointed out the following conclusions:

- the chemical weed control is a main element in the technology of sunflower growing, assuring an average production increase of 5.5 g/ha, that is 26.9 %;

- the efficiency of the Treflan, Alachlor, Eradicane, Dual 500 and Frontier combined with Gesagrade 50 is more secure and higher, because it assures the highest increase of production per hectare;
- out of the herbicides applied in combination, it can be remarked the Treflan variant applied 4 l/ha + Gesagrade 50 3 kg/ha a dosage
- out of the herbicides applied alone, it can be remarked the very good effect of the Alachlor with an average production increase of 6,95 g/ha, that is 33.7% compared to the witness, followed by the Treflan, with an average production increase of 6,80 g/ha and 33,0% compared to the witness;
- the Sencor weed killer, applied 0,4 kg/ha a dosage, combined with the other herbicides (Treflan, Eradicane, Dual 500, Alachlor and Frontier) succeeds a 98% weed controlling percentage but it also presents 70% phytotoxicity upon the sunflower plants;
- herbicides weed control is a very efficient method the level of weed controlling using herbicide is expanded between 73 – 96%, so that the sunflower growing can became fully mechanized, excluding the high quantity of effort for maintaining the crops by hand hoeing.

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RESEARCH ON THE PRODUCTIVITY OF SOME FLAX VARIETIES FOR OIL IN BIHOR COUNTY

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Abstract

Flax, a plant with blue flowers and small brown seeds, is one of the oldest cultivated plants on earth, originating in India and China. It is cultivated in our country for its stems from which textile fibers are extracted and for the seeds from which a fatty oil is extracted, used both in painting and in medicine.

Key words: flax for oil, production, surface, repetition, parcel

INTRODUCTION

Flax is used to extract fibers and oil. Flax seeds are rich in oil and protein. Flax seeds for fiber contain 30-36% oil and flax varieties for oil up to 44%, after pressing results 60-70 kg cakes rich in protein, carbohydrates and fats, which is a high-quality concentrated feed in feeding animals in particular dairy cows with a beneficial effect on its quality.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In 2018 we studied in Inand, Bihor county 3 varieties of flax: Lirina, Star and Elan. We sowed an experiment in 4 repetitions, the surface of the experimental parcel being 10 m² harvestable, at a distance of 12.5 cm between rows, at a density of 1000 germinating grains per m².

For the preparation of the land, a plowing of 30 cm was performed in the autumn of the previous year, and in the spring we performed a passage with a disc harrow at a depth of 8-10 cm. In order to have a quality of the germination bed before sowing, we performed a work with the combine.

The seed was executed at a depth of 2-3 cm with the Wintersteiger TC 2700 experimental seed drill.

Fertilization was carried out with complex fertilizers 20.20.20, 250 kg / ha in a dose of 50.50.50. active substance, ammonium nitrate 150kg /

ha in a dose of 50.0.0 active substance and in the vegetation a foliar fertilization with cropmax 11 / ha was performed.

Fig.1. Aspect in the experimental field

In order to maintain the crop, a herbicide was performed with dual gold EC 1.5 l / ha and in the cotyledon phase to control the pest *Aphthona euphorbiae* (earth flea) I sprayed with the insecticide Decis 2.5 CE 0,5 l / ha.

Harvesting was done with a combine for experiments.

Determination of MMB (mass of 1000 grains) and MHL (hectolitre mass) was made with the Perten AM 5200-A facilities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The productions obtained in 2018 for flax for lei varieties Lirina, Star and Elan vary between 1.7 kg and 2.5 kg / parcel with humidity between 8.0% and 10.5 %

Table 1

The results obtained on the experimental parcels

NO.	VARIETY	SURFACE AREA IN m ²				PRODUCTION/ PARCEL (KG)				HUMIDITY %				MMB (g)	MHL (kg)
		R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄		
1	LIRINA	10	10	10	10	2.1	2.3	2.5	2.4	8.2	8.4	8.6	8.6	6.7	71
2	ELAN	10	10	10	10	1.8	1.7	1.9	1.8	10.5	10.3	10.0	10.5	7.3	69
3	STAR	10	10	10	10	2.3	2.5	2.2	2.1	8.1	8.2	8.0	8.0	6.8	71

R₁,R₂,R₃,R₄ = repetitions 1,2,3 and 4

MMB= mass of 1000 grains

MHL= hectolitre mass

In table 1 are presented the productions of the flax varieties for oil Lirina, Elan, respectively Star on the experimental parcels repetitions 1,2,3 and 4, also at each production / repetition we have the humidity%.

The Lirina variety recorded yields per parcel between 2.1 and 2.5 kg, Elan between 1.7 and 1.9 kg and Star between 2.1 and 2.5 kg.

The highest mass of 1000 grains (MMB) was determined for the Elan 7.3g, Star 6.8g and Lirina varieties 6.7 g.

The hectolitre mass (MHL) is equal to the varieties Lirina and Star 71 kg and to Star is 69 kg.

Table 2

Calculation of productions per hectare at the humidity of 10%

NO.	VARIETY	Production / parcel / ha (kg)				Productions / parcel / ha at humidity of 10% in kg				Average productions /ha in kg
		R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	
1	LIRINA	2100	2300	2500	2400	2142	2340	2538	2437	2363
2	ELAN	1800	1700	1900	1800	1790	1694	1900	1790	1794
3	STAR	2300	2500	2200	2100	2348	2550	2248	2146	2323

In order to be able to calculate the yields per hectare for each variety and to see the production differences between varieties, in table 2 we calculated the yields per parcel per hectare the repetitions 1,2,3 and 4 at the harvest humidities presented in table 1, then we calculated the productions / parcel / ha at a humidity of 10% and we averaged the 4 parcels in order to obtain the production potential per hectare of each variety.

The variety with the best production is Lirina 2363 / ha followed by Star 2323 kg / ha and Elan with 1794 kg|ha

Fig.2. Variation of production per hectare per repetition

Figure 2 shows the production graph per hectare for each repetition where we observe that the Lirina variety exceeds the production of the Star variety in repetitions 1 and 2 and the Star variety exceeds the production of the Lirina variety in repetitions 3 and 4.

The productions of the Elan variety are lower in all 4 repetitions than the productions of the Lirina and Star varieties.

Fig.3. Graph of productions registered for flax varieties for oil in the year 2018

Figure 3 shows the graph of production per hectare of varieties at a humidity of 10%, so Lirina has the highest production 2363kg / ha by 1.7% higher than the Star variety which has a production of 2323 kg / ha and 32% higher than the Elan variety, which has a production of 1794 kg/ha.

CONCLUSIONS

Following this study, the Lirina variety has the highest production of 2363kg / ha, 1.7% higher than the Star variety, which has a production of 2323 kg / ha and is 32% higher than that of the Elan variety, which has a production of 1794 kg / ha.

The highest mass of 1000 grains (MMB) was determined for the Elan 7.3g, Star 6.8g and Lirina 6.7g varieties.

The hectolitre mass (MHL) is equal to the varieties Lirina and Star 71 kg and to Star is 69 kg.

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THE CEREAL SECTOR IN THE NORTH-WEST REGION, ROMANIA

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Abstract

The paper presents the situation of the cereal sector in the North-West Region, a sector represented by the following main crops: maize, wheat, barley, oat and rye. The areas cultivated with these cereals and the productions obtained in the period 2015-2020 are analyzed.

Maize and wheat were detached, occupying the largest areas and having the highest productions. Thus, in 2020, maize was cultivated on 267,679 ha and obtained a production of 1,624,102 tons. The maize area owned by the North-West Region represented 11%, and the maize production 16% of the country total. The wheat was on the 2nd place, which occupied 156,061 ha in 2020 and had a production of 593,572 tons. The area with wheat in the North-West Region represented 7%, and the production of wheat 9% of the country total.

The other cereals studied, barley, oat and rye had areas under 50,000 ha and productions below 100,000 tons in 2020.

Key words: maize, North-West Region, oat, productions, Romania, wheat

INTRODUCTION

Cereals are grown due to their specific nutritional characteristics, for which they are used both in human nutrition and for animal feed. At the same time, it represents the raw material for other sectors of activity. (Chiurciu, et al., 2020)

Romania has an important place in the European Union in the field of cereal cultivation. The data provided by Eurostat show that, in 2020, our country was on the first place in terms of the area cultivated with maize (2,680.10 thousand ha) and on the leading places for the areas cultivated with wheat (on the 4th place – 2,277.42 thousand ha) and barley (on the 6th place - 445.74 thousand ha).

Romania also had top places for cereal production in 2020: for maize, the 2nd place with 10,942.35 thousand tons, for wheat, the 4th place - 6,743.86 thousand tons. (Eurostat)

The object of the present study is the cereal sector in the North-West Region (Fig. 1), a region that stretches on 34,160 km² and in which most of the surface, 64%, is cultivated with cereals (*North-West RDA*).

Fig. 1 North-West Region
Source: North-West RDA

About 50% of the population lives in rural areas and 45.8% of the income registered in the North-West Region, as coming from the rural area, is obtained from agriculture. (Rural SMEs Interreg Europe, 2017)

After Chiurciu et al., 2018, apud Manole et al., 2014, Bihor county has the largest arable area in the Region.

The above information highlights the importance of the cereals sector in the north-west of the country.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study highlights the role of the North-West Region in the cereal's sector in Romania. To illustrate this aspect, the areas cultivated with the main cereals grown in this Region, namely maize, wheat, barley, oat and rye, were analyzed.

Also, the productions obtained from these crops were presented and then the contribution, in percentage, that the North-West Region brings to the total cereal areas of the country and to the total production obtained was studied.

The analyzed data were taken from statistical sites, such as the National Institute of Statistics and Eurostat, and then interpreted in tables and graphs. The period under study is 2015-2020.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows the evolution of cultivated areas in the North-West Region, with the main cereal crops, in the period 2015-2020. Maize occupied the largest area, and at the opposite pole was the rye. In 2016, maize registered 279,496 ha, ie the largest area, and in 2017 the smallest, of 254,391 ha. The next crop, according to the size of the areas, was wheat, for which in 2017 the smallest cultivated area was recorded, of 142,875 ha. Other cereal crops recorded less than 50,000 ha cultivated: barley and spring barley - 35,712 ha in 2020, oat - 18,390 ha in 2020 and rye, 963 ha in 2020.

Fig. 2 Areas cultivated with the main cereal crops in the North-West Region, in the period 2015-2020, ha

Source: Own interpretation according to NIS

The only cereal plant, for which in the analyzed period, 2015-2020, the increase of cultivated areas was noticed was that of wheat, with 6% (Table 1).

For the other cereals studied, there was a decrease in areas in 2020, with 3% for maize, 13% - barley, 16% - rye and 48% for oat.

Table 1

Evolution of cultivated areas with the main cereal crops, 2015-2020, ha

Specification	2015	2020	2020/2015 %
Maize	276,771	267,679	276,771
Wheat	146,614	156,061	146,614
Barley and spring barley	40,956	35,712	40,956
Oat	35,516	18,390	35,516
Rye	1,142	963	1,142

Source: Own calculations according to NIS

Figures 3-7 show the share held by the North West Region in 2020 of the total cultivated areas at country level, with rye, wheat, barley, oat and maize:

- for rye - 8%, 963 ha (Fig. 3), which placed this Region on the 4th place, while on the first place was the North-East Region - 41%, 4,751 ha. The counties in the Region where the largest, respectively the smallest area with rye was cultivated were Bihor - 426 ha and Sălaj County, 4 ha;

- for total wheat - 7%, 156,061 ha (Fig. 4), representing the sixth position in the top of wheat-growing regions, in which the first place was occupied by the South-Muntenia Region with 28% - 602,801 ha. In Bihor county was found the largest area with total wheat - 90,709 ha, and in Maramureş county the smallest, 3,044 ha;

Fig.3 The share of cultivated areas with rye at regional level, 2020 (ha,%)

Fig. 4 Share of areas cultivated with wheat total at regional level, 2020 (ha,%)

Source: Own interpretation according to NIS

- for barley and spring barley - 8%, 35,712 ha (Fig. 5), meaning the 4th place in the ranking by country, where the first place was occupied by the South-East Region with 34% -148,625 ha. The largest barley grower in the Region was Bihor County - 13,220 ha, and the smallest barley area was found in Maramureş County, 558 ha;

- for oat - 18%, 18,390 ha (Fig. 6), the 2nd place, in the top of the regions, the first place being occupied by the North-East Region with 19% - 19.118 ha. The counties in the Region where the largest, respectively the smallest area with oat were cultivated were Bihor – 3.726 ha and Sălaj County, 1.007 ha;

Fig.5 Share of cultivated areas with barley at regional level, 2020 (ha,%)

Fig.6 Share of cultivated areas with oat at regional level, 2020 (ha,%)

Source: Own interpretation according to NIS

- for maize - 11%, 267.679 ha (Fig. 7), the 5th place, in the top of the regions, in which the South-Muntenia Region held the first place with 21% - 545.508 ha. In Bihor county was found the largest area with corn – 91.261 ha, and in Bistrița-Năsăud county the smallest, 18.823 ha.

Fig. 7. Share of areas cultivated with maize at regional level, 2020 (ha,%)

Source: Own interpretation according to NIS

Figure 8 shows the evolution of production obtained in the North-West Region, for the main cereal crops, in the period 2015-2020. The largest quantity was obtained for maize, and rye was placed at the opposite pole, in accordance with the occupied areas. By 2018, when 1.953.648 tons were achieved, maize recorded increases in production, and then it began to decline. Wheat was the next crop in terms of production for which in 2016

the smallest quantity was recorded, of 488,888 tons. Other cereal crops recorded less than 100.000 tons: barley and spring barley – 97.161 tons in 2020, oats - 42,680 tons in 2020 and rye, 2.801 tons in 2020.

Fig. 8 Total production obtained for the main cereal crops, in the period 2015-2020, tons
Source: Own interpretation according to NIS

Increases in production for the analyzed period, 2015-2020, were observed in the following crops: maize - 86%, rye - 5% and wheat - 4% (Table 2). For the other cereals studied, there was a decrease in production in 2020, with 26% for barley and spring barley and 39% for oat.

Table 2

The evolution of the total production obtained for the main cereal crops, 2015-2020, tons

Specification	2015	2020	2020/2015 %
Maize	873,385	1,624,102	186
Wheat	570,476	593,572	104
Barley and spring barley	131,424	97,161	74
Oat	69,997	42,680	61
Rye	2,662	2,801	105

Source: own calculations according to NIS

Figures 9-13 show the share of total production of rye, wheat, barley, oat and maize in the North-West Region in 2020:

- for rye - 10%, 2,801 tons (Fig. 9), which placed this Region on the 4th place, while in first place was the North-East Region - 38%, 10.618 tons. The counties in the Region where the highest and the lowest rye production was obtained were Bihor - 1,364 tons and Sălaj County, 9 tons;

- for total wheat - 9%, 593,572 tons (Fig. 10), representing the sixth position in the top of wheat producing regions, in which the first place was occupied by the South-Muntenia Region with 27% - 1,753,266 tons. In Bihor county was found the highest production with total wheat – 369,424 tons, and in Maramureş county the lowest, 10,523 tons;

Fig. 9 Share of total rye production at regional level, 2020 (tons,%)

Fig. 10 Share of total wheat production at regional level, 2020 (tons,%)

Source: Own interpretation according to NIS

- for barley and spring barley - 9%, 97.161 tons (Fig. 11), meaning the 4th place in the country ranking, where the first place was occupied by the South-East Region with 32% -362,816 ha. The largest barley producer in the Region was Bihor County – 37,160 tons, and at the opposite pole was Maramureş County, 1,402 tons;

Fig. 11 Share of total barley production at regional level, 2020 (tons,%)

Fig. 12 Share of total oat production at regional level, 2020 (tons,%)

Source: Own interpretation according to NIS

- for oat - 21%, 42,680 tons (Fig. 12), the first place in the top of the regions, the 2nd place being occupied by the North-East Region with 17% - 33,291 tons. The counties in the Region where the largest and the smallest quantity of oats were harvested were Satu Mare – 14.451 ha and Sălaj County, 2.480 tons;

- for maize - 16%, 1,624,102 ha (Fig. 13), the 2nd place, in the top of the regions, in which the South-Muntenia Region held the first place with 21% -1,783,082 tons. The highest quantity of maize was obtained in Bihor county – 601,643 tons, and in Maramureş county the smallest, 77,006 ha.

Fig. 13 Share of total maize production at regional level, 2020 (tons,%)
Source: Own interpretation according to NIS

Although it is an important cereal grower, which is highlighted by the places occupied in the tops at EU level, this fact is not supported by a high level of performance (Pânzaru RL & Medelete DM, 2017). As the average productions obtained in Romania were below the EU average, our country must increase its efforts to improve the competitiveness of this sector.

In this context, the implementation of the quality management system and its certification would constantly ensure the quality of production, from transport, storage to marketing (Balan, et al., 2020).

Another important element that must be taken into account is climate change, to which Romania must adapt. The use of appropriate agrotechnical practices and hybrids tolerant to stress at grain-filling period (Bonea D. & Dunareanu, 2021) are two of the methods that can be applied to overcome future problems.

CONCLUSIONS

Analyzing the data presented above, which illustrates the situation of the cereals sector in the North-West Region, the following can be concluded:

- The most cultivated cereals, in 2020, were corn and wheat, from which the largest productions in the Region were obtained;
- Other important cereal crops, grown in the Region, were, in order, barley, oat and rye;
- The area cultivated with oat in 2020 (18.390 ha) represented 18% of the country total and positioned the North-West Region as the second oat grower in the country;
- The North-West Region was in 2020 the largest producer of oat, obtaining a total production of 42,680 tons, which accounted for 21% of our country's production;
- With a maize production of 1,624,102 tons, in 2020 the North-West Region was the second largest producer in the region;
- Bihor County, which has the largest arable area in the region, stands out as the main grower and producer of cereals.

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MANAGEMENT OF MINERAL FERTILISATION IN RELATION TO WHEAT CONTAMINATION WITH *FUSARIUM* *GRAMINEARUM*

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Abstract

Wheat is a basic product for consumption in Romania due to the food consumption model of the population and is the main raw material for manufacture of bakery products. In parallel it is used as animal feed.

For our country's economy is an important segment because it provides significant quantities for export.

*Among the pathogens that affect the wheat crop stands out *Fusarium graminearum*, the pathogen that causes one the most devastating diseases of wheat (ear fusariosis) and reduces production by: inducing sterility of the inflorescences, poor seed filling and reducing grain size.*

*This paper presents the mineral nutrition status of winter wheat in relation with the risks of wheat contamination by *Fusarium* toxins in the conditions at ARDS Livada.*

The plants selected for testing were 5 winter wheat cultivars: Glosa, Gruia, Delabrad, Faur and Dropia. The soil from the experiment was Haplic Luvisol.

In order to quantify the mineral nutrition status of plant with macro and micronutrients, the plant analyses have been carried out in the ear emergence-flowering phase.

The results has been interpreted in connection with the optimum limits of mineral contents in dry matter, mentioned in the specialty literature for these growing stages.

Key words: *Fusarium graminearum*, winter wheat, mineral nutrition

INTRODUCTION

Wheat is most important cereal crop in Europe (Soare and Chiurciu, 2016), being cultivated on 22,876.72 thousand ha and a production of 126,658.94 thousand tons in 2020 (Eurostat, 2021).

The wheat quality and consumer safety is affected by *Fusarium Head Blight (FHB)* caused by *Fusarium graminearum*. The winter wheat varieties cultivated in Europe are susceptible to this disease (Bunta et al., 2011; Taheri, 2018).

The *Fusarium* susceptibility of European cultivars is the main cause of the occurring severe epidemics. Through yield and quality loss, the toxin contamination is a major threat in Europe (Humphreys et al., 2001; Liu and Anderson, 2003; Miedaner et al., 2003, Bunta et al., 2011; Kazan et al., 2017; Dana et al., 2017).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the experimental plot from ARDS Livada, the 5 wheat cultivars susceptible to *Fusarium graminearum* attack were tested on parcels fertilised with the following rates (kg of active ingredients/ha): N₄₀ P₄₀K₀ and N₁₂₀ P₄₀K₀.

From these parcels were collected and analyzed soil samples from ploughed layer and plant samples in the ear emergence-flowering stages.

The analyzes made at the soil samples were: soil reaction (pH), humus total (Ht), total nitrogen (Nt), available phosphorus (P_{AL}) and available potassium (K_{AL}).

In plants, following analyzes were carried out: the content of macronutrients (N, P, K, Mg) and the content of micronutrients (Cu, Zn, Fe, Mn) in dry matter of aerial parts. All analyzes were made according to RISSA methodology (1980, 1981) and the obtained results were compared with the optimum limits from specialty literature (Bergmann, 1992).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Soil characterization

The characterization of the soil from ARDS Livada is presented in Table 1. From the obtained data the soil shows a neutral-weakly alkaline reaction, the registered pH value being of 7.

The soil humus supply status is low and the nitrogen supply status is moderate. The mobile phosphorus content is high and the mobile potassium content is low.

Table 1

The agrochemical properties of soil from ARDS Livada

Soil fertilisation	Humus, %	Nt, %	pH H ₂ O	P _{AL}	K _{AL}
N ₄₀ P ₄₀ K ₀	1.17	0.14	7.00	66.11	66.66
N ₁₂₀ P ₄₀ K ₀	1.08	0.15	7.23	53.69	60.83

Source: own determinations

Characterization of the mineral nutrition status of plants

Normal values of the contents of N (Figure 1), P (Figure 2), Zn, Cu, Fe and Mn (Figures 5-8) were registered in plants.

Low contents were registered in the case of potassium (Figure 3), below the optimal limit, explainable by the lack of potassium fertilisation and the low state of soil supply with this element. Low Mg contents in the plant were recorded on both fertilisation parcels (Figure 4). Lower values of macro and micronutrient content were recorded on parcel with N40 P40 K0, compared to parcel with N120 P40 K0. Glosa and Delabrad varieties showed the highest nitrogen content in the dry matter of plants.

Fig. 1. The nitrogen content in the aerial parts of winter wheat plants, ear emergence-flowering stage, ARDS Livada
Source: own determinations

Fig. 2. The phosphorus content in the aerial parts of winter wheat plants, ear emergence-flowering stage, ARDS Livada
Source: own determinations

Fig. 3. The potassium content in the aerial parts of winter wheat plants, ear emergence-flowering stage, ARDS Livada
Source: own determinations

Fig. 4. The magnesium content in the aerial parts of winter wheat plants, ear emergence-flowering stage, ARDS Livada
Source: own determinations

Fig. 5. The copper content in the aerial parts of winter wheat plants, ear emergence-flowering stage, ARDS Livada
Source: own determinations

Fig. 6. The zinc content in the aerial parts of winter wheat plants, ear emergence-flowering stage, ARDS Livada
Source: own determinations

Fig. 7. The iron content in the aerial parts of winter wheat plants, ear emergence-flowering stage, ARDS Livada
Source: own determinations

Fig. 8. The manganese content in the aerial parts of winter wheat plants, ear emergence-flowering stage, ARDS Livada
Source: own determinations

The relations between the N content and the contents of P, K, Cu, Zn, Fe and Mn, in the dry matter of the plants, are presented in Figures 9-11. Figure 10 shows that the Fe and Mn contents of plants decrease with increasing nitrogen content in plants, a relationship that can be explained by the low accessibility for plants that these micronutrients have in conditions of a neutral-weakly alkaline soil reaction.

Fig. 9. Data on the relationship between the N content and the P and K content in the aerial parts of winter wheat plants, ear emergence-flowering stage, ARDS Livada
Source: own determinations

Fig. 10. Data on the relationship between the N content and the Mn and Fe content in the aerial parts of winter wheat plants, ear emergence-flowering stage, ARDS Livada
Source: own determinations

The zinc and copper content of the plants (Figure 11) decreases with the increase of the nitrogen content of the plants over the optimal limits.

Fig. 11. Data on the relationship between the N content and the Zn and Cu content in the aerial parts of winter wheat plants, ear emergence-flowering stage, ARDS Livada
Source: own determinations

Excess nitrogen can induce imbalances in Cu and Zn nutrition of plants, the low contents of these micronutrients favoring the attack of *Fusarium graminearum*.

The application of potassium fertilizers and the supplementation of plant nutrition with micronutrients, especially Cu and Zn, are agricultural measures to reduce the incidence of *Fusarium graminearum* attack in the studied area.

Agrochemical means of optimizing plant nutrition seem to be important ways to control the attack of *Fusarium graminearum*, especially since they can reduce the susceptibility of some varieties to the attack of *Fusarium graminearum*, by correcting some nutritional deficiencies.

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CONCLUSIONS

The soil shows a neutral-weakly alkaline reaction with pH values between 7.00-7.23.

The nutrient content in winter wheat plant were within the optimum range for N, P, K, Fe, Cu, Zn, Mn and were below the optimum range for K and Mg.

The application of potassium fertilizers and the supplementation of plant nutrition with micronutrients, especially Cu and Zn, are agricultural measures to reduce the incidence of *Fusarium graminearum* attack in the studied area.

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THE IMPACT OF *CASTANEA SATIVA* AND *AESCULUS HIPPOCASTANUM* AQUEOUS EXTRACTS ON *TRITICUM AESTIVUM* L. SEEDS GERMINATION

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Abstract

*The aim of this study was to determine the influence of aqueous extracts (crude extract, 50%, 25%, 10%, 5%, 2.5% and 1% extract, respectively) prepared from the seeds of *Castanea sativa* (CS) and *Aesculus hippocastanum* (AH) on the germination of *Triticum aestivum* L. caryopsis. Germination characteristics were evaluated over 5 days. High concentrations of CS and AH had an inhibitory effect on the germination of *Triticum aestivum* L. caryopsis. The AH extract most strongly influenced the germination capacity of the seeds, therefore no sample reached the germination rate of 100% by the end of the experiment. The CS extract positively influenced the germination at low concentrations, the samples treated with 10%, 5%, 2.5% and 1% CS extract showing a germination percentage of 97-100%.*

Key words: allelopathy, *Castanea sativa*, *Aesculus hippocastanum*, *Triticum aestivum*, extract

INTRODUCTION

Castanea sativa, the edible chestnut, grows in Romania in a discontinuous area represented by long strips located at the foot of the Carpathian Mountains. The most widespread culture is in the Baia Mare area and occupies the northeastern part of the European natural chain (Bolea et al., 2001). *Aesculus hippocastanum* is known as the wild chestnut. It is original from Southeastern Europe (Avtzis et al., 2002; Walas et al., 2018) and it has been planted in Central and Southern Europe since the 17th century (Ianovici et al., 2012; Datcu et al., 2018). Chestnut seeds are large and weigh about 13-20 g in fresh condition (Daws et al., 2004; Bonner et al., 2008).

Some plants release chemical compounds into their environment from different parts. Usually, these chemicals are secondary metabolites secreted in very small amounts of plants, but playing a very important role in defending plants against microorganisms or other abiotic factors (Reigosa et al., 2006). Allelopathy is a common biological phenomenon by which an organism produces biochemicals known as allelochemical substances. These compounds

influence the growth, survival, development and reproduction of other organisms. Specifically, these substances can stimulate or inhibit plant growth. Allelopathy can have beneficial effects such as weed control, crop protection or negative influence by stimulating autotoxicity or biological invasion. Therefore, allelochemicals can be used as growth regulators or herbicides (Chang et al., 1998).

Many authors indicate that the secondary metabolites of plants can stimulate the seed germination or plant growth, but this only happens at low concentrations (Khan et al., 2009; Kocira et al., 2019). The higher the concentration, the greater the toxic effect is (Sipos et al., 2012; Terzi et al., 2008; Turk et al., 2005; Walas et al., 2018; Ianovici et al., 2012). Chestnut seeds contain many biologically active compounds that influence the preservation and germination of seeds, as well as the growth and development of seedlings (Cheng et al., 2015). In this study we tried to find out how different aqueous extracts of *C. sativa* and *A. hippocastanum* influence the germination of *Triticum aestivum* L. seeds.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The biological material consisted of carefully selected caryopsis of *Triticum aestivum* L., Trublion variety, C1, semi-rotten wheat, harvest year 2020. The two aqueous extracts were prepared from the seed of *C. sativa* (CS) and *A. hippocastanum* (AH) respectively, both varieties of chestnut being harvested in 2019. The seeds were stored and kept in a room with a humidity of 40% and a constant temperature of 24°C until 2021 when they were used. 50 g of vegetable material, crushed to a size of 1 mm, were mixed with 100 mL of double distilled water. The mixture was left at room temperature for 24 hours and stirred from time to time, then filtered through 150 mm size filter paper. After filtration, the extract was made up to 100 mL with double distilled water (crude extract, 100% extract) and kept at 4°C until the beginning of the experiment. Dilutions of 50%, 25%, 10%, 5%, 2.5% and 1%, respectively were made from the crude extract.

T. aestivum seeds were carefully selected to have the same size and not be physically damaged. The seeds were washed with running water for 30 minutes, then the caryopsis were immersed in 70° ethyl alcohol for 30 seconds and then rinsed for one minute with double-distilled water. This process was done 3 times. Ten caryopsis were placed on a filter paper in a Petri dish and 5 mL of seed extract was added. The control was prepared by adding 5 mL of

double distilled water. Each experiment was performed in triplicate for the extracts of every concentration. The readings were made for 5 days.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The values of the parameters registered for the control (C) were considered as reference (100%), to which the values of the samples (V1-crude extract, V2-50% extract, V3-25% extract, V4-10% extract, V5-5% extract, V6-2.5% extract and V7-1% extract) were reported. From the first day of the experiment there is a significant difference between the two extracts (CS and AH) and the control. High concentrations of CS and AH extracts caused the germination of a smaller number of caryopsis (Tables 1 and 2).

Caryopsis treated with V5CS, V6CS and V7CS, respectively had a higher germination rate than the control of up to +57% (V5CS), while the caryopsis treated with V1CS and V2CS did not germinate at all on the first day. On day 2, sample V5CS maintains a higher germination rate than the control with a value of +28%. On the last day of the experiment, it can be seen that the seeds treated with V4CS, V5CS, V6CS and V7CS, respectively had a germination percentage of over 97%, very similar to that of the control (100%). The V1CS and V2CS were the ones that most inhibited the germination of caryopsis (inhibition of 76.7% and 73.4%, respectively on day 5) (Table 1, Fig. 1).

The seeds treated with V1AH (crude extract) and V2AH, respectively did not germinate at all until the end of the experiment. The V3AH sample strongly inhibited germination, only 30% of the seeds being germinated at the end of the 5 days (70% inhibition compared to the control). Similar to CS extracts, some dilutions produced a higher germination rate than the control in the early days. In this case there were V6AH (+45.8%) and V7AH (+28.5%). No samples reached the germination rate of 100% by the end of the experiment, however the V6AH and V7AH samples gave very good results with germination rates of at least 90% (Table 2, Fig. 2).

The results of the experiment show differences between CS and AH extracts. It can be seen that the *A. hippocastanum* (AH) extract more strongly inhibits the germination of wheat seeds compared to *C. sativa* (CS) extract, which suggests the different composition of the two extracts.

Table 1

The GF values for control (C) and GF values for samples treated with *Castanea sativa* (CS) extract

Parameters	Exp. V.	V0 (C)		V1 (100%CS)		V2 (50%CS)		V3 (25%CS)		V4 (10%CS)		V5 (5%CS)		V6 (2.5%CS)		V7 (1%CS)	
		Abs. val.	% Val	Abs. val.	% Val.	Abs. val.	% Val.	Abs. val.	% Val.	Abs. val.	% Val.	Abs. val.	% Val.	Abs. val.	% Val.	Abs. val.	% Val.
GF No	1	14	100	0	0	0	0	4	28.6	13	92	22	157	17	121.4	20	142.9
	2	21	100	2	4.7	2	4.7	15	71.4	24	114	27	128	23	109	21	100
	3	28	100	5	17.9	4	14.3	17	60.7	25	89.3	28	100	26	92.9	24	85.7
	4	30	100	6	20	6	20	18	60	26	86.7	30	100	28	93.3	27	90
	5	30	100	7	23.3	8	26.6	19	63.3	30	100	30	100	30	100	29	96.6

Table 2

The GF values for control (C) and GF values for samples treated with *Aesculus hippocastanum* (AH) extract

Parameters	Exp. V.**	V0 (C)		V1 (100%AH)		V2 (50%AH)		V3 (25%AH)		V4 (10%AH)		V5 (5%AH)		V6 (2.5%AH)		V7 (1%AH)	
		Abs. Val.	% Val.	Abs. Val.	% Val.	Abs. Val.	% Val.	Abs. Val.	% Val.	Abs. Val.	% Val	Abs. Val.	% Val.	Abs. Val.	% Val.	Abs. Val.	% Val.
GF*	1	14	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	28.5	10	71.4	20	145.8	18	128.5
	2	21	100	0	0	0	0	4	19	11	52.4	12	57.1	21	100	24	114.2
	3	28	100	0	0	0	0	8	28.6	11	39.3	13	46.4	23	82.1	25	89.3
	4	30	100	0	0	0	0	8	26.6	12	40	13	43.3	24	80	28	93.3
	5	30	100	0	0	0	0	9	30	14	46.6	16	53.3	27	90	28	93.3

*GF – Germinative faculty, **Exp. V. – experimental variant (V0, V1, V2, V3, V4, V5, V6, V7), Abs. val. - number of germinated seeds, % Val - % of germinated seeds relative to % Val of the control which is considered 100%

Fig.1. The influence of *Castanea sativa* extracts on the germination of *Triticum aestivum* seeds

Fig.2. The influence of *Aesculus hippocastanum* extracts on the germination of *Triticum aestivum* seeds

CONCLUSIONS

Studies show that the percentage of germinated and non-germinated seeds is strongly influenced by the concentration of extracts used (Avtzis et al., 2002). As can be seen in the previous graphs, the extracts of *C. sativa* and *A. hippocastanum* greatly inhibited the seed germination in our study. The values obtained were directly proportional to the concentrations of the extracts used, respectively the higher the concentration of the extract, the more strongly the germination of *T. aestivum* L. caryopsis was inhibited. These results suggest a cytotoxic effect of the studied extracts and their potential as a natural herbicide. On the other hand, there are samples of *T. aestivum* seeds treated with *C. sativa* extracts where a higher germination capacity of the control in the first days of the experiment was observed. Similar results have been reported by other allelopathy studies (Melo et al., 2001; França et al., 2008; Silva et al., 2009; Silva-Candido et al., 2010; Silva et al., 2011).

Chiang (Chiang et al., 2003) mentioned that the effect of plant extracts on seed germination comes from different chemical constituents present in these plants. Chemical components (secondary metabolites) can influence seed germination and plant productivity. Inhibition effects usually result from a combination of allelochemicals that interfere with various physiological processes in the recipient plant (Mominul Islam et al., 2018). Some flavonoids have an allelopathic effect and are able to increase the levels of reactive oxygen species causing the inhibition of germination (Kumar et al., 2010). The allelopathic effect on germination rate is due to interference that blocks or delays the progress of metabolic processes during the germination process. The germination rate index measures how long it takes for caryopsis to germinate. The presence of allelochemicals can decrease the rate of development and translocation of endosperm nutrients to the embryo (Ferreira et al., 2004).

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ANALYSIS OF ROMANIAN AGRICULTURE DEVELOPMENT AFTER ACCESSION TO THE EU

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***Abstract.** Within Romania's economy, agriculture is one of the branches of major importance that can contribute to the relaunch of the country's economic growth (UAAs in 2016 were 12,502,000 ha, 6% lower than in 2010) since the role of agriculture cannot substitute any other economic activity, as the demand for food is essential and is permanent for human existence, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, agriculture provides the necessary gross material for relaunching many other industries (agri-foods, textiles, chemicals, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, craftsmanship, etc.) and for export. In this paper, the authors analyse the evolution of agriculture in Romania after joining the E.U. The contribution of agriculture to economic development can be determined by an analysis of the multiple functions it fulfils, as well as by its contribution to equilibrium and social stability and not only, in the light of the share of this branch in the formation of results indicators such as gross domestic product and value added.*

Key words: agriculture, Romania, support, funding, accession

INTRODUCTION

Four major system changes, in the last century, appreciated as four fractures of Romanian agrarian structures – the great agrarian reform in 1921, the agrarian reform in 1945, the collectivization of agriculture during the period 1949-1962 and the effects of the Law of the Land Fund (and of its related laws) in 1991 – made impossible the design and the application of a **long-term Romanian agricultural project**, like the majority of Western European countries. Major successive system changes have generated instability and, more seriously, the absence of continuity and sustainability of the national agricultural system.

The consequences of agricultural policies (reforms, restructuring, adjustments) applied contradictorily, free of continuity after 1989, generated fluid, highly bipolarized, unstructured, non-performing, non-competitive,

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non-concurrently small households (comprising more than 95% of the number of holdings and over 5,000,000 ha of land); the transition from large agricultural units (IAS, CAP), characteristic of Oriental socialism from the communist period, to **large corporate agricultural holdings** (associations, societies), most currently in the phase of primary capitalism of land-ownership type, where about 12,000 large and very large holdings cumulate an eligible European agricultural area of about 5,000,000 ha (over 50% of the arable land of the best quality), as well as a small share of medium-sized farms, characteristic of Western European agriculture, which hold only about 10% of the country's arable land.

The privatization process in Romania began in 1990, proving to be a much more complex and difficult process than originally thought. Romanian agriculture has evolved during the period after 1990 under the influence of the phenomena generated by the transition to the market economy, on the background of acute lack of financial and material resources as well as of an unfavourable international situation. Law 18 from 1991 of the Land Fund divided agricultural areas into small plots and led to their dispersal, plus the depreciation of the material basis, investment stagnation, asset destruction as well as errors in the management of state-owned assets and supporting the making-up process of a private agriculture, which has led to a sharp decline in the profitability of agricultural holdings.

At national level, agriculture has been a basic branch in the structure of the economy, with a strong share in the formation of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Figure 1).

Source: After the Statistical Yearbook of Romania

Figure 1. Share of agriculture and forestry in GDP (Total GDP, Agriculture and forestry in GDP, % of GDP)

Although the contribution of agriculture to GDP formation has fallen long enough during the analysed period, it continues to have a high share

(4.4% in 2018) compared to developed E.U. member countries, where agricultural contribution to the GDP formation does not exceed 2%.

In developed countries, agriculture has a decreasing share of the gross added value (GAV), which is justified by the development of other sectors of activity such as services, trade, constructions, finances, banking, insurance, whose share of the GAV is increasing.

In Romania, the contribution of agriculture to total GAV in 2018 was 4.8%, while the E.U. average was 1.7%. The large share of Romanian agriculture compared to the other E.U. member states in the GAV formation at the economy level is explained by the far too slow process of increasing the share of services and trade in total gross added value

As regards investments in Romania's agriculture during the analysed period, they accounted for an average of 5.38% of the total investments. Under these circumstances, one cannot speak of investment for development but, largely, only of capital allocations to replace fixed assets.

The evolution of the share of the two sectors of agriculture highlights a low share of animal husbandry production that does not exceed the share of 37% throughout the analysed period (only 27.68% in 2018, and agricultural services, 1.42%), according to the data in the Figure 2.

Source: After the Statistical Yearbook of Romania

Figure 2. Evolution of the share of sectors in agriculture (Agricultural services, Animal husbandry, Cropping)

The current situation of Romanian agriculture is characterized by multiple economic and social issues: the existence of numerous small non-viable farms and the excessive parcelling of land on the one hand and, on the other hand, the emergence of large and very large farms of corporate type, currently in the phase of primary capitalism of land-ownership type. Thus, in 2016, 12,310 farms of over 100 ha, i.e., **0.36% of the total Romanian farms**

(3,422,030), **share 47.78% of Romanian UAAs** (12,502,000 ha), i.e., 5,973,450 ha of agricultural land, and 2,480,770 farms with below 2 ha, i.e., **72.49% of the total farms, use 12.32% of the total UAAs, i.e., 1,539,790 ha of agricultural land.**

Regarding the number of farmers by areas, data from APIA confirms that, in 2016, there was a concentration of farms up to 50 ha. Thus, 91.3% of holdings up to 50 ha, i.e., 823.119 holdings use an area of about 3,700,000 ha, i.e., 40.28% of UAAs, and **2,427 holdings above 500 ha (0.27% of the total) exploit 2,850,000 ha of UAAs, i.e., 31.07%.**

Farms above 1,000 ha (0.1% of total farms), i.e., **868 farms, benefit from direct payments for an area of 1,750,000 ha**, with the mention that the average size of these farms is 2,027 ha.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In carrying out this analysis, we started from the premise that, in the economy of each country, irrespective of its development, agriculture, through the natural and human resources available, by its contribution to the creation of gross domestic product, and also by participation in domestic and foreign trade in agri-food products, obviously holds an important position. Agriculture is the economic branch that must ensure the food security of any people. The information analysed was collected through documentary study of specialized literature in the field of the topic addressed and investigated. The research methodology included the statistical analysis of primary data using the Microsoft Excel quantitative analysis program (tables, charts).

One of the methods used to prepare the raw analysis material was the documentation of the official databases provided by the National Institute of Statistics (INS - Tempo Online), data collections published by EUROSTAT, as well as various publications or complementary information taken from the Internet.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Romanian rural economy is predominantly agrarian because, in Romania, agricultural economy itself (mainly primary) shares 60.5% of its structure, compared to only 14.1% in the E.U. The profoundly distorted structure of the Romanian rural economy also determines a similar structure of the rural population occupied by sectors of activity (64.2% primary sector, of which 56.6% in agriculture, 18.5% in the secondary sector, 17.3% in the tertiary sector). Investments in the rural food and non-agricultural economies, in addition to ensuring the increase in gross added value by processing agricultural and non-agricultural commodities from local resources, have a great advantage, both in times of crisis and recession and in economic growth, in the sense of creating

new jobs (for the use and stabilization of local labour), revitalizing rural localities, particularly those in disadvantaged and peripheral areas.

Both rural economy as a whole and agri-food economy as an important element of the rural economy present different structures in Romania compared to the European Union. Thus, if the Romanian rural economy is predominantly agricultural (about two-thirds, 60.5%) or agri-food (more than three-fourths, 78.1%), in the European Union rural economy is dominated by the economy of services (with a share of 42.2%, 2% more than the agri-food economy). Great differences are also in terms of agri-food economy. While turning agricultural raw materials in food (gross value-added carriers) has a share of more than half of the value of the agri-food economy in the European Union, in our country the production of agricultural raw materials (agricultural economy) has a much higher share of the total amount of final agri-food production (over 75%).

Given the precarious rural structure of Romania today, we believe that it is necessary **to create an environment for stimulating investments in rural areas for the extension of primary agricultural products processing SMEs in the non-agricultural rural economy** must become a permanent concern of the local authorities through the achievement, in the process of economic decentralization and decision-making, in rural localities (or rural areas) with a labour force surplus, of **village industrial macrozones**, with county or regional financial support, equipped with the utilities required by industrial activities (electricity, heat, gas, water, sewage, access and interior roads, telecommunications, etc.), according to the model of those created long time ago in the rural areas of E.U. countries.

In conclusion, in addition to the low agricultural production per agricultural worker, the structures of the rural and agri-food economy are still far from what we can call **a competitive rural economy in Romania**.

The poorly developed rural economy has immediate and permanent consequences, visible and negative effects on the Romanian village: sharp demographic aging, youth leaving rural localities through urban exodus or external migration, phenomena that accentuate the social desertification of the Romanian village.

If Romania's agriculture is characterized by a high degree of fragmentation of agricultural areas, low investments, poorly qualified people, aged labour force and a precarious material situation that makes people live at the limit of subsistence, we believe that **the relaunch of agriculture, with its two sectors – plant and animal – so important for our country's economy can only be achieved by attracting European funds and massive investment in this branch**.

In the financial period 2007-2013, the main form of support for agricultural producers was represented by direct payments. Table 2 presents the budget allocated to support these payments to E.U. member states.

Expenditure in the CAP budget for direct payments funding amounted to € 286,000,000,000 for the period 2007-2013. It can be seen that there are large differences between E.U. countries in terms of community support for direct payments and rural development. In the E.U.-15 countries, 83% of the allocated amounts are for direct payments, whereas this value is only 52% in NSM-12. As a result, the second pillar – rural development – is treated as more important in the new member states than in the old member states. This difference revealed that the new member states were in a transition period, gradual implementation of direct payments (25% in the first year after accession, 30% in the second year, 35% in the third year, 40% in the fourth year, following an annual growth of 10%, reaching 100% in the 10th year after accession). The highest shares of their financial packs for direct payments were France, Belgium, The Netherlands, the United Kingdom and Denmark, with an allocation between 90-94% of the funds for this purpose, reserving only 6-10% for rural development. Countries like Portugal, Austria, Finland, Luxembourg, Sweden and Italy have directed between 50-75% of total funds, and for rural development, 25-50%. In NSM-12, the sharing between the two support directions was less pronounced; as a whole, the new member states have allocated half of the funds for direct payments and half payments for rural development, except for Malta, with 79% of the total funds for the pillar two of the CAP.

In absolute value, the largest five beneficiaries of Community funds for **direct payments** were France (€ 58,000,000,000), Germany (€ 40,000,000,000), Spain (€ 32,000,000,000), United Kingdom (€ 28,000,000,000) and Italy (€ 27,000,000,000), and the largest five **rural development** fund users were Poland (€ 13,000,000,000), Italy, Germany and Romania (€ 8,000,000,000) and Spain (€ 7,000,000,000). Therefore, the old member countries are those that have absorbed most of the Community funds for agriculture and rural development, which is understandable to some extent, if we consider that these countries create 85% of the gross added value of the European Union agriculture. The budgetary financial support of farmers in the new member states is made to a much smaller extent, with repercussions on their ability to turn and develop into viable commercial farms. By calculating the level of direct payments relative to the eligible agricultural area and the agricultural area used, the comparison with other E.U. member states, highlights the large difference between the level of subsidization of Romania's agriculture and that of other states (Figure 3)

Source: Council for the Rural Area, The Netherlands, 2008

Figure 3. Direct payments from the E.U. budget per ha of eligible area (€/ha eligible) EU-27

Direct payments per eligible hectare in Romania (annual average of 90 €/ha) account for only 67.2% of the average annual amount of E.U.-12 budget allocations, and 31.9% of the average annual level per eligible hectare of the states in the E.U.-15.

The large difference between the average annual level of payments to Romania and the average annual level of payments granted to the other member states has as a cause both the historical yield underlying the annual limits (the product between the historical yield, different from one state to another, and a fixed amount per t, equal for all member states) and the progressive percentages allocated annually calculated for each member state. From this point of view, we remind that the reference production or historical yield (average of the production in the main crops in 2000-2002), taken into account for Romania was 2.65 t/ha compared to 4.77 t/ha the reference production of E.U.-15 states, 4.0 t/ha the reference production of the 10 new member states (which joined the E.U. in 2004) or by 4.73 in Hungary, 4.2 in the case of Czech Republic, 4.06 in the case of Slovakia, 3.0 in the case of Poland.

The aforementioned gaps have increased more since, in the case of Romania, there is a very large agricultural area considered ineligible (a difference of 5,037,000 ha between the agricultural area used by 13,753,000 ha in 2007 and the agricultural area eligible of 8,716,000 ha), an unacceptable difference eligible due to the excessive crushing of the land (holding less than 1 ha or the fragmentation of a ha in more than 3 plots). Analysing the average of direct payments on a hectare of agricultural area used from the E.U. budget, throughout the 2007-2013 interval (Figure 4), we find that Romania with a payment of 57 €/ha ranked last in the E.U.-27 with only 11.2% of Greece level (508 €/ha), 12.8% of the Netherlands level (444 €/ha), 12.9% of Belgium level (443 €/ha), 18.7% of the France level (304 €/ha), 26% of Hungary level (219 €/ha), and 41% of Poland level (139 €/ha).

Source: Council for The Rural Area, The Netherlands, 2008

Figure 4. Direct payments from the E.U. budget per ha of UAA (€/ha UAA) annual average 2007-2013 in E.U.-27 countries

In addition to direct payments granted through the single area payment scheme, Romanian farmers have also benefited from other support measures. Financial resources for agriculture, throughout the 2007-2013 financial period, can be grouped into three major categories after the source of support funding.

Payments from the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF): Direct SAPS payments; Specific aid scheme granted according to art. 68 of the Reg. CE no. 73/2009; Separate payment scheme; Payment scheme for energy crops; Transitional tomato payment scheme for processing, 100% assured funding from the EAGF; Market measures with funding from the EAGF and the national budget; Programs for the promotion of agricultural products on domestic markets and third countries and export refunds.

Payments representing financial support from the national budget (BN): Complementary national payments in the plant and animal sector; State aid in agriculture for payment of insurance premiums; Life annuity; State aid for Diesel used in agriculture.

Payments from the European Agriculture and Rural Development Fund (EAFRD) for Axis II measures in the National Rural Development Program 2007-2013: Measure 211 “Payments for the disadvantaged mountain area”; Measure 212 “Payments for disadvantaged areas - other than mountain”; Measure 214 “Payments for agri-environment”; Measure 215 “Payments for animal welfare”. These forms of support were managed by the Agency for Payments and Intervention for Agriculture (APIA), the body operating under the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development under Law 1/2004 with subsequent amendments and completions, being the institution responsible for the implementation of the Common Agricultural Policy in Romania. Table 1 presents the funds

managed by APIA in 2007-2014.

Table 1.

Funds managed by APIA in 2007-2014 (millions of €)

Financing source	Limited amount 2007-2014	Payments made 2007-2014	Absorption level (%)
FEGA	7,794	7,660	98.33
FEADR and BN, for the measures in Axis II	3,160	3,040	96.14
TOTAL	10,954	10,700	97.70

Note: FEGA = European Agricultural Guarantee Fund; EAFRD = European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development; BN = National Budget

Source: MADR, 2015

APIA's Annual Activity Report for 2015 shows that the total value of allocations and payments made throughout the 2007-2014 interval, by types of resources, according to data in Table 5 and Figure 5. We mention that in the selected range (2007-2014), payments made in the last year (2014) also include part of the previous year's allocations in view of maintaining for 2014 the payment schemes of the period 2007-2013. For 2014, the level of payments per areas was granted according to the same criteria as during the period 2007-2013.

Source: After MADR

Figure 5. Allocations and payments made by APIA in 2007-2014 (millions of €)

In conclusion, it can be appreciated that the implementation of the European agricultural financing mechanism during this period was with syncopes, both in terms of the creation of the application structures (the Agency for Payments and Intervention for Agriculture), and in terms of payments proper to holdings upon prioritizing their destination.

The graphical representation of the direct payments reported to UAA for each member state in 2019 (Figure 6) is relevant for assessments of these differences.

With all the changes, there are still significant differences in the support per ha for each member state, further differences that generate major imbalances, unfair or discriminatory competition, with obvious negative effects, hard to bear by the poor states of the European Union such as Romania.

Source: After DG AGRI data

Figure 6. Support for direct payments reported to UAA from 2019 (€/ha)

It is noted that the amounts received by the farmers are influenced by the farm size class, the farmer's age and the application of certain agri-environment conditions. The highest subsidy is for the farmers holding 5-30 ha, as this category of farmers benefits from a significant redistributive payment. Thus, a farmer holding 5-30 ha got, in 2015, a maximum of 229.04 €/ha, and in 2019 a maximum of 255.19 €/ha. The lowest subsidies per ha was for the farmers holding farms larger than 60 ha. In these farms, payments varied between a minimum of 138.85 €/ha in 2015, and a maximum of 158.04 €/ha, reaching a minimum of 161.92 €/ha in 2019, and a maximum of 175.24 €/ha (if the farmer also benefited from transient national aids).

Table 2.

Value of payments per ha made to Romanian farmers in 2015-2019, (€/ha)

Farm size	Payment schemes	2015		2016		2017		2018		2019	
		Max		Max		Max		Max		Max	
1-5 ha	SAPS	Max	79.73	Max	96.88	Max	97.24	Max	102.56	Max	102.60
	Greening	182.97	59.12	199.84	57.37	199.73	57.17	206.33	58.23	211.48	59.32
	Redistributive		5.00		5.00		5.00		5.00		5.00
	Young farmer	Min	19.93	Min	22.87	Min	24.31	Min	25.84	Min	31.24
	ANT	143.85	19.19	159.25	17.72	159.41	16.01	165.79	14.70	166.92	13.32
5-30 ha	SAPS	Max	79.73	Max	96.88	Max	97.24	Max	102.56	Max	102.60
	Greening	229.04	59.12	243.34	57.37	243.05	57.17	251.69	58.23	255.19	59.32
	Redistributive	Min	51.07	Min	48.50	Min	48.32	Min	50.36	Min	48.71
	Young farmer	189.92	19.93	202.75	22.87	202.73	24.31	211.15	25.84	210.63	31.24
	ANT I		19.19		17.72		16.01		14.70		13.32
30-60 ha	SAPS	Max	79.73	Max	96.88	Max	97.24	Max	102.56	Max	102.60

	Greening	177.97	59.12	194.84	57.37	194.73	57.17	201.33	58.23	206.48	59.32
	Redistributive	Min	0	Min	0	Min	0	Min	0	Min	0
	Young farmer	138.85	19.93	154.25	22.87	154.41	24.31	160.79	25.84	161.92	31.24
	ANT		19.19		17.72		16.01		14.70		13.32
>60 ha	SAPS	Max	79.73	Max	96.88	Max	97.24	Max	102.56	Max	102.60
	Greening	158.04	59.12	171.97	57.37	170.42	57.17	175.49	58.23	175.24	59.32
	Redistributive	Min	0	Min	0	Min	0	Min	0	Min	0
	Young farmer	138.85	0	154.25	0	154.41	0	160.79	0	161.92	0
	ANT		19.19		17.72		16.01		14.70		13.32

Note: SAPS = Payments under the unique surface payment scheme; Conversion = Payments under the scheme for agricultural practices for climate and environment; Redistributive = Payments under the redistributive payment scheme; Young Farmer = Payments in the Payment Scheme for Young Farmers; ANT = Payments under the Scheme on Transitional National Aid

Source: After MADR reports

CONCLUSIONS

In the field of agricultural policies and their implementing instruments, Romania has been constantly attempting to meet the short-term challenges of more or less electoral political objectives, conditionalities imposed from abroad by international financial bodies or by international organizations whose member Romania wishes to become. These challenges, on the short and medium term, have practically hold its strategies or, better, have been arguments to justify the absence of a political approach of a clear agricultural strategy in the long run.

In our opinion, the starting point of the agriculture development strategy should take into account **a land policy, a fiscal policy in agriculture, a socio-professional policy defining the professional status of the farmer, a policy of developing infrastructure and basic services for agriculture**, topics that need to be addressed mentioning that the solutions proposed to solve the problems in these areas also depend on how the production potential of the different agricultural sectors can be highlighted.

Romania needs a multi-functional, competitive agriculture, complementary to the agriculture of the other European Union countries, as well as major decisions in support of different (competitive and complementary) systems of agriculture.

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GLOBAL STUDY ON THE PRODUCTION AND MARKETING OF BARLEY

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Abstract

This study captured the evolution of barley production and marketing worldwide during 2015-2019. In order to be able to highlight as well as possible this evolution, it was required to present and analyze specific indicators such as: the area cultivated with barley at global level; total barley production worldwide; average yield per hectare of barley worldwide; imports and exports of barley recorded worldwide.

Barley is cultivated in all major regions of the globe, but there are substantial differences in terms of production. Barley grown around the globe is used on the one hand, in human food and animal feed, and on the other hand, in various industries.

In 2019, Europe made 60.15% of the world's barley production, which places it on the first place in the top of barley producers. The data that formed the basis for the elaboration of this work were provided by the FAO website.

Key words: *barley, world barley production, barley imports and exports*

INTRODUCTION

Barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) is one of the species of cereal plants that belongs to the genus *Hordeum*, being included in the family *Poaceae*. The region of origin afferent to barley is found in Near East, but also, in the Eastern Balkan area (<https://ro.wikipedia.org/wiki/Orz>, 2021).

Barley belonging to the genus *Hordeum* L., includes 27 wild species and one cultivated. An important aspect was noticed, namely, of the wild species, 16 are perennial and the rest are annual (Ion, 2010).

Barley has a wide spread around the globe, being the only cereal that reaches 70 degrees north latitude. Barley is also an important cereal crop for regions where very high temperatures are recorded, such as those in North Africa (Ifrim, 2010).

Currently, barley has a number of uses such as: human food; animal feed; use in different industries, it is widely used in the beer industry (Ifrim, 2010; Ion, 2010).

It should be remembered, a very important aspect, namely that the barley grains used in animal feed have an increased nutritional value and a

high degree of digestibility, which brings them much closer to the forage value of the maize grains.

The use of barley grains in animal feed is important, because concentrated feed can be used especially for dairy animals, young animals and for those put to fattening (Ion, 2010; Medelete and Pânzaru, 2013; Dunăreanu et al., 2021).

The specific chemical composition of the barley grains is as follows: carbohydrates (55-65%); protein (9.5-14%); 2-3% fat (2-3%); cellulose (4-7%) and ash (2-3%).

Barley grains are an important matter for the industries of alcohol, glucose, dextrin, etc Because of this, producers who use barley as raw material are very interested on the one hand, to purchase good quality barley, and on the other hand, to buy on the international market at a better price.

Barley remains an important cereal crop for both the population and the animal feed (Derbala and Hashad, 2013; Medelete, 2016; Porumb et al., 2019).

Photo 1. Barley

Source: <https://pixabay.com/ro/photos/orz-cereale-cultura-putere-c%C3%A2mp-4179406/>

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study highlighted the evolution of barley production and its marketing worldwide for the period 2015-2019. In the present work were analyzed a series of specific indicators for the production and marketing of barley.

The main indicators that have been presented and analyzed in the present work are: total area cultivated with barley worldwide; total barley production worldwide; the average yield per hectare of barley achieved worldwide; imports and exports of barley worldwide.

The statistical data underlying this study were taken from the FAOSTAT website.

In order to achieve this paperwork, numerous specialized materials were studied, and the results of the research were presented in tables and in graphic form.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the data published by FAOSTAT regarding the total area cultivated with barley worldwide, it was found that they varied for the period 2015-2019 (Table 1).

The most significant barley-growing area worldwide was recorded in 2019 (51,149,869 ha), and the smallest cultivated area was recorded in 2017 (47,878,057 ha). In 2019, the total area cultivated with barley worldwide registered an increase of 2.63%, compared to 2015.

At the continental level, the total area cultivated with barley varied from one year to the next.

From the presented data it can be seen that Europe occupies the first place at regional level in terms of area cultivated with barley. Here, the smallest area was recorded in 2017 (23,224,858 ha), and the largest area was of 24,222,012 ha (2019).

In 2019, in Europe, the area cultivated with barley increased insignificantly, by only 0.20%, compared to 2015.

On the next position in the top of barley growers at regional level is Asia. Here, the cultivated area increased from 11,475,058 ha (2015) to 12,582,974 ha (2019).

The smallest cultivated area with barley in Asia was of 9,924,782 ha (2017). In 2019, the area cultivated with barley in Asia, increased by 9.65%, compared to 2015. The third place at regional level is occupied by the Americas.

Table 1

The evolution of the barley cultivated area worldwide, during 2015-2019 (ha)

Specification	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2019/2015 (%)
World-total	49,838,421	48,373,562	47,878,057	48,028,284	51,149,869	102.63
Africa	4,825,117	4,303,877	5,194,379	4,556,707	4,116,152	85.30
Americas	5,224,182	5,295,726	4,657,969	5,244,305	5,736,686	109.81
Asia	11,475,058	10,473,752	9,924,782	10,573,658	12,582,974	109.65
Europe	24,171,859	24,140,667	23,224,858	23,473,185	24,222,012	100.20
Oceania	4,142,205	4,159,540	4,876,069	4,180,429	4,492,045	108.44

Source: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL> ; own calculations

The largest area cultivated with barley was highlighted in 2019 (5,736,686 ha). In 2019, the area cultivated with barley increased by 9.81%, compared to 2015.

The next position in this ranking is occupied by Africa. Here, the largest area was recorded in 2017 (5,194,379 ha). In 2019, the area cultivated with barley decreased by 14.70%, compared to 2015.

The last position in this ranking is occupied by Oceania. In 2019, Oceania cultivated 8.78% of the world's barley-grown area. The largest barley area in Oceania was of 4,876,069 ha (2017) (Figure 1). In 2019, the area cultivated with barley increased by 8.44%, compared to 2015.

Fig.1. Total area cultivated with barley worldwide, during 2015-2019 (ha)

Source: Own design based on FAOSTAT database 2021

The total barley production achieved worldwide recorded oscillations from one year to another during the analyzed period (Table 2 and Figure 2).

The most significant barley production worldwide was in 2019 (158,979,610 tons). From the data presented in the table below, it can be seen that in 2019, the world production of barley increased by 7.61%, compared to 2015.

At regional level, the largest barley productions were obtained in Europe. These productions ranged from 83,369,457 tons to 95,634,161 tons. In 2019, the total production of barley in Europe increased by 4.85%, compared to 2015.

Asia ranks second in the ranking of barley producers worldwide. In 2019, production increased by 13.36%, compared to 2015.

Table 2

Evolution of total barley production worldwide, during 2015-2019 (tons)

Specification	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2019/2015 (%)
World-total	147,730,419	145,865,103	148,478,878	139,743,307	158,979,610	107.61
Africa	7,561,489	4,842,505	6,566,569	7,698,573	6,884,764	91.05
Americas	17,333,411	20,239,308	17,103,399	18,961,808	21,699,045	125.18
Asia	22,545,084	21,137,228	20,325,523	20,079,913	25,559,043	113.36
Europe	91,206,970	90,289,602	90,679,798	83,369,457	95,634,161	104.85
Oceania	9,083,465	9,356,460	13,803,589	9,633,556	9,202,597	101.31

Source: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL> ; own calculations

In America, the most significant barley production was recorded in 2019 (21,699,045 tons). Smaller productions were obtained in Africa and Oceania. In 2019, barley production increased by 1.31% in Oceania compared to 2015. In Africa, in 2019, barley production decreased by 8.95%, compared to 2015.

The barley production achieved at global level was determined by a series of factors, of which the most representatives are: the cultivated area; the degree of fertilization, the level of precipitations, etc.

Fig. 2. Total production of barley worldwide, during 2015-2019 (tons)

Source: Own design based on FAOSTAT database 2021

The average yield per hectare for the barley crop recorded worldwide, varied from one year to another in the period under analysis (Table 3). The highest average yield per hectare of barley in the world was

achieved in 2019 (3,108 kg/ha). In 2019, the average barley production increased by 4.85%, compared to 2015.

Europe in the analyzed period obtained the highest yields for barley production, they varied between 3,552 kg/ha - 3,948 kg/ha. In 2019, the average yield per hectare of barley in Europe increased by 4.63%, compared to 2015.

This increase in the average yield per hectare of barley in Europe is almost equal, with the increase recorded worldwide for the same analyzed period.

America ranks second in terms of average yield per hectare achieved for the barley crop. The most significant average yield per hectare of barley was achieved in 2016 (3,822 kg/ha). In 2019, the average yield per hectare of barley increased by 14.01%, compared to 2015.

Table 3

The evolution of the average yield per hectare for the barley crop worldwide, during 2015-2019 (kg/ha)

Specification	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2019/2015 (%)
World-total	2,964	3,015	3,101	2,910	3,108	104.85
Africa	1,567	1,125	1,264	1,690	1,673	106.76
Americas	3,318	3,822	3,671	3,616	3,783	114.01
Asia	1,965	2,018	2,048	1,899	2,031	103.35
Europe	3,773	3,740	3,904	3,552	3,948	104.63
Oceania	2,193	2,249	2,830	2,304	2,049	93.43

Source: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL> ; own calculations

Oceania ranks third in the regional ranking in terms of average yield per hectare of barley. The most significant average yield per hectare of barley was achieved in 2017 (2,830 kg/ha). In 2019, the average yield per hectare of barley decreased by 6.57%, compared to 2015.

Asia, although it ranks 2nd in terms of barley production obtained, it ranks fourth in terms of yield per hectare. The most significant yield per hectare achieved for the barley crop was 2,048 kg/ha (2017). In 2019, the yield per hectare increased by 3.35%, compared to 2015.

Africa occupies the last position at regional level in terms of yield per hectare for barley production. The highest yield was recorded in 2018 (1,690 kg/ha). Here, in 2019, the average yield per hectare for the barley crop increased by 6.76%, compared to 2015.

Fig. 3. Average production per hectare of barley worldwide, for the period 2015-2019 (kg /ha)

Source: Own design based on FAOSTAT database 2021

World trade in barley during 2015-2019 reflected a differentiated evolution. In table no.4 is presented the evolution of worldwide imports and exports of barley in the period 2015-2019.

Quantitative barley imports recorded worldwide fluctuated from one year to the next. The most representative quantitative imports of barley were in 2017 (39,237,488 tons), and the smallest were in 2019 (31,330,240 tons). In 2019, quantitative barley imports decreased by 12.38%, compared to 2015.

Table 4

Evolution of worldwide barley imports and exports, in the period 2015-2019 (tons)

Specification	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2019/2015 (%)
Import	35,754,892	33,964,238	39,237,488	34,525,663	31,330,240	87.62
Export	38,318,647	35,109,192	39,573,720	36,543,704	31,061,984	81.06

Source: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL> ; own calculations

Quantitative barley exports changed between 2015 and 2019. The most significant exports were recorded in 2017 (39,573,720 tons), and the smallest were in 2019 (31,061,984 tons). In 2019, world barley exports decreased by 18.94%, compared to 2015.

From the statistical data presented in Table no. 4 for the period 2015-2018 it can be noted that the world exports of barley were superior to the world imports of barley. There was only one exception, namely 2019, when world barley imports overthrew world exports by 268,256 tons.

Fig. 4. Worldwide imports and exports of barley, during the period 2015-2019 (tons)

Source: Own design based on FAOSTAT database 2021

At the level of 2019, according to the published statistical data, it was found that France is on the first position in the top of the first barley exporters highlighted worldwide. France held in 2019 a share of 23.08% of the world's barley exports.

The following places in the top of barley exporters are occupied by: Russian Federation (12.68% of world barley exports); Australia (9.24% of the world barley exports); Argentina (8.10% of world barley exports) and Ukraine (7.56% of world barley exports).

Fig. 5. Top of the first barley exporters registered at worldwide level in 2019 (tons)

Source: Own design based on FAOSTAT database 2021

In 2019, the world's top 5 exporters of barley held 60.66% of the world's barley exports.

CONCLUSIONS

Following the analysis of the main indicators specific to the production and sale of barley worldwide, the following results were obtained:

- The total area cultivated with barley worldwide increased by 2.63%, in 2019, compared to 2015;
- Europe is the leader in terms of barley-growing area;
- In 2019, the world's largest barley production was recorded, namely, 158,979,610 tons;
- In Europe, barley production increased by 4.85%, in 2019, compared to 2015;
- The most significant yield for barley worldwide was of 3,108 kg/ha (2019);
- In 2017, the world's largest imports of barley were recorded, of 39,237,488 tons;
- Global quantitative barley exports decreased by 18.94% in 2019 compared to 2015.
- France occupied in 2019, the first position in the top of barley exporters registered worldwide, with an export level of 7,171,937 tons.

In perspective mankind can rely on this cereal crop, because it can be grown on the one hand, both in regions with high temperatures, and on the other hand, at high altitudes.

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THE EFFECTS OF CANNABIS SATIVA HYDROEXTRACTS ON TRITICUM AESTIVUM SEEDLINGS PIGMENT CONCENTRATIONS

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Abstract

Cannabis, or hemp, is a plant with a huge medical and economic potential. Known since ancient times, Cannabis is rich in cannabinoids of which cannabidiol (CBD) is the most biologically active compound with almost none of the negative aspects of its fellow cannabinoids. Since the 19th century, Cannabis has been used as an analgesic, anesthetic, antidepressant, sedative and even antibiotic. However, its bio-industrial potential has not yet been fully explored and given that Cannabis plants are harvested for hemp, animal feed and various agricultural purposes, their potential effects as fertilizer or herbicide have not yet been identified.

*This paper presents the effects of *C. sativa* hydroextract on *Triticum aestivum* seedlings. During this study it was observed that *Triticum aestivum* seedlings treated with 100%, 10% and 5% *C. sativa* extracts showed lower levels of Chlorophyll A and B than the control sample. The seedlings treated with 50% and 25% *C. sativa* extracts showed higher levels of Chlorophyll A and lower content of Chlorophyll B when compared to the control. There was an increase in the carotenoids detected in all samples, with 50% and 25% showing the highest levels. This suggests that *C. sativa* extracts have the ability to increase the carotenoids levels in *T. aestivum* seedlings and modify the amount of Chlorophyll A and Chlorophyll B extract in a dose-dependent manner.*

Key words: *Cannabis sativa*, extract, spectrophotometry, carotenoids, chlorophyll, *Triticum aestivum*

INTRODUCTION

Cannabis, also known as marijuana, is the dried and processed leaves, flowers and body of the genus *Cannabis*. The oldest mention of it dates back to China in the year 2,120 B.C. (Devinsky et al., 2014; Russo, 2007). Cannabis contains substances called cannabinoids of which two cannabinoids, namely *Tetrahydrocannabinol* (THC) and *Cannabidiol* (CBD), are the ones with the highest level of medical potential. Nowadays there is an increase interest for CBD's and THC's analgesic, anti-nociceptive, anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective, immuno-stimulative, anti-cancerous and many more effects (Elias et al., 2019; Massi et al., 2004; Klein et al., 2003; Lah et al., 2021; Go et

al., 2020; Qamri et al., 2009), with particular interest towards CBD's medical potential. The reason why CBD has such an immense medical potential is that it does not trigger a "high" reaction as THC does.

The effects of CBD are mediated by the G protein coupled receptors, which are divided into two categories namely type I (CB1) and type II (CB2) (Jones et al., 2010). CB1 receptors are in abundance in the central nervous system, especially in the hippo-campus region and the CB2 receptors are primarily located in the immune system. Upon activation of CB1 receptors, an inhibition of synaptic transmissions was found through potassium and calcium channels, which are known to modulate epileptic and convulsive activity (Welty et al., 2014; Giacobbe et al., 2020).

CBD has multiple beneficial effects on the central nervous system therefore, in addition to its potential in the treatment of seizures, it reduces anxiety and sleep disorders (Shannon et al., 2019; Welty et al., 2014; Sholler et al., 2020).

The most recent area of interest for CBD is its potential use in the treatment of Covid-19-associated lung inflammation. Recent studies have shown that its anti-inflammatory and anxiolytic effects, combined with its ability to inhibit the "cytokine storm", gave rise to the idea of using it as an adjunct in the treatment of Covid-19 (Shi et al., 2020; Anil et al., 2021).

Applications of *Cannabis sativa* in areas such as the textile, agricultural or construction industries have recently been rediscovered and re-evaluated (Bailoni et al., 2021). Because the main focus is on its medical properties, the textile, industrial and agricultural potential are overlooked or completely ignored in current studies. This paper focuses on the effects of aqueous *C. sativa* extract on *Triticum aestivum* seedlings.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The biological material consisted of carefully selected caryopsis of *Triticum aestivum* L., Trublion variety, C1, semi-rotten wheat, harvest year 2020. The *Cannabis sativa* (non-THC strain) was provided by Canah International Srl and Alcos Bioprod SRL.

To 1g of dried and grounded leaves were added 9g of distilled water and the mixture was kept at room temperature for 48 hours according to the Aguawa and Mittal extraction method (Aguawa et al., 1981). After filtration, the resulting extract has been labelled as 100% *C. sativa* hydroextract and kept at 4°C until the

beginning of the experiment. Subsequent dilutions of 50%, 25%, 10%, 5%, 2.5% and 1%, respectively were made from the crude extract.

Ten germinated seeds of *Triticum aestivum* were placed on a filter paper in a Petri dish and 5 mL of *C. sativa* extract was added. The control was prepared by adding 5 mL of double distilled water. Each experiment was performed in triplicate for extracts of each concentration. The Petri dishes were kept for a period of 5 days for the roots and body of the infant grain plant to grow.

On the 5th day, a weight of 0.05 g of plant (body and leaf) from each Petri dish was treated with a solution of 80% acetone. After a period of 72 hours, the mixture was decanted and the resulting solution was analyzed using a PG Instruments T80+ UV/VIS spectrometer. The readings for the samples were done at 470 nm, 646 nm and 663 nm wavelengths, along with the control for comparison. The absorption reading was performed seven times for each wavelength and then the arithmetic average was calculated.

Wellburn's formulas were used to determine the concentration of Chlorophyll A, Chlorophyll B and Carotenoids:

$$\text{Chlorophyll A } \mu\text{g/mL} = 11.65 \times \text{Abs } 663 \text{ nm} - 2.69 \times \text{Abs } 646 \text{ nm}$$

$$\text{Chlorophyll B } \mu\text{g/mL} = 20.81 \times \text{Abs } 646 \text{ nm} - 4.53 \times \text{Abs } 663 \text{ nm}$$

$$\text{Carotenoids } \mu\text{g/mL} = (1.000 \times \text{Abs } 470 \text{ nm} - 0.89 \times \text{Chlorophyll A} - 52.02 \times \text{Chlorophyll B})/245$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in Tables 1 and 2 and in Chart 1, the results showed a marked decrease in Chlorophyll B and an increase in Chlorophyll A and carotenoids, the 50% and 25% *C. sativa* extracts being the ones that produced the most significant results.

Chlorophyll A and B differ in their roles in the photosynthesis process, with Chlorophyll A being the main pigment that directly captures the light and Chlorophyll B being the accessory pigment with the role of collecting energy and passing it to Chlorophyll A. Chlorophyll A has the property to absorb light at 430 nm to 660 nm from the violet-blue and orange-red spectrums, while Chlorophyll B absorbs primarily blue spectrum of light at 450 nm to 650 nm.

Chlorophyll B has a higher presence in shade adapted chloroplasts, therefore one of Chlorophyll B's functions is absorbing energy in conditions of indirect sunlight/shaded areas and passing the energy to Chlorophyll A. An increase in the level of Chlorophyll A means that the ability of a plant to capture

light directly increases, while the decrease in Chlorophyll B means a decrease in the ability to indirectly capture light in shaded areas (Rabinowitch et al., 1965).

Carotenoids are pigments that have a dual role of photoprotective agents and have accessory properties for collecting light, along with which they give the plants a reddish to orange coloration. The hydroextracts of *C. sativa* showed the ability to increase the total amount of carotenoids in *T. aestivum* seedlings at each concentration studied. This imparts an increased or huge photoprotection in *T. aestivum* seedlings, the highest being at concentrations of 50% and 25%. Anyway, a marked increase was observed at all concentrations in terms of carotenoid levels.

Table 1

UV/Vis average absorption values of the samples at each wavelength

Sample	Chlorophyll A 470 nm	Chlorophyll B 646 nm	Carotenoids 663 nm
Control	0.698	0.803	0.612
100% <i>C. sativa</i>	0.489	0.198	0.235
50% <i>C. sativa</i>	0.924	0.475	0.892
25% <i>C. sativa</i>	1.103	0.638	1.073
10% <i>C. sativa</i>	0.530	0.310	0.461
5% <i>C. sativa</i>	0.376	0.214	0.244
2.5% <i>C. sativa</i>	0.822	0.442	0.719
1% <i>C. sativa</i>	0.607	0.352	0.504

Table 2

The content of Chlorophyll A, Chlorophyll B and carotenoids in the samples

Sample	Chlorophyll A [µg/mL]	Chlorophyll B [µg/mL]	Carotenoids [µg/mL]
Control	4.969	13.938	0.1284
100% <i>C. sativa</i>	2.207	3.060	1.338
50% <i>C. sativa</i>	9.113	5.844	2.497
25% <i>C. sativa</i>	10.784	8.332	2.693
10% <i>C. sativa</i>	4.5367	4.362	1.220
5% <i>C. sativa</i>	2.266	3.428	0.798
2.5 % <i>C. sativa</i>	7.187	5.940	1.825
1% <i>C. sativa</i>	4.924	5.042	1.389

Fig. 1. Levels of Chlorophyll A, Chlorophyll B and carotenoids in *T. aestivum* seedlings treated with *C. sativa* hydroextracts

Taking into account these results it can be suggested that *C. sativa* might be used to create specialized crops for regions with inhospitable climates (e.g. higher temperatures, dry areas, higher intensity of sunlight) that are resistant to high levels of sunlight that would cause the standard crops to wither from too much light, as well as for obtaining crops with a high content of carotenoids for aesthetic and industrial purposes.

The data shows that the effects of *C. sativa* hydroextracts on *T. aestivum* seedlings are dose dependent. As suggested by Fig. 1, the level of Chlorophyll A detected in the samples treated with 50% and 25% *C. sativa* extracts, respectively shows that a specialized culture can be obtained which has a high capacity to directly absorb sunlight at wavelengths of 450 to 650 nm. This leads to the hypothesis of specialized crops that would be optimal for artificial lighting conditions with purple-blue and orange-red light in the range of 450 to 650 nm with direct constant light sources, such as greenhouses. On the other hand, the seeds treated with 10% and 1% *C. sativa* extracts suggest a plant adapted to equally absorb purple-blue and orange-red light by Chlorophyll A and blue by Chlorophyll B, with an equal ability to capture direct and indirect sunlight.

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of *C. sativa* hydroextracts on the levels of Chlorophyll A and B is dose-dependent. *T. aestivum* seedlings treated with 100%, 10% and 5% extracts, respectively showed lower levels of Chlorophyll A and B than the control, while the seedlings treated with 50% and 25% extracts showed high level of Chlorophyll A and low content of Chlorophyll B thus resulting in plants with a higher capacity to absorb direct sunlight and a reduced capacity to absorb indirect/shaded light.

This shows that, depending on the concentration of the extract, plants with a different content of chlorophyll and/or carotenoids pigments can be grown. With a significant increase in dose-dependent carotenoids and an increase in the photoprotection of plants, we can conclude that *C. sativa* extracts have an overall potential for designer crops that can be grown in areas with intense light, more intense than the natural climate of the plant. In addition, we can suggest that *C. sativa* hydroextract has the ability to create stronger and more specialized plants, but also to inhibit their development in a dose-dependent manner. This suggests the potential of *C. sativa* aqueous extract to be used to create crops that are tailor made for harsher lighting conditions or more artificial ones.

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INTERESTS FOR THE DESIGN OF BIOSOURCED DERIVATIVES BY CHEMO-ENZYMATIC SYNTHESIS

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Abstract

Conventional chemistry is difficult to implement with carbohydrates, the basis of many "green" surfactants. Biocatalysis appear as a possible solution to synthesize biosourced molecules with more sustainable industrial processes that comply with the principles of green chemistry: energy saving, product selectivity, monodispersity, reduction of the use of solvents, with energy eco-efficiency. Enzymes have a great versatility, their active site can receive very variable substrates, in mild conditions and in alternative solvents. Thus, biosourced products such as carbohydrates derived from biomasses such as beet or starch crops, are used as platform entities to obtain high added value products. An optimization of monosaccharide ester synthesis has been done by modulating different parameters. The synthesis of linolenic ester of glucose allowed to determine the interest of using tertiary alcohols as reaction solvent. Reaction parameters of temperature, medium stirring, reaction time, enzyme ratio, desiccant in the reaction medium, and ose:fatty acid ratio were determined after several trials. Moreover, by adding a solubilizing agent at different concentrations, the yields could be improved. The optimal parameters were applied to other fatty acids (FA) and allowed to determine a relative affinity for long hydrocarbon chains (C18 saturated or not) compared to shorter chains. The operating conditions were transposed to transesterification and a better molar yield was obtained. An optimization of this reaction was carried out by modifying the ratio, the reaction time, and the stirring. The results show the importance of the ose:FA ratio of 1:3 against the 1:2, 48h of reaction time and a high agitation, 240 rpm, as well as an activation temperature of catalytic activity between 50°C and 60°C. A variation of the osidic derivative shows an identical affinity for all glucose epimers and this lipase.

Key words: biobased, biocatalysts, chemo-enzymatic, optimization.

INTRODUCTION

Fatty acid esters and sugar esters are non-ionic biosurfactants obtained from naturally renewable resource (Klein et al., 2019). As such, they have the property of reducing surface tension at air/water interfaces and oil/water interfacial tension (Sachdev and Cameotra, 2013). This set of molecules, classically called surfactants, is mainly obtained by chemical means or by microbial means, as with rhamnolipids for example. The use of microorganisms generates a non-negligible cost, particularly for purification, and even more, the small quantities generated are a limiting factor (Nott et al., 2013). The alternative, particularly in terms of the cost of synthesis, would be to turn to so-called classical chemistry syntheses. Nevertheless, classical chemistry is difficult to implement with carbohydrates (Gloster, 2020). Biocatalysis is emerging as a possible solution for designing biosourced

molecules. Over the past two decades, interest in biocatalytic transformations has increased due to an urgent need for more sustainable industrial processes that are consistent with green chemistry principles (Santi et al., 2021). Enzymatic engineering allows the production of high value-added molecules (Benítez-Mateos et al., 2021). Every year, the number of published studies on biocatalysis increases (Nikulín and Švedas, 2021). Enzymatic synthesis will have many advantages compared to chemical synthesis: energy saving, product selectivity, reduced use of pre-sourced solvents. The use of enzymes makes it possible to avoid the undesired obtaining of by-products, as well as the steps of protection and deprotection of hydroxyl groups of the carbohydrate molecules platforms (Perugino, 2004). These steps have a significant cost and complicate the syntheses. Enzymes have great versatility, their active site can receive various substrates, under varying conditions of temperature and alternative solvents. The optimization of a synthesis pathway will require the consideration of relatively different factors, ranging from the conditions necessary for catalytic activity, to those required to make the substrates bioavailable to the enzyme. The main enzymes used are lipases, which catalyse hydrolysis and esterification reactions. Due to the unique properties of lipases, they can be used in several fields.

Lipases are active in environments that contain at least two distinct phases, in which all the reactants are distributed between these phases, although their distribution is dynamic as the reaction proceeds. The kinetics of lipase-catalysed reactions are governed by several factors (Stergiou et al., 2013). Optimizing a synthesis will involve varying these to improve yields, or simply to decrease the overall carbon footprint of the final product. Enzymes are generally sold immobilized on polymeric support. This immobilization confers to the lipases a stability to the reuse, to decrease the effects of the thermal variations as well as a maintenance in time of the active conformations of the protein sites. The choice of a reaction solvent is also an element to consider: it is necessary to consider the fact that acylation will progressively increase the solubility of the oses (Chamouleau et al., 2001) in organic solvents. Co-solvents, such as DMSO, pyridine or DMF have the advantage of solubilizing almost all the molecules but inactivate the enzyme (Jia et al., 2010). Another alternative to improve the synthesis of carbohydrate esters by enzymatic reaction is the transesterification. The objective of this work was therefore to discriminate different solvents for glucose esterification reactions and to optimize the synthesis of lauric ester of glucose by transesterification.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

All reagents used had a minimum purity of 98% unless otherwise stated.

Tert-butanol (t-But), 2-methyl-2-butanol (2M2B) were from Janssen (Belgium). Dichloromethane was from Carlo Erba Reagents. Ethyl Acetate (AcOEt), methanol (MeOH) and petroleum ether were from VWR (France). Molecular sieve 3Å (8-12 mesh, preactivated by drying 4h at 250 °C before use, then dried overtime at 105°C), diméthylsulfoxide (DMSO), glucose monohydrate, glucose, rhamnose, galactose, mannose, lauric acid (C12), ethyl laurate (C12Et) and vinyl laurate (C12V) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA). Xylose was obtained from TCI.

Acrylic lipase (EC 3.1.1.3), $\geq 5,000$ U/g, recombinant, expressed in *Aspergillus niger*, was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (USA).

Esterification protocol:

Molecular sieve (10% w/v), ose (1eq) and a fatty chain (3eq) were stirred together in t-But or 2M2B. 20% DMSO (v/v) was added next. The reaction mixture was stirred and heated to the target temperature in a closed thermostatically agitator. After 1 hour of heating and a homogeneous medium observed, a sample was taken in order to carry out TLC kinetics. The enzyme was finally added with a ratio of 1% (w/v). The syntheses were always conducted with a negative control, without enzyme.

Fig. 1 Desired products from the synthesis of lauric ester of glucose by esterification (C12) and transesterification (C12Et)

Purification of the product:

After synthesis, the reaction media were immediately cooled to 4°C. The samples were then stored at -18°C before being purified. They were then filtered on paper to recover enzyme and sieve. The enzyme was washed with MeOH or t-But and stored at 4°C. The organic solvents, tertiary alcohols, were then evaporated under reduced pressure. A liquid extraction with H₂O and dichloromethane was then performed. The organic phase was recovered and evaporated. The oil-like crude product, mixture of the starting fatty chain of the desired biosurfactant, was then purified by flash chromatography with a mobile phase consisting of a variable ratio of petroleum ether, ethyl acetate and methanol. The isolated product was then characterized by IR-FT and lyophilized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first experiments were performed to test various solvents that can allow the formation of the desired product (as described in the conditions described in Figure 2). The experiment was led with heptane, acetone, ethanol, water, isobutanol, isoamyl alcohol, as well as co-solvents heptane/acetone, ethanol/water, hexane/THF. The characterization of reaction media by TLC allowed to highlight that isobutanol and isoamyl alcohol, although complicated to evaporate, could be good candidates. Particular attention was paid to the solubility of the initial mixture. Glucose and more generally, the oses, are only very slightly soluble in isoamyl alcohol and isobutanol. Therefore, based on this fact, the use of ethanol seems to be the best candidate to solubilize all the reagents. The infrared spectra obtained show the formation of an ester, hence an enzymatic activity, but also the absence of glucose free hydroxyl groups, located around 3300 cm^{-1} on IR-FT spectra. The molecules obtained were therefore alcohol esters. Ethanol is indeed a very good substrate for the this Lipase, expressed in *Aspergillus Niger*. However, non-substrate solvents for lipases are mainly tertiary alcohols but weakly solubilize oses. The best reaction solvent among t-But and 2M2B was determined, as shown in Figure 2. DMSO was added in 20% (v/v) proportion to increase the solubility of starting raw materials.

Figure 2: Effect of solvent on molar yield for the synthesis of oleic ester of glucose with fatty acid – 56°C – 72h – 240rpm

The results obtained here distinguish a highly positive effect of DMSO when it represents 20% of the final concentration. 2M2B seems to be a better reaction solvent. Triplicates performed on this synthesis confirm the results with an average of 26% yield in tert-butanol, 39% when 20% DMSO is added, and 32% and 45% yield in 2M2B and 2M2B with DMSO.

Then, the objective of the work was to extrapolate the results obtained to other fatty acids. First, the interest was to see if the 2M2B/DMSO mixture was still the best mixture. Glucose has a solubility, at 60°C , of 2.40 g/L in

2M2B, and 2.30 g/L in t-But. The solubility of glucose is increased by a factor of 5 in 2M2B when the DMSO concentration is close to 20% at 60°C (Tsavas et al., 2002). DMSO would potentially induce a conformational change in the tryptophan residues of lipase. Studies report a non-essential activating effect, not leading to structural changes in lipase (Mangiagalli et al., 2020). Further study will confirm one of these hypotheses. Secondly, the objective was to determine a potential affinity for some chain. The preferred solvent is 2M2B with 20% DMSO with 45% for the oleic glucose ester (Figure 3). Moreover, the yields were higher with long chain (C18:1) and unsaturated compared to shorter chain (C12) and saturated. Without lipase, a product was obtained, probably a sugar ester, hypothesis validated by IR-FT.

Fig. 3 Effect of DMSO on molar yield – 56°C -72h – 240 rpm (abs means without), light grey for negative control, black for synthesis with lipase.

The work then focused on transesterification, comparing the best conditions, namely 2M2B with DMSO, at 56°C, 240rpm, during 72h. Two ratios were tested and 3 fatty chains were compared: lauric acid for esterification and ethyl laurate and vinyl laurate for transesterification (figure 4).

In their native medium, lipases use to catalyze the hydrolysis reaction of esters. When lipases are used in organic solvents, the reverse reaction is performed. If the neoformed water is not eliminated as it is formed, the equilibrium of the reaction is shifted towards the hydrolysis of glucose esters.

Fig. 4 Molar yield for the variation of ratio for the synthesis of ester lauric glucose

Transesterification is an interesting alternative to fatty acid esterification because, in addition to the fact that alcohol esters are more reactive than fatty acids, the by-product formed is an alcohol and is therefore easier to eliminate.

Vinyl esters are generally preferred over ethyl and methyl esters. The vinyl alcohol formed is tautomerized to acetaldehyde, which is volatile and therefore expected to be easily removed. Nevertheless, acetaldehyde could react with the free amine groups of the lysine residues leading to the inactivation of lipases (van den Broek and Boeriu, 2013). Here, comparable results are obtained with ethyl laurate for a ratio of 1:3 and vinyl laurate for each ratio. For both products, the same profile is obtained by FTIR (cm^{-1}): 3308(O-H), 1730(ester C=O), 1171(C-O), 2850, 2919(aliphatic C-H).

Therefore, it seemed interesting to optimize the lauric glucose ester synthesis by transesterification for the other parameters, namely the synthesis time t , the temperature T and finally the stirring. As for the solvent condition 2M2B+20% DMSO and the ratio (1:3), they were set based on the previous results. For each condition assessed, the other parameters were all fixed. This experimentation allowed to highlight the role of each parameter (figure 5).

It is therefore possible to conclude that a longer synthesis time is not necessarily synonymous with a higher yield of sugar ester. Indeed, it appears that, for a reaction time beyond 48h, the yield (50%) is lower than for 48h reaction (71%). This is probably due to a destruction of the neoformed product during the synthesis, the lauric ester of glucose becomes the preferred substrate of the lipase instead of glucose. Regarding the temperature, it is obvious that there is a plateau of catalytic activation between 50 and 60°C. Regarding stirring speed, it is interesting to note that it has a very important effect on the reaction efficiency, mainly on the probability that the enzyme, here immobilized on the resin, meets the reactants. Best results were obtained for a minimum agitation of 240 rpm.

Fig. 5: Molar Yield obtained for the optimization of production of lauric ester glucose

Simultaneously, the objective was to synthesize hexose esters using the previously optimized reaction conditions: transesterification with ethyl laurate in ratio 1:3, 2M2B + 20% DMSO as solvent, 56°C reaction temperature, stirring at 240 rpm, 72 hours reaction time. The yields are similar for the epimers of glucose, namely mannose and galactose. For xylose, the monodispersity of the reactions is different. Indeed, besides the fact that the yield is lower, about 30%, 24% of monoester are obtained, but also 6% of polyester. The monodispersity of the reaction is lost, probably due to the cyclic furanose/pyranose form of xylose. For rhamnose, the negative control, same in all aspects but without enzyme, allows to highlight the catalytic activity of DMSO. The yields are similar for both samples, with and without enzyme, which means that the lipase does not accept rhamnose as a substrate. In fact, for glucose for example, the addition of the ester bond is done exclusively in position 6 of the pyranose ring, on the CH₂OH. As rhamnose is a deoxyose, the lipase does not seem to recognize this substrate.

CONCLUSIONS

This work has highlighted the interest of using enzymes in the context of sugar ester synthesis. Biocatalysis appears as an interesting alternative to classical chemistry. In addition to the green chemistry aspects, enzymatic catalysis allows to obtain syntheses easier to implement, with a relative monodispersity, a great versatility in the substrates and especially a great possibility of optimization, with many parameters on which it is possible to change, with the aim of producing more, with a lower carbon footprint.

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RESEARCH ON THE EFFECT OF COPPER ON GERMINATION AND GROWTH OF *Phaseolus vulgaris* var. Nanus

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Abstract.

*Copper has been and continues to be widely used in agriculture due to its antifungal and antibacterial properties. In the same time, foliar fertilizers, many of which contain a significant amount of copper, are applied to crops during the vegetative stage in order to increase efficiency. Therefore, providing copper to crop plants prevents the appearance of diseases and increases crop production; however, because copper is a heavy metal, it accumulates in the soil over time, reaching toxic concentrations, resulting in increased mobility in soil solution and increased bioavailability for plants. The effects of toxic copper levels on plants are not fully understood, but they have sparked serious concern among scientists. The goal of the study was to see how different copper concentrations affected the germination and growth of seedlings of *Phaseolus vulgaris* var. Nanus in their early stages of development.*

Key words: abiotic stress, copper, germination, heavy metal, *Phaseolus*

INTRODUCTION

Copper is a heavy metal that is widely used in agriculture as a fungicide for the treatment of seeds and plants, as a foliar fertilizer, and as an algacide in water treatments. Copper has been and continues to be used in agriculture as a result of its antifungal and antibacterial properties, as well as its high efficiency and low cost, in the form of various commercial products based on: hydroxide Cu, oxychloride, or Cu sulphate. However, copper accumulates in the soil over time, reaching toxic concentrations (Ballabio et al., 2018), resulting in increased mobility of the soil solution and increased bioavailability to plants. According to the ICPA Soil Monitoring Report, the average copper content in 670 agricultural land sites in the country is 26.07mg/kg dry soil, in conditions where, according to MAPPM Order no. 756/1997, the normal value of the Cu concentration in the soil in Romania is 20 mg/kg dry soil, the values considered alert thresholds are 100 - 200 mg/kg d.s. and the values for intervention are 250 – 500 mg/kg d.s. Thus, 48.7% of the analyzed sites had normal copper contents, 50.6 % were between the normal value and the alert threshold for sensitive use, and 0.44 % (i.e. 3 sites) had values above the alert threshold, while only one site exceeded the threshold intervention, recording 551mg Cu/kg soil (Dumitru et al., 2011).

Under normal conditions, Cu is found in plant tissues at concentrations of 10 ug/g s.u. (Baker and Brooks, 1989, Kanoun-Boulet et al., 2009), being an essential element with an important role in the synthesis of chlorophyll and enzymes, as well as in photosynthesis, respiration, and the metabolism of carbohydrates, proteins, and cell wall constituents, or in lignification (Yruela, 2005). As a result, copper deficiency can alter various metabolic functions in plants (Rehman et al., 2019). Light spots were also observed on the leaves, and in the case of straw cereals, white and empty ears, as well as delaying twinning and reducing resistance to falling (Scăețeanu and Pele, 2013). However, high copper concentrations in soil are toxic to most plants and slow plant growth due to changes in mineral nutrition, photosynthesis, enzymatic activities, and decreased chlorophyll synthesis (Adrees et al., 2015). Its toxicity stems primarily from the possibility of forming free radicals, which cause oxidative stress in plants (Fernandez and Henriques, 1991). Shen et al. (1998) demonstrated that excess Cu can have a variety of direct and indirect effects on the metabolism on *Vigna radiata* plants. Aladessanni et al. (2019) discovered an increase in Cu content of plants while studying the phenomenon of heavy metal bioaccumulation in corn (*Zea mays*), which affects not only productivity but also the quality and safety of food. As a result, the continuous release into the environment and on a large scale of agrochemicals based on copper, which have traditionally and sometimes excessively been used in agriculture, has become an urgent problem, with numerous cases of phytotoxicity documented. Previous research by Xu et al. (2006), Verma et al. (2011), Thounaojam et al. (2012), Bharwana (2015), and others has shown that increased copper levels in soil can affect plant growth, significantly reduce crop productivity, and even threaten human health by penetrating the food chain.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The plant material used in the current experiments was seeds of *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. var. Nanus (*Fabaceae*), a plant native to South America that is now grown all over the world (Graham and Ranolli, 1997).

To conduct the experiment, we used transparent plastic pans with lids measuring 22/14 cm and h = 6 cm. In each casserole, we used absorbent paper as a base and evenly distributed 50 grains. The experimental group also included a control variant (V_0), which was only watered with distilled water throughout the experiment. According to the experimental protocol shown in Table 1, we used different concentrations of active substance (0.1%, 1%), applied foliar or root, for the other three variants.

The chemical substance that we used was fungicide CHAMP 77 WG (50% metallic Cu from copper hydroxide) dissolved in distilled water for the experiment.

Table 1

Experimental protocol (DW– distilled water; Cu –copper, active substance; T– temperature).

Germination conditions	Experimental variants and mode of application	Biometrics	Time for measurements
T = 22° ± 2°C Natural light	V ₀ - radicular – DW on the first day - foliar – DW on the 7 th day	Germination rate	24h 48 h 72 h 5 days 7 days 10 days 14 days
	V ₁ – radicular – 0.1% Cu (100mg/l) on the first day - foliar – DW on the 7 th day		
	V ₂ - radicular - 1 % Cu (1000 mg/l) on the first day - foliar – DW on the 7 th day	Growth indices: - embryo root length - adventitious roots number - hypocotyl length - epicotyl length - leaves number - plant size - dry weight	14 days
	V ₃ – radicular – DW on the first day - foliar – 0.1% Cu (100 mg/l) on the 7 th day		

The abiotic stress to which the beans from variants V₁ and V₂ were subjected consisted of watering them at the base by how many 20 ml of liquid (3 ml of solution + 17 ml of DW) from the concentration solution corresponding to each experimental variant on the first day of the experiment. On all other days, we used only distilled water.

For V₃ variant we used the same concentration as in variant V₁ (3 ml of 0.1% solution), applied foliar on the seventh day of the experiment. For watering on the rest days, we used only distilled water, in the same amount as in the case of variants V₁, V₂, and V₀ (control). On the same day of the experiment (7th), we used the same amount (3 ml) of distilled water for foliar application of seedlings for all other experimental variants (V₀, V₁, V₂).

Following the completion of the experiment and removal of the remaining material seedlings, the seedlings of each experimental batch were wrapped in aluminum foil and kept in the oven at 115°C, for 4 hours, for 3 consecutive days, after which the dry weight was determined by weighing on an analytical balance.

Data from biometric measurements were mathematically and statistically processed in the Microsoft Excel 2010 program, with the average arithmetic, difference from control, standard deviation, and student test calculated (*t* test).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The germination process in all experimental variants started 24 hours after the seeds were planted and ended 10 days after the experiment began (Fig. 1). The rate of germination was found to be greater than 96% for all experimental variants at the end of the experiment, indicating that Cu treatment of applied copper hydroxide root or leaf did not inhibit the germination process in beans (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Monitoring the germination rate of bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* var. Nanus) seeds, on the following experimental variants: V₀ – distilled water; V₁ – 0.1% Cu, radicular application; V₂ - 1% Cu, radicular application; V₃ – 0.1% Cu, foliar application, at different time intervals (h-hours, d-days).

Verma et al. (2011) found similar results when they followed the germination of mung bean seeds (*Vigna radiata*) treated with different concentrations of Cu in copper sulfate and discovered that the percentage of germination was over 95%, indicating that the germination process was not inhibited by different concentrations of copper. Similar findings were reported by Saquoir et al. (2008), who investigated the toxic potential of copper on *Vicia faba* and *Pisum sativum* plants in hydroponic culture conditions.

In terms of the growth and development indices of seedling beans, the root-treated batch with 1% Cu showed very statistically significant negative differences compared to the control group, both in terms of the length of the embryo root, the length of the hypocotyl, and, implicitly, seedling size and number of leaves (Table 2).

Table 2

Statistical processing of bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* var. Nanus) growth index values, 14 days after seeding to germinate on different experimental variants: V₀ – distilled water; V₁ – 0.1% Cu, radicular application; V₂ – 1% Cu, radicular application; V₃ – 0.1% Cu, foliar application.

Variants	Average ± standard deviation						Difference from control (cm)/ significance of difference					
	Embryo root length (cm)	Adventitious roots number	Hypocotyl length (cm)	Epicotyl length (cm)	Leaves number	Plant size (cm)	Embryo root length (cm)	Adventitious roots number	Hypocotyl length (cm)	Epicotyl length (cm)	Leaves number	Plant size (cm)
V ₀	5.41 ± 4.33	3.92 ± 2.01	1.98 ± 2.11	0.05 ± 0.13	0.48 ± 0.86	7.44 ± 5.89	-	-	-	-	-	-
V ₁	4.14 ± 3.47	4.14 ± 1.75	1.89 ± 2.14	0.06 ± 0.19	0.56 ± 0.91	6.09 ± 5.13	-1.27**	0.22*	-0.09**	0.01*	0.08*	-1.35*
V ₂	1.50 ± 0.80	3.68 ± 1.56	0.87 ± 0.31	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	2.38 ± 1.01	-3.9***	-0.24*	-1.11***	-0.05**	-0.48***	-5.06***
V ₃	4.47 ± 3.58	3.92 ± 1.74	2.57 ± 2.72	0.23 ± 0.52	0.87 ± 1.00	7.26 ± 6.19	-0.94*	0.00 ns	0.59*	0.18**	0.36**	-0.17*

Note: *** p<0.01 - very significant; ** p<0.1 - distinctly significant; * p<0.5 – significant; ns p>0.5 – no statistically significant difference.

At 7 days, both the seedlings in the group treated with root with 0.1% Cu and those in the foliar treated group with the same concentration of metal not only did not show inhibitions, but even recorded a significant increase over the group control, demonstrating that the toxic effect of copper on plants beans is manifested only at high concentrations, less in the case of length embryo root.

Because the values in the tables were only mentioned with two decimals in mathematical processing, statistical results appear even at apparent values of 0.00 (Table 2).

In the case of testing the manufacturer's recommended concentration, but with root application, encoded V₁ in our case, the rhizogenesis was inhibited, with average deficits of 1.27 cm recorded compared to the control, these being statistically significant (Table 2). High concentration of Cu, similar to the alert threshold tested in group V₂, conducted to high deficits, both in terms of rhizogenesis and caulogenesis, according to statistical data (Table 2), with these inhibitions also found in seedling dry weight values (Table 3).

These findings are consistent with previous research, but we also observed growth increases in seedlings treated with the recommended concentration of Cu, indicating that Cu acts as a micronutrient with stimulating effects on development bean seedlings. Iqbal et al. (2018) observed inhibitory effects on lentil root growth (*Lens culinaris*) at concentrations of 25 mg Cu/l, but only at high Cu concentrations (75 mg/l and 100 mg/l) were significant toxic effects on stem growth observed. In addition, Oros et al. (2011), in a study on *Medicago sativa* plants, concluded that at low concentrations, copper has a stronger toxic effect on the stem and a weaker inhibitory effect on the root, and at high concentrations, the relationship is reversed, with the inhibitory effect being stronger on the root.

The dry weight data (Table 3) support the inhibitory effect of increased copper concentration on the growth of bean seedlings.

Table 3

Dry weight of bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* var. Nanus) seedlings, 14 days after seeding to germinate on different experimental variants: V₀ – distilled water; V₁ – 0.1% Cu, radicular application; V₂ - 1% Cu, radicular application; V₃ – 0.1% Cu, foliar application.

Experimental variants	Dry weight (g)
V ₀	1.9887
V ₁	1.8930
V ₂	0.9295
V ₃	2.0077

Thus, the batch treated with 1% Cu root had the lowest value compared to the control group (Table 3), as well as the batch with the strongest inhibitions of growth and development indices (Table 2). This

decrease in yield is associated with an increase in copper in soil, indicating that copper has a high level of phytotoxicity to plants at high concentrations. Other researchers have reported a significant reduction in plant biomass under high copper conditions (Baszynski et al., 1988; Lidon and Henriques, 1991).

At the same time, the batch treated with 0.1 % Cu, the manufacturer's recommended concentration, had a value similar to that of the control batch, and in cases of foliar-treated seedlings, after 7 days, with the same concentration of copper recorded an increase compared to the value of the control group (Table 3).

CONCLUSIONS

1. The presence of copper, regardless of the concentrations tested, influenced lightly the bean germination rate.
2. Copper generated increases and inhibitions of growth rates in the dicotyledonous species in low concentrations (0.1%), radicular applied, but the overall size of the seedlings and their dry weight were found to be inferior to the control group, at the end of the experiment.
3. The toxic effect of copper was found at the high concentration of copper (1%), radicular applied on the first day, causing significant inhibitions of the growth indices, both from the perspective of rhizogenesis and caulogenesis.
4. Foliar application of 0.1% Cu solution, according to agricultural crop recommendations, on the seventh day of the experiment, after the appearance of the first leaves, was a significant incentive for bean seedlings, only in terms of caulogenesis and dry weight.

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USE OF NATURAL EXTRACTS FROM *PRUNUS SEROTINA* IN TEXTILES AS DYES

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Abstract

Since ancient times the humans developed and used various products for improving the appearance of textiles materials for different purposes.

The aim of this paper was related to find a suitable natural products that have no allergenic properties, reduced carbon footprint and resilience due to source and properties. The reason was related with reviewing the ancient handicrafts as an option for comercial aggressive chemical products.

In this way it was a challenge to find proper dosage, way of production and way of use of natural extracts but keeping the desired appearance. Also it was important to asses the quality obtained in comparison with products obtained in clasical aproach and resilience in environment.

*It was used an natural alchoolic extract from *Prunus serotina* specie that have intense red color and is provided from natural spontan flora near Săcuieni village.*

Key words: *Prunus serotina*, natural colorant, textiles, dyes, chemical compounds substitution.

INTRODUCTION

Color was during history one of the main goal of the human mankind in order to create an pleasent environment, answering to the increasing demands about beauty but also for technical reasons. Colorants for textiles known as dyes were in this way one of the most important concerns of the textile industry.

Many times colors were used as symbols or have special meanings like mooring, joy or in latest time abstract meanings like red color for comunism and socialism.

From the begining coloring was used in caves or walls and later for coloring textile materials for various use.

Is well known the purple color specific for phenicians and this information is coming from over 3000 years. This is a fact that lead to the importance of textiles materials coloring in the past and even nowadays.

The colors used in the past were combinations of natural ingredients from plants, soil, animals, etc.

Unfortunately this kind of colorants is very unstable from different reasons. Chemical composition of them is a key factor but also because the organic compounds are an excellent support for growth of many types of

micro-organisms and due to composition rich in sugars and having high water content.

Due to this aspects the technology of coloring textile materials was turned in one of the most pollution one. In this way there were developed products fossil combustible based, sintetic substances and the use of high quantities of energy for obtaining and using in the textile coloration.

The stability of the colors obtained is influenced by several factors. In our study we compared the color of the *Prunus serotina* natural extract with two comercial chemical products from the begining and after exposure at U.V. as degrading factor.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Aims of the study were the following:

- Producing the colorant,
- Testing the resilience of the colorant in comparison with chemical products,

For fullfiling this there were established following objectives:

- Producing the natural extract,
- Finding the proper dosage in textile coloring,
- Assesing the resilience of the colored textiles by using U.V. exposure.

Producing the natural extract was done following the production flow from below.

Fig. 1. Producing the natural extract and quality control (Timar, 2020)

The main issues was raw materials management. In this way raw materials were characterized, conditioned and mechanical procesed.

Preparation of the extract was the second issue because it was important to maintain specific appearance of raw materials.

Preparation of extract from *Prunus serotina* was done by maceration in alcoholic solution in 1:1 ratio for 48 hours and then under vacuum extraction the alcohol was evaporated.

We pay attention for yield of production due high price of *Prunus serotina* fruits, short shelf life of them and in this way the fruits were ultrafrozen at -80 °C and later 24 hours immersed for maceration in ethylic alcohol.

The assessment of the extract quality was done by optic method – coloring scale.

Before using the extract it was stored at 0 °C to avoid alteration.

The textile material taken in to study was linen based.

The properties of the material are the following:

- Unmelted pure canvas
- 15/15 threads per cm
- width 215 cm

Appearance:

- smooth,
- semi-transparent

Color: Ivory

Print: Folk

Width: 215 cm

Weight: 190 gr/sqm

Composition: 100% linen

The chemical products used for coloring are the following:

Product A: Galus red, 10 g per unit.

Product B: La Nave No: 8 Rojo, 20 g per unit.

The textile material was cutted in pieces of 10x10 cm for coloring.

Finding the proper dosage

It was done by assessing the global quality of the colored samples in comparison with two well known commercial chemical products.

There were conducted trials with following concentration of extract:

- 0 % (blank sample), Sample 1
- 2 %, Sample 2
- 5 %, Sample 3
- Product A, Sample 4
- Product B, Sample 5

The coloring was done in the following way according with the producers recommendation:

Step 1: Weight the textiles to determine the required amount of paint. Use rubber gloves.

Step 2: Fill a container with enough water to completely cover the clothes and heat until it reaches the boiling point. Cool the water (30-40°C).

Step 3: Empty the contents of one or more sachets of paint into the amount of water and mix well, for example using a wooden spoon, until it dissolves.

Step 4: Put the clean and damp clothes in the container, keep the water temperature for 30 minutes, and then remove the clothes.

Step 5: Add 6 tablespoons of vinegar. Maintain the temperature for another 30 minutes. Shut down the fire and keep the product in solution, gently removing the clothes from time to time, until the water cools. Rinse with plenty of water until no more color comes out. Do not squeeze the clothes. Dry in the shade.

Step 6: To clean the utensils, put hot water in the container in which you painted, dissolve the contents of the cleaning product and insert the rest of the utensils used. Let them soak for an hour, after which you can easily clean them. If this box does not contain the envelope with the cleaning product, use lye and a measure of your usual detergent. Never use the cleaning product with your clothes as it will damage them.

For *Prunus serotina* natural extract the coloring is done in similar way without preparation of coloring solution that is natural extract themselves.

Fig. 2. Production flow for coloring

After drying the samples were exposed at an U.V. source with the following properties:

- LAMP OSAGA 2G 11
- Power - 18W
- Wave lenght - 253.7 nm.

Fig. 3. Experimental device for U.V. exposure

The Figure 3. Is presenting the experimental device. The exposure was done for 24, 48 and 72 hours. Afer each increment was done the color assesment.

The red color assessment was done according color codification as is presented in figure 4.

PMS 1555	PMS 1565	PMS 1575	PMS 1585	PMS 1595	PMS 1605	PMS 1615
PMS 162	PMS 163	PMS 164	PMS 165	PMS 166	PMS 167	PMS 168
PMS 1625	PMS 1635	PMS 1645	PMS 1655	PMS 1665	PMS 1675	PMS 1685
PMS 169	PMS 170	PMS 171	PMS 172	PMS 173	PMS 174	PMS 175
PMS 176	PMS 177	PMS 178	Warm Red	PMS 179	PMS 180	PMS 181
PMS 1765	PMS 1775	PMS 1785	PMS 1788	PMS 1795	PMS 1805	PMS 1815
PMS 1767	PMS 1777	PMS 1787	Red 032	PMS 1797	PMS 1807	PMS 1817
PMS 182	PMS 183	PMS 184	PMS 185	PMS 186	PMS 187	PMS 188
PMS 189	PMS 190	PMS 191	PMS 192	PMS 193	PMS 194	PMS 195
PMS 1895	PMS 1905	PMS 1915	PMS 1925	PMS 1935	PMS 1945	PMS 1955
PMS 196	PMS 197	PMS 198	PMS 199	PMS 200	PMS 201	PMS 202
PMS 203	PMS 204	PMS 205	PMS 206	PMS 207	PMS 208	PMS 209
PMS 210	PMS 211	PMS 212	PMS 213	PMS 214	PMS 215	PMS 216

Fig. 4. Color codes for red

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first set of results was obtained after coloring and drying. The results are presented in table 1.

There was record that colors were intens and the samples colored with natural extract are almost in the same range of color like the chemical compounds based dyes.

Table 1.

Comparison of color after coloring and drying

No. Crt.	Sample	Color code
1	Sample 1	withe
2	Sample 2	PMS 1805
3	Sample 3	PMS 1807
4	Sample 4	PMS 1817
5	Sample 5	PMS 1815

The second set of data are reffering to the color assesment after 24 hours of U.V. exposure. The results are presented in table 2.

Table 2.

Comparison of color after 24 hours of U.V. exposure

No. Crt.	Sample	Color code	
		At the begining of the experience	After 24 hours of U.V. exposure
1	Sample 1	withe	withe
2	Sample 2	PMS 1805	PMS 1795
3	Sample 3	PMS 1807	PMS 1797
4	Sample 4	PMS 1817	PMS 1805
5	Sample 5	PMS 1815	PMS 1807

There was recorded that color of the natural extract based textiles become lighter than chemical based products samples.

The third set of data are reffering to the color assesment after 48 hours of U.V. exposure. The results are presented in table 3.

Table 3.

Comparison of color after 48 hours of U.V. exposure

No. Crt.	Sample	Color code		
		At the begining of the experience	After 24 hours of U.V. exposure	After 48 hours of U.V. exposure
1	Sample 1	withe	withe	withe
2	Sample 2	PMS 1805	PMS 1795	PMS 1788
3	Sample 3	PMS 1807	PMS 1797	PMS 1788
4	Sample 4	PMS 1817	PMS 1805	Warm Red
5	Sample 5	PMS 1815	PMS 1807	PMS 179

There was recorded that color of the natural extract based textiles recover and was in similar range like chemical based products samples.

The forth set of data are reffering to the color assesment after 72 hours of U.V. exposure. The results are presented in table 4.

There color of the natural extract based textiles become once again lighter than chemical based products samples. Howewer the color of natural extract based textiles was brighter.

Table 4.

Comparison of color aft
er 72 hours of U.V. exposure

No. Crt.	Sample	Color code			
		At the begining of the experience	After 24 hours of U.V. exposure	After 48 hours of U.V. exposure	After 72 hours of U.V. exposure
1	Sample 1	withe	withe	withe	withe
2	Sample 2	PMS 1805	PMS 1795	PMS 1788	Red 032
3	Sample 3	PMS 1807	PMS 1797	PMS 1788	PMS 185
4	Sample 4	PMS 1817	PMS 1805	Warm Red	PMS 185
5	Sample 5	PMS 1815	PMS 1807	PMS 179	PMS 185

CONCLUSIONS

Natural compounds enjoy positive consumer image and have application in obtaining of traditional products. The natural compounds used shown properties comparable with chemical based products but the resilience was not so strong.

This aspect despite reduce the efficiency was compensated by reduced carbon footprint do to use of fruits that are growing spontaneous in the forests and preparation of coloring solution demand small energy quantities and produce no pollutants.

RECOMANDATIONS

The most importnt recomandation that we are propose is related with the extraction time that we are proposed to be extended in the future.

Another recomandation that was drawn was the comparison of natural coloring compounds from extract and the antioxidant activity in order to predict the paint quality.

Also there are different other plants from spontaneous flora that we propose to be take in to study and compared with current results like *Viscum*

nigra, *Atropa beladona*, *Ribes nigrum*, *Vaccinium myrtillus* and blue varieties of *Vitis vinifera*.

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THE INFLUENCE OF GROWTH REGULATORS ON THE PRODUCTIVITY OF WINTER WHEAT IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE WESTERN PLAIN

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Abstract

Winter wheat is one of the agricultural plants that reacts positively to the application of fertilizers in all soil and climatic conditions in our country, but which can cause under certain conditions the fall of plants.

In order to avoid this, it is necessary to apply a correct cultivation technology, which also includes carrying out preventive treatments by using certain substances with retarding effect, such as growth regulators.

Growth regulators are organic compounds with retarding action that are of particular interest in wheat cultivation. They are produced on the basis of chlorocholine chloride, which is applied foliarly, during the straw elongation period.

In order to highlight the role of growth regulators in the autumn wheat cultivation technology, the level of production and its quality for the Exotic wheat variety was analyzed, using a differentiated application of the growth regulator doses: Medax Top in doses of 0.6 l/ha and 1 l/ha and Stabilan in doses of 1.8l/ha and 2 l/ha, compared to the untreated control.

Key words: growth regulators, retardant action, plant fall, chlorocholine chloride

INTRODUCTION

Wheat is demanding on fertilizers due to the following peculiarities: its root system is poorly developed and with poor solubilizing power compared to more insoluble compounds in the soil; although it has a long period of vegetation, most of the nutrients are extracted in a short time, from filling to maturity in milk: 70-92% N, 75-88% P₂O₅ 85-88% K₂O (Borcean et al., 2006).

The best results in the application of chemical fertilizers are obtained when all methods of application are used, before sowing, to sowing, during vegetation, by a judicious combination of the different forms and doses to be applied, in relation to the variable needs of the plants, so that they are provided with necessary substances throughout the vegetation (Oancea, 2005).

The fall of cereals can cause significant crop losses and occurs mainly in the years when the evolution of climatic factors favors the excessive growth of the vegetative mass and the reduction of the resistance tissues of the stem. The phenomenon is favored by high sowing density, early sowing and fertilization with excess nitrogen or without respecting the balance in the soil supply with phosphorus and potassium. (Sin, 2005).

Preventing the fall of wheat plants is a necessary task sometimes especially in wetlands and in conditions of application of high doses of nitrogen fertilizers. To prevent wheat from falling, along with the application of a correct cultivation technology, preventive treatments are recommended at the beginning of straw elongation (simultaneously with herbicide), using substances with retarding action (dwarfing) based on chlorocholine chloride, known under various trade names: Cycocel , CCC, Cycogan, Stabilan etc. (Borza, Stanciu, 2010).

The main effect on wheat plants is to reduce the size of wheat plants, especially by shortening internodes 1 and 2 or 3 and 4, depending on when the treatment is applied. At the same time, the product has a positive effect on the thickening of the internodes. Chlorocholine chloride therefore has a dwarfing action and the direct consequence of this action is to increase the fall resistance of wheat plants (Ceapoiu, 1984).

The treatment of wheat crop with Cycocel also has the effect of increasing production, different increases from 3q/ha to over 13q/ha. Cycocel is administered extraradically, in spring, at the beginning of the straw elongation. The treatment can be carried out simultaneously with the application of herbicides, because the physical mixture is compatible and, as such, the nanizant does not change its type of action. Cycocel acts on plants, in general, by blocking the synthesis of gibberellin and by reducing the biosynthesis of endogenous auxins (Bîlteanu, 2003).

Some research has considered the effect of treating wheat seeds with Cycocel. Wetting the seeds for 2.5-4 hours in 10% Cycocel solution and drying them until the state in which mechanized sowing becomes possible, I.Radonțev et al. (1969), obtained in 3 varieties of wheat, an obvious deepening of the twinning node and a significant increase in plant resistance to winter conditions. It also obtained positive results in the accumulation of dry matter in autumn and in the increase of grain production. (Bîlteanu, Bîrnaure, 1989)

By applying treatments with growth regulators, the following results are obtained: reduction of plant height by 25-30 cm, shortening and thickening of the basal internodes, developments of the sclerenchymal tissue and thus an increase to overall resistance to fall, redistribution of assimilates between plant organs and as a result, increase of the leaf area, the number of grains in ear, MMB and productions. Crops with increased fall resistance and which can be harvested mechanically without difficulty are obtained (Muntean L.S., 2001).

Medax Top is a grain growth regulator, which increases the resistance of plants to falling, and avoids production losses. The stimulating effect of rooting due to the active substance prohexadione calcium is very

pronounced, manifests itself quickly and is not matched by any other ingredient.

Increased root growth means improved anchoring of plants in the soil, additional access to water and nutrients, reduced stress due to root diseases and drought, increased production of cytokinins (cytokinins play a major role in improving production factors). Medax Top can improve twinning in winter wheat more than untreated crops or those treated with other substances with a growth regulator effect (BASF, 2017).

Stabilan is a versatile growth regulator, capable of producing a wide range of physiological changes in different species of plant varieties. It is quickly absorbed into plants within 2-4 hours, especially in conditions of high humidity. It acts on the waist of plants as a growth inhibitor, stimulates fruiting and fruit quality. Stabilan applied to wheat, causes the straw to thicken and it shortens the internodes, thus preventing the plants from falling. (<https://www.ultrasunetedaunatori.ro/produs/tratamente-agricole/plante/ingrasamant-foliar/regulator-de-crestere-stabilan>).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Research on the influence of growth regulators on wheat production and its quality was carried out at the Exotic wheat variety, at the Leș Bihor agricultural farm, in 2020.

The factors looked at were:

- Factor A - Type of growth regulator
 - Medax Top
 - Stabilan
- Factor B - Doses of growth regulators:
 - V1 - Witness
 - V2 - dose of 0.6l/ha - Medax Top
 - V3 - dose of 1.0 l/ha - Medax Top
 - V4 - dose of 1.8 l/ha - Stabilan
 - V5 - dose of 2.0 l/ha - Stabilan

Two working variants and a common control of each type of growth regulator were studied. The 2 variants studied were treated with doses of 0.6 l/ha and 1 l/ha in the case of Medax Top application, which is in the form of a concentrated suspension, having active substances 300g/l mepiquat chloride + 50g/l prohexadione– calcium, and Stabilan was applied in doses of 1.8 l/ha and 2.0 l/ha, which has as active substance 400 g/l chloromecate chloride.

The cultivation technology applied to the Exotic wheat variety complied with the specific technological requirements of the wheat in the

conditions of a luvic brown soil, and the sowing was carried out in the optimal period October 10-20.

The application of growth regulators was done during the vegetation period, from the elongation of the stem up until the appearance of the standard leaf, in a single treatment.

The analysis of the production level and its quality for the Exotic wheat variety was performed under the conditions of nitrogen fertilization and complex chemical fertilizers with nitrogen and phosphorus NP 20:20. The variant chosen as a control was V1 - untreated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Efficiency of growth regulators on the level of production of winter wheat.

The research on the efficiency of the application of growth regulators on the production level to the Exotic winter wheat variety carried out in 2 working variants for each type of growth regulator depending on the administered doses, is presented in table 1.

Table 1

The influence of the application of growth regulators on the production of the Exotic winter wheat variety, Leş-Bihor, 2020

Type of growth regulator	Dosage	Production		The difference	
		Kg/ha	%	Kg/ha	%
Medax Top	V ₁ - Martor	4750	100	-	-
	V ₂ - 0.6 l/ha	5460	115	+710	15
	V ₃ - 1.0 l/h	5680	120	+930	20
Stabilan	V ₁ - Martor	4750	100	-	-
	V ₄ - 1.8 l/ha	5320	112	+570	12
	V ₅ - 2.0 l/ha	5610	118	+860	18

The level of production for the Exotic wheat variety in 2020, shows significant differences compared to the control depending on the type and dose of growth regulator applied.

By applying the Medax Top growth regulator, at a dose of 0.6 l/ha, the production obtained was 5460 kg/ha, achieving a production increase of 115%, compared to the untreated control variant; and by applying the maximum recommended dose of 1.2 l/ha, the production achieved was 5680 kg/ha, and a production increase of 120%.

When applying the Stabilan growth regulator, production increases are also achieved depending on the dosage. By applying a dose of 1.8 l/ha, the production was 5320 kg/ha, obtaining a production increase of 112% compared to the untreated Control variant; and by applying the dose of 2 l/ha, the production obtained was 5610 kg / ha, with a production increase of 118%.

At the Medax Top growth regulator, the production increase was between 710-930 kg/ha, and the percentage between 15-20%, compared to Witness, and Stablan, achieved a production increase between 570-860 kg/ha, the percentage being 12-18%.

2. Influence of the application of growth regulators on the mass of 1000 grains of winter wheat

The application of growth regulators together with fertilization with higher doses of nitrogen, determines the shortening of plant height, combating the phenomenon of fall and an increase in production of 10-20%, by increasing the number of grains in the ear and an increase in mass of 1000 grains.

In terms of the quality of wheat production, at the level of 2020 studied, by applying growth regulators in crop technology, the mass of 1000 grains, there are differences depending on the type of growth regulator and the dose applied (Table 2).

Table 2

The influence of the application of growth regulators on quality production for the Exotic winter wheat variety, Leş-Bihor, 2020

Type of growth regulator	Dosage	Mass to 1000 grains		The difference
		g	%	%
Medax Top	V ₁ - Martor	48.0	100	-
	V ₂ - 0,6 l/ha	49.4	102.9	2.9
	V ₃ - 1,0 l/h	50.5	105.2	5.2
Stablan	V ₁ - Martor	48.0	100	-
	V ₄ - 1,8 l/ha	49.0	102.1	2.1
	V ₅ - 2,0 l/ha	49.9	103.9	3.9

The mass of 1000 grains represents the weight of 1000 grains at the moisture content they contain at the time of determination, and it is an indicator of the quality of the wheat for baking.

In case of application of the growth regulator Medax Top, in a dose of 0.6 l/ha, the value of the Mass of 1000 grains is 49.4 g, representing an increase of 102.9%, compared to the untreated variant, and at the administration of the dose maximum of 1 l/ha, the mass level of 1000 grains is 50.5 g, respectively an increase of 105.2% compared to the untreated variant.

The mass value of 1000 grains when applying the Stablan growth regulator shows lower increases than when using Medax Top. By applying a dose of 1.8 l/ha of Stablan The mass of 1000 grains is 49.0, representing a slight increase of 102.1%, and at a dose of 2 l/ha, the increase of the Mass of 1000 grains is 3.9%, corresponding to a value of 49.9 g.

By comparing the two types of growth regulators, it is observed that the mass level of 1000 grains is higher, being between 49.4-50.5g in the variants treated with Medax Top and 49.0-49.9 g in Stablan, depending on the dose applied, compared to the untreated variant, which is 48.0 g.

CONCLUSIONS

In order to obtain wheat yields exceeding 5 t/ha, it is necessary to use growth regulators, which prevent the plants from falling and breaking. Growth regulators began to be used mainly by large farmers to protect their plants from the main factors that lead to wheat fall: the type of cultivated variety, fall resistance and stem height. Humidity, rainy weather and wind also directly contribute to this phenomenon, which can cause losses of up to 40% of total production.

Growth regulators contain active substances that behave similarly to the plant's natural hormones, regulate their growth and help strengthen the stem. The effect of growth stimulants on winter wheat is manifested by: stimulating the development of the root system to advanced stages of vegetation, which determines the stronger anchoring of plants in the soil and reduces the risk of falling; improving the physiological activity of the roots, which favors improved absorption of nutrients and water and increased tolerance to drought-induced stress.

Growth stimulants reduce the length of the wheat stalk, help slow the development of the primary sibling and stimulate the development of the secondary siblings, causing straw thickening and shortening of internodes, thus preventing plant fall, regardless of the choice of nitrogen-based fertilization program.

Growth regulators limit the development of the stem by height, which means that they have a flexible application window, from the beginning of the elongation of the stem, up until the appearance of the standard leaf, and the optimal application temperatures are between 5-20° Celsius.

By applying the growth regulators in the winter wheat cultivation technology, production increases of 115-120% were obtained, in the case of the Medax Top growth regulator, depending on the administered doses, and at the Stabilan growth regulator a production increase between 112-118%, depending on the doses administered.

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RESEARCH ON THE INFLUENCE OF CULTIVAR ON KALE CULTURE GROWN IN SOLARIUMS

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Abstract

Kale has its origins in antiquity, it was widely cultivated in the Middle Ages in Europe. It has recently been rediscovered due to its benefits to the human body. Research has shown an abundance of vitamins and minerals, anticancer actions, beneficial effects in lowering cholesterol, improving digestion and more. We cultivate quite a bit, most of the production comes from imports. The pedoclimatic conditions in Romania allow the cultivation of kale with good results, without additional effort.

Keywords: Cabbage, kale, leaves

INTRODUCTION

Cabbage for leaves, or more recently called "kale", is part of the group of cabbage vegetables, being cultivated for over 2000 years. The name kale comes from the Danish word "kåle" of Danish, Swedish and Norwegian origin, from the German word "Khal" and from the Scottish-Welsh word "cal" or "kall". Due to the very low requirements for vegetation factors, especially resistance to low temperatures, this variety has been a real success over time being cultivated especially in Europe. Its resistance to low temperatures enriches the assortment of fresh vegetables during the cold periods of the year.

Traditionally used as a fodder plant, its consumption as human food has been gradually abandoned in many countries. At the beginning of the 21st century, its nutritional qualities were brought to light, making these green vegetables return to the market stalls that they had forgotten. (Wiki)

Kale has an attractive appearance, with strongly corrugated leaves and different colours, depending on the variety and can also be used as an ornamental plant. Kale has a slightly sweet taste with an astringent texture due to its high iron content. However, the taste can be different depending on the variety. Kale has attracted attention through the richness of vitamins, minerals, few calories, with many benefits on the human body. According to some studies, kale is low in carbohydrates, low in calories. It is a good

source of fiber, calcium, magnesium, potassium, vitamins B2 and B6. It is rich in beta-carotene (provitamin A), vitamins K, C and B9. It offers remarkable proportions of copper, iron, magnesium, vitamins E, B1 and B3. Simultaneously with the increase in the consumption of kale, the research in this direction has intensified. German researchers have conducted a study to confirm the benefits of kale. A regular intake of kale could maintain an optimal concentration of lutein and zeaxanthin in the macula (Arnold & al.,2013).

Other specific constituents of brassicas, glucosinolates and their derivatives, have been highlighted by researchers (Capuano et al). Kale contains glucosinolates - such as green or red cabbage, broccoli and Brussels sprouts - in varying proportions, depending on the variety (Hanh & al.,2016). These sulphur compounds (responsible for the strong taste of cabbage) are used to protect the cabbage from pests and are transformed in plants or the human body (especially due to enzymes in the intestinal microbiota) into isothiocyanates or indole-3-carbinol (Rouzaud & al.,2004). The latter could prevent cancer by multiple mechanisms: by neutralizing carcinogens, by protecting the DNA of cells, by blocking the proliferation of cancer cells or by promoting apoptosis, their natural death (Capuano et al).

Diets rich in vegetables from the Brassicaceae family are associated with lower levels of LDL cholesterol in the blood, "bad" cholesterol (C.N. Armah et al). Kale combines soluble fiber (pectin), which captures some of the fat in meals in the digestive tract and phytosterols, which limit the absorption of cholesterol (Souci,Fachmann & Kraut).

Vegetables rich in carotenoids or beta-carotene, including kale, are thought to help prevent breast cancer, and vegetables rich in vitamin C help prevent colon cancer. (<https://www.wcrf.org/dietandcancer/contents>)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research was carried out in a vegetable microfarm in the Husasău de Tinca village (NV of Romania), certified ecologically. Being cultivated only sporadically in our country, kale is demanded by Romanian consumers, the largest quantity from us coming from imports. In addition to the promotion of this vegetable, growers should also benefit from some data on the variety of cultivation, which will make their crop profitable. In the autumn of 2019, in a 500 m² plot, a single-factor experiment was set up according to the subdivision blocks method, with nine variants in three repetitions, each variant had five plants. The nine cultivars were: Nero di Toscana, Westlander Winter, Red Ursa, Beurre Blond, Russian Frills, Wild Red, Hanover Salad, True Siberian, Siberian. The statistical processing of the experimental data was done by analyzing the variance. The media of the

experience was chosen as a witness. The culture was established in the last decade of October. At the time of planting, the seedling was 48 days old. The technology of cultivation applied was the ecological one for kale.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Harvesting in the case of cabbage vegetables is differentiated according to variety. Thus, some, such as cabbage, are harvested in a single pass, while kale and others are harvested in stages. In the case of the present experiment, the harvest began in the first decade of February and lasted until the first decade of April. At each pass, the harvest was done on variants and repetitions, the average production of the repetitions was recorded in table 1. The leaves that reached the characteristic size of the variety were harvested each time, any delay in harvesting leads to a decrease in quality.

The experimental data in Table 1 show that the cultivar significantly influences the production of leaves. Thus the absolute production / m² varied from 1.03 to the Westlander Winter variety and reaching 3.61 to Red Ursa, which is 3.5 times more than the first variety. At Red Ursa, the increase in production compared to the average experience was 57.65%, the difference was ensured statistically very positive. The second cultivar that exceeded in absolute production 3 kg / m² (3.12), was True Siberian. From this, 0.49 kg / m² more leaves were harvested than the control. The difference was statistically assured, very significant positive. The Russian Frills variety recorded in absolute production, with 4.6 t / ha more than the average of the experience, the difference being statistically assured, a significant significant positive. Of the nine crops grown in the studio, the weakest leaf harvest was recorded at Westlander Winter, only 1.03 kg / m², less by 1.26 kg / m² compared to the average experience, the difference being ensured statistically very significant negative. Another very poorly produced variety was Nero di Toscana. He managed to get only 55.48% of the witness's output. The difference from it was statistically assured, very significant negative. The varieties, Beurre Blond and Hanover Salad, had close leaf yields, but below the average production level of experience. In both varieties, the differences from the control were statistically assured, distinctly significant negative. Leaves from the Wild Red variety were harvested in quantities close to the average of the experiment, but the difference compared to this did not exceed the threshold $p = 5\%$, not being statistically assured.

Table 1

Production of kale
Husasău de Tinca, 2020

Cr. no.	Variant	Absolute production of kale kg/m ²	Relative production of kale %	± d kg/m ²	Significance
1	Nero di Toscana	1.25	55.48	-1.04	000
2	Westlander Winter	1.03	44.97	-1.26	000
3	Red Ursa	3.61	157.65	+1.32	xxx
4	Beurre Blond	1.82	79.47	-0.47	00
5	Russian Frills	2.75	120.08	+0.46	xx
6	Wild Red	2.45	106.98	+0.16	-
7	Hanover Salad	1.83	71.91	-0.46	00
8	True Siberian	3.12	136.94	+0.83	xxx
9	Siberien	2.78	121.39	+0.49	xxx
10	Average Mt.	2.28	100.00	0.00	-

LSD_{5%}=0,27LSD_{1%}=0,35LSD_{0,1%}=0,48

Table 2 shows the quality of leaf production for the analyzed varieties, both in absolute value and in % of total production. Regarding this aspect, it can be seen that, if in the case of quantitative production the differences between the varieties were quite large, the quality of the leaves was highlighted in most of them. Thus, the extra quality production exceeded 40% of the total production for all varieties analyzed. In this respect, the Red Ursa variety stood out with 63.15% of the total production, respectively 22.8 t / ha, in absolute production. The lowest amount of extra quality leaves was obtained from the True Siberian variety, only 44.23% of the total production. For the other varieties, the values of extra quality production as a percentage of the total were between 44.80 for the Hanover Salad variety and 56.73 for the Wild Red variety. The production of quality I leaves had values from 24.80% of the total for the Nero di Toscana variety, to 40.98% for Hanover Salad. It can be noticed that the leaves of extra quality cumulated with those of quality I, for all varieties, represent over 70% of the total production. Finally, the second quality represented very little for the Red Ursa variety (3.23%), but quite a lot for the Nero di Toscana variety (28.80%).

Tabel 2

The quality of the kale production
Husasău de Tinca 2020

Cr no.	Variant	Absolute production kg/m ²	Extra quality out of total		1 st quality out of total		2 nd quality out of total	
			Kg/m ²	%	Kg/m ²	%	Kg/m ²	%
1	Nero di Toscana	1.25	0.58	46.4	0.31	24.80	0.36	28.8
2	Westlander Winter	1.03	0.47	45.63	0.34	33.00	0.22	21.35
3	Red Ursa	3.61	2.28	63.15	1.21	33.51	0.12	3.32
4	Beurre Blond	1.82	0.95	52.19	0.57	31.31	0.30	16.48
5	Russian Frills	2.75	1.40	50.90	0.75	27.27	0.60	21.18
6	Wild Red	2.45	1.39	56.73	0.69	28.16	0.37	15.10
7	Hanover Salad	1.83	0.82	44.80	0.75	40.98	0.26	14.20
8	True Siberian	3.12	1.38	44.23	1.15	36.85	0.59	18.91
9	Siberien	2.78	1.35	48.56	0.94	33.81	0.49	17.62

CONCLUSIONS

The researches carried out in an ecological microfarm from NW Romania regarding the influence of the cultivar on the kale cabbage culture, highlighted some conclusions, namely:

1. The cultivation of kale in the ecological system is very suitable for the winter in a protected (solar) system.
2. Kale cabbage leaves harvested in late winter and early spring, enrich the assortment of green vegetables, the demand being quite high during this period.
3. Comparing the average production of the nine cultivars grown in the studio with the yields of other green vegetables, they are close, so the crop could be implemented by other vegetable producers.
4. With an absolute production of 36.1 t / ha and an increase in production exceeding 57% compared to the average experience, the Red Ursa variety had the highest amount of leaves, compared to the other varieties studied.
5. The lowest production potential of kale leaves was recorded at the Westlander Winter cultivar (1.03 kg / m²), at the same time with a lower leaf quality.
6. The analysis of the quality of the production of kale leaves showed a very good quality of the leaves in the Red Ursa variety, 63.15% of the total, extra quality and over 96% cumulated extra quality and quality I.
7. True Siberian was the variety with the lowest leaf quality.

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THE INFLUENCE OF SOIL WORK ON QUINCE PRODUCTION IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

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Abstract

Setting up a quince orchard is a safe and highly profitable business from the start. The lifespan of quince trees is about 15-18 years, and the fruit can be quickly exploited because they can be eaten fresh, preserved in compotes and are the raw material for the production of schnapps and plum brandy. It is recommended to set up the orchard with grafted seedlings purchased from certified authorized nurseries that offer quality guarantees and practical advice for tree maintenance. Quince bears fruit in the 3rd year after planting, and in the 5th year it reaches maturity and can produce 30 tons per hectare. Particular attention should be paid to tillage, which can severely affect the quantity and quality of the crop.

The most productive variety recommended for setting up a quince orchard is the BERECZKI variety, characterized by vigorous, self-fertile trees with large and very large fruits.

Key words: chernozem, nursery, self-fertile, treatments,

INTRODUCTION

The quince (*Cydonia oblonga*) is part of the Rosaceae family, being a rustic tree, frequently found in family households. It is a tree of medium vigour, with a robust appearance originating from Southwest Asia, being cultivated since antiquity. The quince is an early fruit tree which bears fruit 2-3 years after being planted and has a high production capacity. It is a demanding species for light and heat. If the plantations are located on shady land, the branches become bare, and the productive potential decreases. The root system is shallow and the crown is thick. The bark of trees is very sensitive, being affected even by superficial blows. The fruits are rich in gelling substances. For this reason, they are sought after for jam or marmalade. Quinces also contain sugars, proteins, pectin, calcium, magnesium, potassium, and iron.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the spring of 2014, the Berezki quince variety was planted in the farm belonging to PFA Gîtea Daniela, on an area of 0.50 ha, four meters between rows and three meters between trees per row (833 trees per ha).

150 kg N, 100 kg P₂O₅, and 100 kg K₂O were administered annually. During the vegetation period, the plantation was visited weekly so as to closely observe the evolution of the health of the trees.

Vegetation cover treatments were carried out against pests, according to the biology of each pest, the existing damage threshold, with one of the following substances: Decis Mega EW 50, Calypso 480 SC, Karate Zeon 50 CS, Faster 10 CE, Novadim Progress, Nurelle D. 1.5% Confidor Oil was sprayed during the vegetative rest.

Treatments with copper-based substances were the most used for diseases because they fight most of the existing diseases in quince.

During the vegetative rest, copper sulphate sprays were used in concentrations of 4%, 2%, 1% to better control the fungi and bacteria existing on the bark of the trees, by bathing the trees.

Funguran OH 50 WP at a concentration of 0.3% was used as a treatment in the pre-flowering stage while, during the flowering one, a spray with Aliette WG 80 was applied at a concentration of 0.3%.

During the vegetation stage, warning and cover spraying was carried out with one of the following fungicides or, if the weather conditions required, even mixtures of contact fungicide + systemic fungicide: Dithane M 45, Champ 77 WG, Systhane Plus 24 E, Score 250 EC, Topsin, Captan 80 WDG, Thiovit Jet 80 WG, Kumulus DF.

The soil maintenance in the quince plantation was carried out by preserving it as a dead-fallow.

The dead-fallow is especially indicated in the first years after planting and consists of superficially loosening the soil 5-6 times during the growing season, with the help of a disc harrow or a cutter. The execution of the soil mobilization works can be interrupted, leaving natural grassing to facilitate the circulation of the tractors on the plantations located in areas with a lot of precipitation during the fruit harvest. One or two manual ploughs do the maintenance of the soil on the row of trees in the first years after planting, after which in the following years the superficial loosening is carried out with rotary hoe with sensing device in the first part of the year, followed by the administration of herbicides in the second part of the year. Of these, Roundup 3-4 l / ha, Glyphothim 4l / ha gave satisfactory results.

A 20 cm deep ploughing was carried out in autumn, which tried to incorporate all the existing plant residues as well as the leaves fallen from the trees in order to reduce the possible outbreaks of diseases.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The autumn tillage and another 1-3 light interventions to break the ridge during the summer, plus spraying herbicides in the spring are great solutions for orchards located in areas with lower rainfall. The maintenance of the soil with mulch brought from outside the orchard is even more appropriate, as it maintains a lower temperature in the soil during the summer, allowing a regular activity of the roots.

The soil works depend on the maintenance system adapted in the respective orchard and aim at creating a loose, structural soil rich enough in fertilizers, with enough humidity and able to maintain an intensive bacterial life.

The main link in the chain of works that is applied to the soil in the quince orchards is the autumn ploughing. It aims to loosen the soil to a maximum depth allowed, making it easier for water and air to penetrate, to better apply fertilizers and, at the same time, to help the roots to penetrate and stay as deep as possible.

The best time to plough in autumn is 20-25 days before the leaves fall or 10-12 days before their turning yellow on the harvested trees. It is necessary to do it at the mentioned times as the active growth of the roots takes place in autumn, which helps to heal the wounds, and benefits to the maximum from the improved conditions created by ploughing. Leaving the land unploughed and often heavily trampled after the harvest means significantly reducing the active growth rate of autumn roots. The less rocky the autumn plough, the better it is for soil microorganisms and tree roots. Therefore, ploughland is harrowed immediately or after rain.

6-8 works are necessary in the rainy regions to destroy the weeds with the detachable disc during the summer, while in the dry ones 3 are 4 are enough. When weed destruction and loosening work are not done in time and weeds have grown too large to be destroyed by light mobilizations, the soil is ploughed at 10-12 cm depths and dug immediately. Particular attention will be paid to tillage in intensive orchards, located on slopes and terraces, which must contribute to prevent erosion. For this purpose, tillage is mandatory in the direction of contours. At the same time, it must be ensured that on the un-terraced lands and continuous terraces, with a sloping platform, the

working tools, and especially the plough, do not continuously and significantly transport the soil from upstream to downstream.

The condition of the soil at the time of the work is important for both the autumn works and the light work of loosening and destroying the weeds during the year. Working a too dry or too wet soil leads to the rapid loss of physical properties. For the effective control of weeds in the quince plantations and to limit the number of superficial works, which damage the structure, it is recommended to apply herbicides, supplemented with loose soil. Commercial herbicide products used in fruit growing are divided into two types: - preventive herbicides (which act on the root system of weeds at the time of seed germination. They should not be used in large quantities, as they may damage the roots to some extent, especially in young plantations); - curative herbicides (which destroy weeds through the aerial part) and which are of two types: herbicides that burn the leaves and stems of the weeds by contact; they give very good results only in dry (droughty) springs; if it rains after treatment, their effect decreases greatly; systemic herbicides - these are applied to the leaves and stems of weeds, after which they enter their body and are transported by sap to the roots, which they destroy.

These systemic herbicides are the only ones that destroy perennials: wheatgrass, creeping thistle, field horsetail, wild stevia, etc. However, one must take into consideration the fact that these substances should not fall on the organs of the tree (stem, leaves, fruit) because they cause burns and are toxic. Therefore, they must be applied in nice weather without wind, the pressure in the sprayer must be low, and the jet must be directed towards the ground. Very good results are obtained by applying herbicides if a preventive herbicide is combined with a curative one in a single treatment. The treatment can be done later in the spring when some weeds have sprouted. In this way, weeds are destroyed and the seeds in the soil are prevented from germinating.

Thus, in the agricultural year 2021, when we were dealing with a prolonged atmospheric and pedological drought, when the rainfall amounted to a total of 47 mm during 5 calendar months falling in 4 stages, and the temperatures between June and September were mostly above 33°C, and in some periods the temperatures were for periods of 5-7 days in the range 38-42° C, the lack of water was felt strongly leading to taking agrotechnical measures to maintain water in soil.

During the summer months with water deficit, the land mobilization works were reduced by repeated disking and milling between the rows of trees, from 6-8 works in average years to 3 millings. In the direction of the

rows of trees, only one milling was carried out using a rotary hoe with sensing device at the beginning of the period deficient in precipitation, after which mulching was carried out in the direction of the rows of trees with geotextile foil for mulching covered with a mixture of sawdust and chopped straw.

This mulch was made in the direction of the rows, covering them with 1.10 m wide geotextile foil on either side of the row of trees, then covered it with a 20 cm layer of a mixture of sawdust and chopped straw, materials that can be incorporated in the ground in autumn. Sawdust was chosen for its longer water retention capacity.

After placing this mulch, the mixture was moistened by watering it once a week, with the spray pump with the nozzles modified for this wetting. 2000 litres of water were applied in the direction of the row from one end to the other in the early morning hours, no later than 8 am.

CONCLUSIONS

The observations made during the whole vegetation period show the following data:

- the annual growths of the trees, whose rows were mulched, were (on average) 16 cm longer than the growths of the trees on the uncultivated control row

- the soil on the unmulched control row showed obvious cracks, even 4-5 cm wide, with detrimental influences on the roots, especially in terms of water supply to the trees

- the growth force of the tree trunk showed an increase of 3.6 cm (on average) in the number of trees on the mulched rows compared to the non-mulched control row

- the production registered differences between the control row and the mulched rows by up to 28.8%, from the collected data resulting the fact that we have a production of 15.6 tons/ ha at the control row, and 20.1 tons / ha at the mulched rows

- in terms of fruit quality, it was observed a decrease in fruit quality by the fact that the fruits from the production of the control row were smaller in size and weight, also showing sclereids compared to the fruits from the production of mulched rows. The ratio between the first and second quality fruit was 1/1 in the case of unpeeled rows, compared to 2/1 in favour of first quality fruit in the case of mulched rows.

For fruit species grown without the possibility of installing an irrigation system, the method of mulching the rows of trees is an acceptable

solution in terms of the costs involved, which can lead to saving the crop in years with a rain deficit.

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RESEARCH ON THE INFLUENCE OF THE CULTIVAR, DENSITY OF PLANTS AND CROP SYSTEM ON THE GROWTH AND FRUCTIFICATION OF EGGPLANT PLANTS

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Abstract

The general objective was to establish technological elements that would improve the quantitative and qualitative parameters, as well as the possibilities of cultivating eggplants in the ecological system, compared to the conventional crop system.

The general objective was a study on the influence of plant density on plant growth in some eggplant crops. The aim was to observe the plant's growth at 7 varieties of eggplants grown in different systems, using three variants of density made by ensuring different distances between plants in a row.

Key words: eggplant, variety, conventional system, ecological system

INTRODUCTION

A balanced diet involves the daily use of both animal and plant foods, which provide, in balanced proportions, nutritional factors: carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, mineral salts, water and vitamins (Indrea, et al., 2009) .

Eggplants are among the 35 cultivated plants, considered to be very important for global food security, being included in Annex 1 of the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (Fowler et al., 2003, cited by Plazas et al., 2019).

Eggplants are annual plants in temperate climates, autogamous, developed in the form of a woody shrub up to 1 m tall and 0.4-0.7 m in diameter. Under the conditions of a warm climate, without frost in winter, it behaves like a perennial species, developing a woody shrub at the base, with a height of about 1.5 m and a diameter of 1-1.2 m (Apahidean and Apahidean, 2000, Post, 2008).

Compared to the environmental conditions, eggplants are the most demanding plants, from the group of solano-fruit trees. Coming from a tropical area, with a monsoon climate (warm, with low oscillations from day to night, humid) eggplants have the highest requirements compared to natural factors and the field culture does not exceed the latitude of 48-50 °C (Indrea et al., 2012).

It is recommended to eat eggplant for people with rheumatic, renal, hepatic or diabetes, as they have anti-inflammatory, diuretic and hematopoietic properties.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research took place in 2021, in an ecological micro-farm and a garden of adjacent vegetables, in a conventional system, in Husasău de Tinca, a village located in the NW of the country.

The experiment was trifactorial with the following experimental factors:

- Factor A, the cultivar with 7 graduations: a1- Zaraza, a2- Violetta di Firenze, a3- Black Beauty, a4- Japanese Pickling, a5- Dourga, a6 - Monstrueuse de New York, a7- Listada Da Gandia;
- Factor B, plant density, with 3 graduations: b1-34,6 thousand plants/ha, b2-45,5 thousand plants/ha, b3- 60,6 thousand plants/ha.
- Factor C, crop system, with 2 graduations: c1- conventional system, c2- ecological system.

By combining the experimental factors resulted 42 experimental variants, which were placed in two rows on a 1.20 m wide foil, with a distance between rows on the foil of 0.70 m and between plants in a row of 0.50 m; 0.40 m and 0.30 m, for realizing the three densities established by the experimental protocol. The experimental variants were placed in three repetitions, the surface of a variant plot being 3.0 square meters (380 m²/experience).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiences were set up in early May. The first aspect analyzed was plant growth.

The height of the plants was influenced by the cultivator used, the number of plants / ha as well as the cultivation system practiced (table 1).

The height of the plants in the conventional cultivation system was between 41.03 cm for the New York Monstrueuse variety at a density of 45.5 thousand plants / ha and 56.87 cm for the Violetta di Firenze variety, at a density of 60.6 thousand plants /ha.

In the organic crop system, the plant height was between 34.59 cm at Monstrueuse in New York, at a density of 34.6 thousand plants / ha and 56.02 cm at Violetta di Firenze, at a density of 60.6 thousand plants /ha.

In both conventional and ecological systems, the plants recorded the lowest heights in the Monstrueuse de New York variety and the highest in the Violetta di Firenze variety, regardless of the density of the plants per hectare.

Table 1

The height of the plants in some varieties of eggplant cultivated at the different densities

Alternative		Plant height (cm)		
Variety	Density thousands of plants/ha	Conventional system	Ecological system	Difference
Zaraza	34.6	50.01	47.19	2.82
	45.5	52.33	46.32	6.01
	60.6	48.28	47.01	1.27
Violetta di Firenze	34.6	55.93	55.59	0.34
	45.5	53.05	51.11	1.94
	60.6	56.87	56.02	0.85
Black Beauty	34.6	45.06	43.25	1.81
	45.5	42.02	38.13	3.89
	60.6	50.89	49.91	0.98
Japanese Pickling	34.6	49.98	47.67	2.31
	45.5	43.78	43.34	0.44
	60.6	49.53	49.24	0.29
Dourga	34.6	42.92	41.18	1.74
	45.5	47.02	43.85	3.17
	60.6	47.44	47.28	0.16
Monstrueuse de New York	34.6	41.99	34.59	7.40
	45.5	41.03	37.16	3.87
	60.6	42.97	40.78	2.19
Listada Da Gandia	34.6	42.86	37.14	5.72
	45.5	46.04	44.54	1.50
	60.6	49.34	47.95	1.39

The difference in height for the eggplant varieties grown in the two cropping systems ranged from 0.16 cm to 7.40 cm. The largest differences in height were recorded in the New York Monstrueuse varieties 7.40 cm, at a density of 34.6 thousand plants / ha followed by the Zaraza variety with 6.01 cm at a density of 45.5 thousand plants /ha.

The average number of leaves per plant was influenced by the cultivar used, the number of plants / ha and the crop system practiced. (table 2).

Table 2

The medium number of leaves/plant in some cultivated eggplant varieties at different densities

Alternative		The medium number of leaves/plant		
Variety	density thousands of plants/ha	Conventional system	Ecological system	Difference
Zaraza	34.6	21.25	18.75	2.50
	45.5	19.50	17.25	2.25
	60.6	16.00	15.00	1.00
Violetta di Firenze	34.6	20.00	19.00	1.00
	45.5	18.50	15.75	2.75
	60.6	19.50	17.50	1.75
Black Beauty	34.6	20.00	19.25	0.75
	45.5	18.75	17.50	1.25
	60.6	18.25	17.00	1.25
Japanese Pickling	34.6	18.00	17.00	1.00
	45.5	17.75	16.25	1.50
	60.6	18.25	17.50	0.75
Dourga	34.6	20.75	18.00	2.75
	45.5	18.75	18.25	0.50
	60.6	20.25	19.25	1.00
Monstrueuse de New York	34.6	21.75	19.50	2.25
	45.5	20.00	17.50	2.50
	60.6	18.50	18.00	0.50
Listada Da Gandia	34.6	19.75	18.75	1.00
	45.5	19.25	18.50	0.75
	60.6	17.75	16.75	1.00

In the conventional crop system, the number of leaves / plant was between 16.00 pieces (Zaraza variety, with a density of 60.6 thousand plants / ha) and 21.75 pieces (Monstrueuse de New York variety, thickness of 34.6 thousand plants / ha).

At a density of 34.6 thousand plants / ha, in the conventional system, the number of leaves / plant was between 18.00 (Japanese Pickling) and 21.75 pieces (Monstrueuse de New York). At a density of 45.5 thousand plants / ha, in the conventional crop system, the number of leaves / plant was between 17.75 pieces (Japanese Pickling) and 20.00 pieces (Monstrueuse de New York). At the maximum density, of 60.6 thousand plants / ha, the number of leaves / plant was between 16.00 pieces (Zaraza) and 20.25 pieces (Dourga).

In the organic crop system, the number of leaves per plant was between 15.00 pieces, (Zaraza density of 60.6 thousand plants / ha) and 19.50 pieces (Monstrueuse de New York, density of 34.6 thousand plants /Ha).

At a density of 34.6 thousand plants / ha, in the organic crop system,

the average number of leaves / plant was between 17.00 pieces (Japanese Pickling) and 19.50 pieces (Monstrueuse de New York). At a density of 45.5 thousand plants / ha, in the conventional crop system, the average number of leaves / plant was between 15.75 pieces (Violetta di Firenze) and 18.50 pieces (Listada Da Gandia). At the maximum density of 60.6 thousand plants / ha, the average number of leaves in plants grown in the organic system was between 15.00 pieces (Zaraza) and 19.25 pieces (Dourga).

The difference in the average number of leaves / plant in the eggplant varieties grown in the two cropping systems ranged from 0.50 to 2.75 pieces.

The average number of flowers per plant was influenced by the cultivar used, the number of plants / ha, as well as the cultivation system practiced (table 3).

Table 3

The degree of flowering of the plants in some varieties of eggplants grown in different densities

Variety	Alternative Density thousands of plants/ha	Medium number of flowers+buds/plant		
		Conventional system	Ecological system	Difference
Zaraza	34.6	7.00	6.00	1.00
	45.5	6.75	6.25	0.50
	60.6	7.25	6.00	1.25
Violetta di Firenze	34.6	7.25	6.75	0.50
	45.5	6.25	5.75	0.50
	60.6	5.50	5.25	0.25
Black Beauty	34.6	6.50	5.25	1.25
	45.5	6.25	5.75	0.50
	60.6	4.75	3.75	1.00
Japanese Pickling	34.6	7.75	7.25	0.75
	45.5	7.25	6.50	0.75
	60.6	7.25	5.25	2.00
Dourga	34.6	6.75	5.50	1.25
	45.5	6.00	5.50	0.50
	60.6	6.00	5.50	0.50
Monstrueuse de New York	34.6	6.25	5.75	0.50
	45.5	6.00	5.50	0.50
	60.6	5.75	4.75	1.00
Listada Da Gandia	34.6	5.75	5.50	0.25
	45.5	5.25	4.75	0.50
	60.6	6.75	5.00	1.25

In the conventional crop system, the number of flowers / plant, in the first decade of July, was between 4.75 pieces and 7.75 pieces.

At a density of 34.6 thousand plants / ha, in the conventional system, the number of flowers / plant was between 5.75 (Da Gandia List) and 7.75 pieces (Japanese Pickling). At a density of 45.5 thousand plants / ha, in the

conventional crop system, the number of flowers / plant was between 5.25 pieces (Da Gandia List) and 7.25 pieces (Japanese Pickling). At the maximum density, of 60.6 thousand plants / ha, the number of flowers / plant was between 4.75 pieces (Black Beauty) and 7.25 pieces (Japanese Pickling and Zaraza).

In the organic crop system, the number of flowers per plant was between 3.75 pieces and 7.25 pieces.

At a density of 34.6 thousand plants / ha, in the ecological crop system, the average number of flowers / plant was between 5.25 pieces (Black Beauty) and 7.25 pieces (Japanese Pickling). At a density of 45.5 thousand plants / ha, in the ecological crop system, the average number of flowers / plant was between 4.75 pieces (Listada Da Gandia) and 6.50 pieces (Japanese Pickling). At the maximum density of 60.6 thousand plants / ha, the average number of flowers in plants grown in the organic crop system was between 3.75 pieces (Black Beauty) and 6.00 pieces (Zaraza).

The difference in the average number of flowers / plant in eggplant varieties grown in the two cropping systems ranged from 0.25 to 2.00 pieces.

Table 4

The fruiting of the plants in some varieties of eggplants grown in different densities

Alternative		Medium number of fruit/plant		
Variety	Density thousands of plants/ha	Conventional system	Ecological system	Difference
Zaraza	34.6	5.25	4.50	0.75
	45.5	5.00	4.25	0.75
	60.6	5.25	4.25	1.00
Violetta di Firenze	34.6	4.50	3.75	0.75
	45.5	4.00	3.75	0.25
	60.6	4.25	4.00	0.25
Black Beauty	34.6	4.75	3.75	1.00
	45.5	5.25	4.25	1.00
	60.6	5.25	4.00	1.25
Japanese Pickling	34.6	6.50	5.25	1.25
	45.5	6.75	5.75	1.00
	60.6	6.50	5.50	1.00
Dourga	34.6	4.50	4.00	0.50
	45.5	4.25	3.50	0.75
	60.6	3.50	3.00	0.50
Monstrueuse de New York	34.6	4.00	3.50	0.50
	45.5	3.50	3.25	0.25
	60.6	3.50	3.25	0.25
Listada Da Gandia	34.6	4.25	4.00	0.25
	45.5	4.00	3.50	0.50
	60.6	3.25	2.50	0.75

The average number of fruits per plant was influenced by the cultivar

used, the number of plants / ha as well as the crop system practiced (table 4).

In the conventional crop system, the number of fruits / plant was between 3.25 pieces and 6.75 pieces.

At a density of 34.6 thousand plants / ha, in the conventional system, the number of fruits / plant was between 4.00 (New York Monstrueuse) and 6.50 pieces (Japanese Pickling). At a density of 45.5 thousand plants / ha, in the conventional crop system, the number of fruits/plant was between 3.50 pieces (Monstrueuse de New York) and 6.75 pieces (Japanese Pickling). At the maximum density, of 60.6 thousand plants / ha, the number of fruits / plant was between 3.25 pieces (Listada Da Gandia) and 6.50 pieces (Japanese Pickling).

In the organic farming system, the number of fruits per plant ranged from 2.50 pieces to 5.75 pieces.

At a density of 34.6 thousand plants / ha, in the organic crop system, the average number of fruits / plant was between 3.50 pieces (Monstrueuse de New York) and 5.25 pieces (Japanese Pickling). At a density of 45.5 thousand plants / ha, in the conventional crop system, the average number of fruits / plant was between 3.25 pieces (Monstrueuse de New York) and 5.75 pieces (Japanese Pickling). At the maximum density of 60.6 thousand plants / ha, the average number of fruits of plants grown in the organic system was between 2.50 pieces (Da Gandia List) and 5.50 pieces (Japanese Pickling).

The difference in the average number of fruit / plant in the eggplant varieties grown in the two cropping systems was between 0.25 and 1.25 pieces, in favor of the conventional cropping system.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Plant height, number of leaves per plant, number of flowers per plant, and number of fruits per plant are influenced by the cultivar used, the number of plants / ha and the cultivation system practiced.
2. Eggplants grown in the field, in an ecological system, had a smaller size compared to plants grown in the conventional system.
3. The highest heights were recorded in the Violetta di Firenze variety, both conventionally and ecologically, regardless of plant density per hectare.
4. Eggplants grown in the field, in an ecological system, had a lower average number of leaves per plant compared to plants grown in the conventional system.
5. In the conventional cultivation system, the Japanese Pickling variety had the highest number of flowers / plant.
6. In the ecological culture system, the highest number of flowers / plant was registered for the Japanese Pickling variety at a density of 34.6

thousand plants / ha and 45.5 thousand plants / ha and the Zaraza variety at a density of 60.6 thousand plants / ha .

7. The average number of fruits per plant was the highest in the Japanese Pickling variety, both in the conventional system and in the ecological system, regardless of the density of plants per hectare.
8. The difference in the average number of fruits / plants in the eggplant varieties grown in the two cropping systems was between 0.25 to 1.25 pieces, in favor of the conventional cropping system.

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EVOLUTION OF ASCORBIC ACID CONCENTRATION FROM *ROSA CANINA* AND *HIPPOPHAE RHAMNOIDES* FRUITS TO JAM

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Abstract

This article presents a comparative study of the variation of the concentration of ascorbic acid (vitamin C) in the fruits of *Rosa Canina* and *Hippophae Rhamnoides* species, but also in their fruits paste and their jams obtained by boiling of the fruit pasta for one hour. The study found that the concentration of ascorbic acid was higher in fresh fruits of *Rosa canina* than in *Hippophae Rhamnoides*. This difference was maintained throughout the study. The concentration of ascorbic acid in fruits decreased over time and was favored by the presence of light and increasing of temperature. Even in fruits kept at 5 °C in the dark, the concentration of ascorbic acid slowly decreased over time. In fruit paste ascorbic acid was in a lower concentration compared to that in fruit, and in jams, the decrease in ascorbic acid concentration was critical. All these changes in the concentration of ascorbic acid are due to its very easy oxidation, especially by oxygen in the air, but not only because of it.

Key words: *Rosa canina*, *Hippophae Rhamnoides*, ascorbic acid, fruits, jam

INTRODUCTION

Rosa canina L. is a very widespread species from the Black Sea coast to 1700 meters in the mountain regions. In the spontaneous flora of our country we find 30 species of rosehips (Pârvu, 2002). The chemical composition of *Rosa canina* fruits varies depends by several factors such as the stages of growth and both geographical and climatic characteristics (Tiță, 2005). This plant is a species that does not need excessive light and heat to grow, and is very resistant to low temperatures of up to -30 °C, grows well in bright places, has moderate pretensions to water, easily withstands pedological drought and trophicity low in the soil due to the deep reticular system (Mihaylova et al., 2015). *Rosa canina* fruits have been used over time in human and veterinary medicine for the treatment of various diseases and due to the high intake of vitamin C (Donea, 2003). *Rosa canina L* products have a pleasant and aromatic taste, are easy to administer and have a mild laxative effect (Bojor, 2012).

Hippophae Rhamnoides L. is a bushy shrub, found on the banks of rivers, from the coastal region to the mountain region. *Hippophae Rhamnoides L.* needs a lot of light, it has good resistance to temperatures between -40 °C and + 45°C (Tiță, 2005). The fresh fruits have a pleasant and aromatic smell, with a juicy yellow-orange pulp, but they cannot be eaten

with pleasure, being sour and astringent, and if harvested after freezing they have a much more special aroma (Yao Y, 1993). The fruit has a great importance for human and veterinary medicine (Bojor O., 2012). It is a general tonic, has antitumor properties and can be used in diets because it inhibits appetite, but at the same time vitaminizes the body (Constantinescu. et al., 2004).

Ascorbic acid (vitamin C) is needed by the body for the synthesis of collagen, L-carnitine and other amino acids, folic acid and neurotransmitters like dopamine, norepinephrine and adrenaline, regulates redox processes, is a powerful antioxidant and intervenes in the regeneration of other antioxidants, such as vitamin E. Vitamin C also plays an important role in autoimmune defense and promotes iron absorption, increases the body's resistance to infections by activating leukocytes, helps detoxify the body and increases wound healing, ensures the proper functioning of the endocrine glands, the brain, heart and spleen.

In this paper we aimed to monitor how the concentration of ascorbic acid varies in different stages of preparation of fresh fruit from jam. The analyzed samples were the fruits of *Rosa Canina* and *H. Rhamnoides*, from the Beiuș area, Bihor county, their fruit paste and jam, keeping in different environmental conditions.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The samples were made from healthy fruits with a homogeneous appearance by *Rosa Canina* and *H. Rhamnoides* collected, washed, dried and weighed. Some of fruits were analyzed immediately, and others were dried in an oven at 105 °C for one hour. Other fruits samples from each species were kept for 3 days in the air at 22 °C or in the fridge at 5 °C. The concentration of ascorbic acid was determined from fresh fruit paste or boiled for 10 and 30 minutes in a closed saucepan to minimize the oxidative action of the air. Both *Rosa Canina* and *H. Rhamnoides* jams were prepared from 1 kg of fresh fruit paste mixed with 500 g of sugar, boiled for one hour. The *Rosa Canina* samples are shown in Fig. 1, and those of *H. Rhamnoides* in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. *Rosa canina* samples (fresh and dried fruits, fruits pasta and jam)

Fig. 2. Hippophae Rhamnoides samples (fresh and dried fruits, fruits pasta and jam)

The iodine used to oxidize ascorbic acid was obtained from an iodate/iodide mixture in an acid medium (Satpathy L et al, 2021). The amount of ascorbic acid was determined indirectly by titration with sodium thiosulphate of excess unreacted iodine with ascorbic acid (Ikewuchi C. J et al., 2011):

All reagents used in these experiments were high chemical purity. Only bidistilled water was used for preparation of all solutions. 1mg/mL ascorbic acid standard solution, 0,002 M KIO₃, 0,6 M KI, 1M HCl, 0,002M Na₂S₂O₃ and 1% starch solutions were prepared.

Samples were prepared from 100 g of crushed fruit, fruit paste or jam dissolved in 50 mL of bidistilled water with stirring and filtered. The filtrate was diluted to 100 mL with bidistilled water in volumetric flasks.

To determine the concentration of ascorbic acid in the 20 mL sample, 5 mL 0.6 M KI solution, 5 mL 1M HCl solution and 1 mL 1% starch were added. The mixture was titrated with 0.002 M KIO₃ potassium iodate solution to indigo blue. The resulting excess iodine was titrated with a 0.005 M Na₂S₂O₃ solution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Fig. 3 it can be seen that the highest concentration of ascorbic acid was recorded in fresh fruits of *Rosa canina* (284.01 mg/100 g) and decreased almost 10 times in the jam (29.93 mg/100 g) (Poiana M.-A et al., 2011). The concentration of ascorbic acid decreased after 3 days after harvest, and this decrease was more drastic when sample was kept in the light, at 22 °C (Inegedu Audu S. et al., 2020). A greater decrease of vitamin C was recorded in dried fruits at 105 °C (Mieszczakowska-Frac M. et al., 2021). In the fruits paste, the concentration of vitamin C was lower than that in the fruit kept intact for 3 days in the air, and when the pasta was boiled, the amount of

vitamin C decreased critically with the cooking time (Herbig A.-L. et al., 2017). Loss of vitamin C was also recorded when storing the fruit paste for 3 days, especially in the air, at 22 °C. In Fig. 4 it can be seen that the behavior of ascorbic acid in *H. Rhamnoides* samples under environmental factors action presented closely similarities.

In Figs. 3 and 4 it can be seen that in all the analyzed samples the concentration of ascorbic acid was lower in the fruits of *Rosa Canina* than in those of *H. Rhamnoides* (Oprica L. et al., 2015). A similar situation was encountered in the fruit paste and jam of *Rosa Canina* and *H. Rhamnoides* (Shivembe A. et. al, 2017).

Fig. 3. Vitamin C concentration in *Rosa Canina* samples (fresh and dried fruits, fruits pasta and jam) in different stage of study

Fig. 4. Vitamin C concentration in *H. Rhamnoides* samples (fresh and dried fruits, fruits pasta and jam) in different stage of study

CONCLUSIONS

In all studied samples, the concentration of ascorbic acid was higher in the fruits of *Rosa Canina* than in those of *H. Rhamnoides*. Higher concentrations of vitamin C in whole fruits compared to fruits paste was determined by the fact that the protective role of the outer epicarp of the fruit that prevented oxidants to degrade ascorbic acid. The presence of light favored the photochemical degradation of vitamin C, but this degradation was much accentuated by the increase in temperature and the prolongation of the exposure time to high temperatures (Stešková A. et al, 2006). Even at 5 °C, in the dark, a process of degradation of vitamin C, slow, over time was recorded. A drastic decrease of the ascorbic acid concentration was obtained in the jam preparation, which once again showed a negative influence of the high temperatures, like the boiling point. All these changes in the concentration of ascorbic acid are due to its very easy oxidation, especially by oxygen in the air, but not only because of it.

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RESULTS REGARDING THE INFLUENCE OF IRRIGATION ON THE ROOTSTOCK SEEDLINGS IN THE FIRST FIELD OF THE FRUIT TREE NURSERY

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Abstract

Water is essential for plants, being a basic component of living cells and tissues. Only in the presence of water can the processes of assimilation, disassimilation and gas exchanges take place. Once in the plant, the water keeps the cell walls stretched and thus gives the cells and tissues turgidity, which ensures the mechanical balance of the various organs. Together with the dissolved substances, the water determines the pressure of the cells and tissues, ensuring the intercellular exchanges. As a participant in plant metabolism, water is involved in the fundamental processes of the living world, photosynthesis, respiration, transpiration. In fruit tree nursery, as in all crops, the growing process depends largely on the climate and soil conditions they have at their disposal. Of these, along with heat, light, air and minerals, water plays a very important role. This paper is a research regarding the influence of irrigation in the fruit tree nursery, under the effect of different watering rules.

Key words: irrigation, rootstock seedlings, fruit tree nursery

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of fruit growing would not have been possible without the continuous improvement of the quality and methods of production of seedlings. As planting material, the fruit growers used seedlings from the spontaneous fruit flora. The high genetic variability of trees from these sources has allowed fruit growers to make a selection, for centuries, of the most valuable specimens (Venig Aurora, 2006). They were propagated by vegetative means, the only method by which the valuable biological and agro-productive properties were passed on to offspring, from these specimens were obtained local varieties, varieties that have long provided the necessary fruit on domestic and foreign markets (Drăgănescu, 2002). As the market demanded more and more fruit, researches were intensified for the creation of new, more productive varieties and rootstocks with high quality fruit and for the continuous improvement of cultivation technologies (Schmid, 2019). In the development and modernization of fruit growing, the main link was the production of planting material (Drăgănescu, 1998).

Raising the production of trees in nurseries is largely determined by the quality of rootstocks. The authenticity of rootstocks is a very valuable trait (Fazakas, 2000).

In order to obtain high quality planting material in large quantities per hectare, it is necessary to plant rootstocks in quality with 100% authenticity and purity, one year old, with healthy roots, with tender tissues, without mechanical damage, without wounds caused by frost and parasites, with a minimum length of 25 cm (Hoza, 2000). The rootstocks have multiple influences on the varieties regardless of the species we are referring to. Among these we list: determines the vigor of tree growth, influences the age of fruit set, influences resistance to diseases and pests, influences resistance to unfavorable pedo-climatic conditions (frost, drought, soils with excess calcium and moisture, sandy soils, etc.) (Klock, 2019). Due to the tendency to intensify fruit crops in order to increase the economic efficiency of orchards, and in the case of plums, the rootstock is one of the decisive factors (Cichi, 2006). That is why there was a special concern in our country in this field, which ended with the approval of a large number of rootstocks. (Branîște, Stănică, 2011)

Plum rootstocks are demanding of water, their culture being extended to larger areas in areas with a richer rainfall regime (Chira, 2010). From the large amount of water absorbed from the soil by the roots, for the synthesis of organic substances, the rootstock uses only a small part, the rest being eliminated by the phenomenon of perspiration (Mazilu, Duțu, 2014). In the case of planting rootstocks on wet and poor soils in which the soil solution has a lower concentration of fertilizers, the transpiration coefficient is higher than in the case of rootstocks planted on more fertile soils (Spira, 2013). By ensuring sufficient amounts of water in the soil, the transpiration coefficient decreases so that the water is used more economically by the rootstock (Maurer & co., 2016).

The operation of irrigation facilities covers a number of aspects related to water planning and distribution, rootstock care as well as the maintenance of the irrigation system (Ghena, 2004). It is a complex of measures whose correct application depends to a large extent on the success of irrigation. Failure leads to a decrease in the efficiency of the investments that were made for this purpose (Grumeza, Ionescu, 1970). Thus, the administration of uncontrolled watering of rootstocks, without taking into account their requirements, can have harmful effects not only on the production in that year, but also on their quality (Domuța, Sabău, 1998).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The main working methods were the experiment and the observation, to which are added the measurements performed on the plum rootstocks in the nursery, during certain periods of vegetation. The method of research is the drip irrigation on the rootstock seedlings in the nursery. The placement of the experimental variants in the field when establishing the watering norm was done randomly in four repetitions with 50 trees in the variant and 200 trees in the repetition. Through the research methods used, was studied the influence of two factors:

- Factor A- plum variety with two variants A1 = Stanley, A2 = Cacanska Lepotica

- Factor B- watering norm with 4 variants B1 = 0 mm, B2 = 10 mm, B3 = 20 mm, B4 = 30 mm

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Regarding the unilateral effect of irrigation, the percentage of seedlings caught showed an amplitude of variation of 9.80%, with average values between 88.70% in the case of the non-irrigated variant and 98.50% in the case of application of the watering norm of 30 mm, in the conditions of a reduced variability of 4.56% between the four irrigation treatments. At the level of the whole experience in this year's climatic conditions, the irrigation showed a significant effect on the capture of the seedlings related to increases between 2.58 and 9.80%. The increase of watering norms from 10 to 20 mm and from 20 to 30 mm, respectively, also had a significant influence on the attachment of rootstocks, materialized by increases of 3.47-3.75%.

Table 1

The average percentage of planting seedlings under the effect of different watering rules applied in the first field

Watering rule	Average percentage		Relative values (%)	Difference/ Meaning
10 mm – 0 mm	91,28	88,70	102,91	2,58**
20 mm – 0 mm	94,75	88,70	106,82	6,05***
30 mm – 0 mm	98,50	88,70	111,05	9,80***
20 mm – 10 mm	94,75	91,28	103,80	3,47***
30 mm – 10 mm	98,50	91,28	107,91	7,22***
30 mm – 20 mm	98,50	94,75	103,96	3,75***

LSD_{5%}=1,46 LSD_{1%}=1,98 LSD_{0,1%}=2,65

Regarding the interaction between varieties and irrigation (Table 2) it is found that in both varieties irrigation and respectively the progressive increase of watering norms showed significant positive influences on the capture of seedlings, with higher effects on the Stanley variety.

Table 2

The effect of variety and irrigation on the percentage of seedlings planted in the first field

Variety	Watering rule				$\bar{x} \pm s_{\bar{x}}$	S%
	0 mm	10 mm	20 mm	30 mm		
Stanley	u 86,25 b	z 90,25 b	y 95,00 a	x 98,75 a	92,56±0,68	5,37
Cacanska Lepotica	z 91,15 a	z 92,30 a	y 94,50 a	x 98,25 a	94,05±0,48	4,60
$\bar{x} \pm s_{\bar{x}}$	88,70±0,85	91,28±0,58	94,75±0,56	98,50±0,39	93,31±0,42	
S%	6,07	3,99	3,77	2,91	5,68	

Variety - LSD_{5%}=1,89 LSD_{1%}=2,55 LSD_{0,1%}=3,39 (a,b)
 Irrigation - LSD_{5%}=2,06 LSD_{1%}=2,79 LSD_{0,1%}=3,74 (x, y,z,u)

Based on the exponential regression, it is observed that in the case of the Cacanska Lepotica variety, the percentage of seedlings catching showed an average growth rate of 0.237% for each mm of watering, with the limits from 0.115% / mm to 0.375% mm. The respective estimates have an accuracy of 94.64%, in the conditions of a catch percentage of approximately 91% in the absence of irrigation. For the Stanley variety, the effect of irrigation on the seedlings was more pronounced, showing an average growth rate equivalent to 0.417% / mm, amid variations of 0.375% / mm between the last two watering norms and 0.475% / mm between the norms of 10 and 20 mm. The predictability of the logarithmic regression between the watering rate and the percentage of seedlings for the Stanley variety is 99.73%, based on an initial value of 86.31% in the absence of irrigation.

Table 3

The effect of irrigation on the planting rate of seedlings of different varieties in the first field

Watering rule x Stanley	Average percentage		Relative values (%)	Difference/ Meaning
	10 mm – 0 mm	90.25		
20 mm – 0 mm	95.00	86.25	110.14	8.75***
30 mm – 0 mm	98.75	86.25	114.49	12.50***
20 mm – 10 mm	95.00	90.25	105.26	4.75***
30 mm – 10 mm	98.75	90.25	109.42	8.50***
30 mm – 20 mm	98.75	95.00	103.95	3.75***
Watering rule x Cacanska Lepotica	Average percentage		Relative values (%)	Difference/ Meaning
	10 mm – 0 mm	92.30		
20 mm – 0 mm	94.50	91.15	103.68	3.35**
30 mm – 0 mm	98.25	91.15	107.79	7.10***
20 mm – 10 mm	94.50	92.30	102.38	2.20*
30 mm – 10 mm	98.25	92.30	106.45	5.95***
30 mm – 20 mm	98.25	94.50	103.97	3.75***

LSD_{5%}=2,06 LSD_{1%}=2,79 LSD_{0,1%}=3,74

Regarding the effect of irrigation on the percentage of seedlings of each variety (Table 3) it is observed that at Stanley the values were between 86.25% for the non-irrigated variant and 98.75% in case of application of the watering norm of 30 mm. Compared to the non-irrigated version, the other watering norms had significant effects of 4-12.5%. It is also found that the increase in watering rate by 10 mm was associated with a significant increase in seedling attachment of 3.75-4.75%

In the case of rootstocks for Cacanska Lepotica variety, the variability between the effects of irrigation was lower associated with an amplitude of 7.10%, between 91.15 in the absence of watering and 98.25% for the norm of 30 mm. The 10 mm watering norm showed a small and insignificant influence on the attachment of the

seedlings, instead the other two watering norms generated significant increases in the attachment percentage. The supplementation of 10 mm irrigation resulted in a significant increase of 2.2-3.75% in the percentage of attachment to the seedlings of the Cacanska Lepotica variety.

CONCLUSIONS

Against the background of the research climatic conditions characterized by a low level of precipitation in spring, irrigation showed the highest contribution to the variability of the percentage of rootstock in the first field (44.70%), significantly higher than the effect of the variety (13.27%) and fertilization (3.67%).

The Cacanska Lepotica variety showed a significantly higher attachment of the seedlings to the non-irrigated variant and under the effect of the 10 mm watering norm. The seedlings of the two varieties capitalized on a similar level of irrigation in the case of watering norms of 20 and 30 mm.

For the Stanley variety, compared to the non-irrigated variant, the other watering norms had significant effects of 4-12.5% on catching the seedlings. The progressive increase of the watering norm by 10 mm was associated with a significant increase in seedling attachment of 3.75-4.75%.

In the case of Cacanska Lepotica rootstocks, only 20-30 mm irrigation showed a significant influence on seedling capture. The supplementation of irrigation with 10 mm determined a significant increase by 2.2-3.75% of the percentage of rootstocks.

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**COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE REGENERATIVE AND
ORGANOGENIC CAPACITY OF *Opuntia* (Tournef.)
Mill. fragilis var. *fragilis*, IN THE PRESENCE
IN CULTURE MEDIUM 2,5 mg/l 3- indolylbutyric acid (AIB)
and a 2,5 mg/l 2,4dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D)**

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Abstract

Of all the cacti, the Opuntia genus has the greatest economic importance, which makes the demand for virus-free propagating material to be higher, which can only be achieved by in vitro micropropagation. (Johnson și Emino 1979, Escobar et al., 1986; Rubluo; și colab., 1996; Smith și colab. 1991).

Opuntia fragilis var. *fragilis* to initiate vitro cultures of lime strains prelevet hold with areolas mature, sectiont fragments of about 1 cm long and 0,5 cm thick but at least 2-3 areola. Hold the strains have been deposited on the sterilized culture medium consists of macro and Fe EDTA Murashige-Skoog (1962) Heller microelements (1953), supplement with two auxins, respectively 2,5 mg/l AIB (V₁) and 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D (V₂)

The evolution of the explants was monitored for 90 days. Their response was different depending on the presence in the culture medium of auxin 3-indolylbutyric acid (AIB) or dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4 D), in both cases new stems and roots were generated, but the presence in the culture medium of 2,5 mg/l AIB determined the highest number of newly formed strains 2,2 (157,14%) but also of 5,0 roots (294%), The genesis of the horse was noted only in explants grown on medium with the addition of 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D (V₂), on average 1,4 calluses/variant (140%) with an average diameter of 2,4 cm (240%).

Keywords: indolylbutyric acid (AIB) 2,4dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D), newly formed stems, roots, callus.

INTRODUCTION

Phytohormones are endogenous stimuli, but can be added to the culture medium, the exogenous form of synthetic compounds that have the ability to mimic the effects of natural growth regulators. In callus culture, auxin ensures high friability, facilitating the separation of cells in cell suspensions and somatic embryogenesis (Cachiță et al., 2004).

The presence in the culture medium of auxins substances with direct action on cell division, rhizogenesis and callus formation (Cachiță et al., 2004). 3 Indolylacetic acid (AIB), the only natural auxiliary is a less thermally stable compound and oxidizes in light, thus reducing its efficiency, is formed in the growth tips of the stems, but is also present in

meristems, it is known that the presence in the culture medium of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) plays an important role in cell growth and metabolism, the introduction into the environment being sufficient to induce callus (Sandra Aparecida et al., 1996).

According to Griffith, 2001 Pinkava, 2002 the genus of cactus *Opuntia* (fig.1) includes the most studied species in the world, due to the economic importance of this cactus. *Opuntia* cactus is an economic asset, it is consumed as a vegetable, but there are also edible fruits, also used as fodder (Kluge and Ting, 1978; Casas and Barbera, 2002). This plant is considered a good indicator of the presence of pollutants (Nobel, 1994), it is also considered an important tool to combat desertification (El Gamrat, 2004).

Fig.1 - Cactus *Opuntia fragilis* var. *fragilis*. Where: a - plant, b and c – fruit

The purpose of this experiment was to study how *Opuntia fragilis* var *fragilis* reacts to supplement the V_0 culture medium with two auxins, 2,5 ml/l AIB (V_1) and 2,5 ml/l 2,4 D (V_2).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

To initiate *in vitro* cultures of *Opuntia fragilis* var *fragilis* I keep prelevet strains with mature areolas but with less thorns trainers, shorts and white. The material so obtained was sectioned transverse operation which resulted dished washers that were divided so that eventually fragments were inoculated following dimensions: about 1 cm long and 0,5 cm thick, yet have minimum 2-3 areola. After these operations we obtain the explants from mid dial and lateral (fig.2).

After sterilization, the plant material was deposited in Petri capsules on filter paper discs (previously sterilized in the oven) in a laminar flow hood, horizontal air sterile operation, followed by sizing operation and future inocula removal of necrotic parts thereof.

Culture medium used for growth explants consisted of: macro Murashige-Skoog EDTA and Fe (1962), Heller microelements (1953), mineral mixture to which was added vitamins: pyridoxine HCl, thiamine HCl and nicotinic acid (containing 1 mg/l each), m-Inositol - 100 mg/l, sucrose - 20 g/l and agar 7 g/l pH of the medium was adjusted to a value of 5,8, its first autoclaving.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of *Opuntia fragilis* var *fragilis* young stems (a, b), and how slicing it into rings ellipsoid (c) and lateral explants inoculated on media centers and aseptic (d), where: ar - areola.

Medium free of growth regulators (V_0) and baseline media supplemented with 2,5 mg/l AIB (V_1) and 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V_2).

The culture medium was placed in a glass vial with a capacity of 15 ml (each container was placed 5 ml of medium). Medium vials were sterilized for 30 minutes, by autoclaving at a temperature of 121°C. After cooling media proceeded to inoculate explants, aseptic room operation performed in a laminar flow hood with sterile air. To obstruction fitoinoculi containers we used polyethylene, immobilized with elastic.

Containers inocula were transferred to room for growth, under the following conditions: temperature ranged from 24°C in peroda light and 20° during the phase of darkness and light was the regime fotoperiodic 16 hours lumină/24h, lighting cultures achieving is the white light emitted by fluorescent lamps, the intensity of 1700 lux.

Reaction and evolution of explants was monitored for 90 days. In this time period were conducted periodic observations and readings every 30 days. Values recorded biometric control group (V_0 , explants grown on basic medium, without growth regulators) were considered the reference as 100% being reported - every trait - all readings averaged every experimental variant part.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Comparing the results of the biometric measurements performed on the 90th day after the initiation of the present experiment, compared to the mature variant V_0 (medium without growth regulators), a slowing of the growth rate was observed in terms of the average length of the main strain at variants V_1 (supplemented with 2,5 mg/l AIB) by 0,3 cm, which is due to a very good and rapid development of the explants inoculated on the control group, while at explants cultured on V_2 (mean supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D) the absolute values of this parameter increased by 0,5 cm (Fig.4)

compared to the values of V_0 (1,6 cm), which which in percentage values represents a deficit of 18% in the first case and an increase of 18% (Fig.5) in the second case (Fig.4). Values that, statistically, are considered to be distinctly significant (Table 1).

Fig.3. Inoculi of *Opuntia* (Tournef.) Mill. *fragilis* var. *fragilis*, 90 days after inoculation of the "in vitro" explant. A-on basic environment modified by us and lacking growth regulators (V_0); B-on basic medium with the addition of 2,5 mg/l AIB (V_1); C-on base medium with the addition of 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V_2); d-roots formed on inocula grown on basic medium with the addition of 2,5 mg/l AIB. Where: iiv – the viable initial inoculum; mc – culture medium; nc-newly formed strain; rd-root; ar-areoles; sp-spines; cl-calus; mg-buds.

The average number of newly formed strains (Fig.3) was above the values recorded in the control sample (V_0), with a difference of 0,8 new strains/variant, in explants inoculated and grown on culture medium supplemented with 2,5 mg/l AIB (V_1) which represents an increase of 57,14%, while in the explants belonging to variant V_2 (medium supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D) there was a decrease of 0,5 cm (Fig.4) Compared to the control (1,4 cm), so a deficit of 35,72% (Fig.5).

At this time, the average length of the largest newly formed strains (Fig.3) was, at absolute value, at V_1 (mean supplemented with 2,5 mg/l AIB) by 0,4 cm (Fig.4), Above the values of control V_0 (3,2 cm) and 0,2 cm in the explants of variant V_2 (mean supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D), which in the first case represents an increase of 12% and 6% in the second case (Fig.5), results confirmed in our 2015 research (Vidican, 2015)

Table 1.

Results of evaluations of the values read in the vitroplants of *Opuntia* (Tournef.) Mill. *fragilis* var. *fragilis*, performed 90 days after inoculation of explants on basic aseptic media (V₀) with the addition of 2,5 mg/l AIB (V₁) and 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D (V₂)

Parametrul	Lungimea medie a tulpinilor principale ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificatia		Numărul mediu al neoformațiunilor caulinare ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificatia		Lungimea medie a celei mai mari neoformațiuni caulinare ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificatia		Numărul mediu de rădăcinițe ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificatia		Lungimea medie a celei mai mari rădăcinițe ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificatia		Numărul mediu de calusuri ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificatia		Diametrul mediu al calusurilor ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificatia	
	Varianta																																									
90 ZILE																																										
V0	1,60±0,15	0,0211	***	1,40±0,45	0,2042	**	3,40±0,32	0,1053	***	1,70±0,29	0,0800	***	3,40±0,29	0,0863	***	0	0			0	0																					
V1	1,90±0,40	0,1537	**	0,90±0,33	0,1079	*	3,20±0,84	0,7084	**	2,30±0,53	0,2763	**	4,70±0,75	0,5631	***	1,40±0,25	0,0632	**	2,40±0,30	0,0895	***																					
V2	1,30±0,29	0,0842	**	2,20±0,45	0,2000	**	3,60±0,41	0,1653	***	5,00±0,92	0,8421	**	9,80±0,88	0,7633	***	0	0			0	0																					

Legenda : „***” - foarte semnificativ, „**” - distinct semnificativ, „*” - semnificativ, „NS” - nesemnificativ.

Regarding the average number of newly formed roots (Fig.3), it exceeded the control in all experimental variants, thus with an increase of 3,3 roots/variety (Fig.4), Recorded in the explants of variant V₁ (average supplemented with 2,5 mg/l AIB) an increase of 194% was reported compared to the control group V₀ (culture medium without growth regulators), and an increase of 0,6 cm roots/varied at V₂ (average supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D), so an increase of 35% (Fig.5).

The average length of the largest newly formed root (Fig.3) also showed the largest increase in phytoinocules of variant V₁ (average supplemented with 2,5 mg/l AIB), which with an absolute average value of this parameter of 9,8 cm (Fig.4), Recorded an increase of 188% (Fig.5). Compared to the control V₀ (3,4 cm), significantly lower values were recorded for variants V₂ (average supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D) which recorded at this parameter an average of 4,7 cm, (Fig.5), so an increase of 38%.

Fig.4. Graphic presentation of the average values corresponding to the parameters read in the in vitro cultures of *Opuntia* (Tournef.) Mill. *fragilis* var. *fragilis*, on basic aseptic medium modified by us - (variant V₀) - with the addition of 2,5 mg/l AIB (V₁) and 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V₂), data expressed in absolute values ; (where: A – the average length of the main stem; B – the average number of newly formed stems; C – the average length of the largest newly formed stem; D – the average number of roots; E – the average length of the largest root; F -the average number of calluses, G-the average diameter of the calluses.

A. Average length of main stem strains

B. The average number of newly formed strains

C. Average length of largest new formed stem

D. The average number of roots

E. The average length of the largest root

F. The average number of calluses

G. The average diameter of the calluses

Fig.5. Graphic presentation of the average values corresponding to the parameters recorded at the level of in vitro cultures of *Opuntia* (Tournef.) Mill. *fragilis* var. *fragilis*, on a modified aseptic basis by us, with the addition of 2,5 mg / l AID (V₁) and 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V₂), data expressed as a percentage, obtained after reporting the values

monitored at the results recorded at the respective parameters read in the control group (V₀), without growth regulators, values considered to be 100%; (where: A – average length of main stem; B – average number of main stems; C – average length of largest main stem; D – average number of roots; E – average length of largest root; F-number callus medium; G-average callus diameter).

These results attest to the special rhizogenic effect that AIB has (Fig.3), On this species of cactus, in vitro-culture regime, and especially, added in the culture medium in a concentration of 2,5 mg/l. The results obtained at this parameter are considered, from a statistical point of view, to be very significant (Table 1).

The presence in the culture medium of 2,5 mg/l 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (V₂) stimulated the generation of callus (Fig. PP), forming on average 1,4 calluses/variant (Fig.4), It increasing to an average diameter of 2,4 cm, which represents an increase of 40% in the first case and 140% in the second case (Fig.5). These results were also confirmed in our research on *Opuntia* (Tournef.) Mill. *fragilis* var. *fragilis* in 2016 (Vidican et al., 2016).

CONCLUSIONS

1. After 90 days from the initiation of the in vitro culture of of *Opuntia* (Tournef.) Mill. *fragilis* var. *fragilis* we observed that explants grown on medium supplemented with 2,5 mg/l AIB (V₁) generated the most new strains, exceeding by 0,8 new strains/control variant, which represented an increase of 57,14% .
2. Rhizogenesis was manifested in both variants studied but with the highest values, compared to control V₀, are the explants grown on culture medium supplemented with 2,5 mg/l AIB (V₁) which with 5 roots /variant in an average length of 9,8 cm showed an increase of 194% compared to the control group V₀ (culture medium without growth regulators), in the first case and 188% in the second case.
3. The genesis of callus was manifested only in inocula grown in culture medium improved by 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D (V₂) which formed on average 1,4 calluses/variant, it increasing to an average diameter of 2,4 cm, which is an increase of 40% in the first case and 140% in the second case.

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IMPROVEMENT BY SELECTION OF ACACIA (*ROBINIA PSEUDOACACIA* L.) IN ROMANIA

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Abstract

In the broadest sense, the selection involves choosing from a plant population, based on well-established criteria, a certain number of plants that will participate in obtaining the next generation of the respective population, but which similarly follow towards the objective principle of improvement in the case of acacia, that of productivity of wood biomass. Certainly, besides the productivity of woody biomass, there are also other criteria that are worth remembering such as: resistance to pedoclimatic factors, nectar productivity, resistance to pollution, resistance to diseases and pests or the quality of wood.

There are a large number of selection variants, differentiated according to a number of methodological criteria. The present work presents a synthesis of the evolution in time of the improvement works regarding the acacia, with references from the most extensive theses elaborated by researchers of Romanian origin, theses that provided for the selection of trees plus and the creation of stands seed sources, up to current data on the selection and productivity of current varieties of acacia.

Key words: black locust, plus trees, selection, improvement by selection

INTRODUCTION

The ways of penetration of the acacia tree in the areas of Europe located in the south-east of the Carpathians, namely in the eastern part of the Balkan Peninsula, in European Turkey, in Macedonia, Bulgaria, old Romania, up to Bukovina and Bessarabia, are not from the west, from France, through Austria and Hungary, but vice versa, from the south-east, from Constantinople, the intercessors being, very probably, the Turks, and the period when this happened, it was a few decades before 1777. Constantinople seems to have been, thus, in the 18th century, the center from where the acacia tree spread in South-Eastern Europe (Drăcea, 2008;1926).

In Romania, the acacia culture has received special attention, especially since the second half of the Nineteenth century, being cultivated throughout the country, as an ornamental tree, but also in forest crops, in the lands with a lot of summer heat. It became naturalized, becoming a subsponatan, from the plains to the lower mountain area. The first acacia forest crops were established in 1852, in Băilești Dolj, so that, subsequently, the species to be planted on larger and larger areas, especially in Oltenia, on lands with moving sands. Besides that area, it was also used in other resorts with continental

sands, such as those in the north-west of the country, between Oradea and Carei, or those in Moldova, at Hanul Conachi etc. (Doniță, 1999).

In Europe, by far, the largest acacia grower is Hungary, with 345,000 ha covered with this species (Németh and Molnár, 2005). According to the data published by DeGomez and Wagner (2011) as well as Keresztesi (2013), at the end of the 80's, large areas cultivated with acacia were also found in the USSR (144,000 ha, mainly in Ukraine and Moldova), Romania (120,000 ha), France (100,000 ha), Bulgaria (58,000 ha), Yugoslavia (50,000 ha), Czechoslovakia (28,000 ha). In Asia, large acacia cultivators are the Republic of Korea (1.22 million ha) and China (1.0 million ha).

Today in Romania, acacia has an area of over 255 thousand hectares forested with acacia, representing a percentage of about 3.71% of the total area of forests reported in the forest system.

In all crop plants, selection is the main method of exploiting the natural or artificial variability existing, at a time, in the species with which they work. In forest species, selection, as a method of improvement, has many peculiarities imposed by the particular biology of each species. The fundamental principles of selection, for the forest species, were enunciated by Wright (1963) and are discussed in detail in valuable treaties of forestry improvement from our country (Stănescu, 1983; 1997; Enescu, 1975; 1985; 2002; Savatti, M. and Savatti Jr., 2005).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research was carried out between 2010 and 2021 in Bârzești, Arad County, Romania.

The main objective pursued in the improvement programs for acacia as well as for other crop species is the productivity of woody biomass. The character is very complex and depends on a fairly large number of elements of which the most important are: the height of the trees, their diameter, the tendency to infurcation, the growth rate, the resistance to winter frosts, the resistance to diseases and pests.

The researches afferent to the present study aim to evaluate the behavior of the selections of *the Oltenian variety* compared to *the rectissima variety* in the pedoclimatic conditions of the submontane area of the Apuseni Mountains (Bârzești, jud. Arad), following the ways of growing, acclimatizing and manifesting the respective variety in the installation period and the next period.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data obtained by measurements made on 50 individuals selected from each acacia variety taken in the study show that, in the period 2010-2021, the variety *rectissima* presented average values of diameter growth between 1.26 and 3.1 cm, values recorded at the height of 1.30 meters from the ground (fig.1).

For the *Oltenian variety*, the variability limits of this character were equally extended, with values between 1.19 – 2.8 cm and a coefficient of variability very close to that obtained in the *rectissima variety*.

Fig. 1. Average annual growth (cm) to a height of 1.3 meters.

Fig. 2. Average annual height increases

The results obtained in Bârzești, regarding the average annual increase in height (fig.2) of the plants selected by acacia I of the two varieties tested, are consistent with those from the specialized literature which states that, in general, the vigor of the Oltenian variety is lower than that of the *rectissima* variety. Obviously, there are real differences between the two varieties at least from two points of view regarding the height of the plants:

- of the speed of growth in height of plants;
- of the dynamics of the average annual increases of this character.

According to the way of assessing the selection criteria, it can be:

- **Phenotypic selection**, based on the visible and eventually measurable manifestation, in the chosen individuals, of the favorable characteristics pursued by the breeder.
- **Genotypic selection** is based not only on the phenotypic aspect of the chosen individuals but also on the performance of the offspring of these individuals. In most forest species this type of selection is quite difficult to apply due to the long life periods of the respective species.

According to the direction in which the selection is oriented, this can be:

- **Positive selection**, in the sense that only elected individuals, who have desired characteristics, are retained for the perpetuation of the population. This type of selection is specific to the improvement and production of seedlings.
- **Negative selection** occurs when all individuals who do not meet the characteristics desired by the breeder are eliminated from the population. This type of selection is commonly used in cultural works applied to stands of different ages.

According to the way in which the performances of the chosen individuals are traced, in the lineage, two fundamental types of selection are distinguished, namely:

- **Individual selection** involves assessing the lineage of each individual chosen and retaining those descendants in which all or most individuals have the characteristics desired by the breeder. The retained descendants will be multiplied (seminal or vegetative) and tested in comparative cultures (plantations) executed with the most accurate measurement of the characteristics pursued and the comparison of the population averages.
- **Mass selection** occurs when all the descendants of the chosen individuals are tested together, in the mixture, in terms of the characteristics pursued. Effectively, through mass selection, the initial population in which the selection was made is replaced by a new population, made up of the descendants of the most valuable individuals of the initial population.

Acacia, being a strictly allogam species, lends itself better to mass selection than to individual. Individual selection, by forcing the descendants of a single individual to pollinate each other, inevitably leads to the manifestation, to varying degrees, of the depression of inbreeding. Mass selection presents three distinct variants, depending on the number of choices made and the ways of grouping the seeds of the chosen individuals:

- *Simple mass selection with one choice;*
- *Repeated mass selection;*
- *Mass selection by groups of plants.*

Regardless of the variant, mass selection efficiently exploits the natural and/or artificial variability of tree populations with an obvious genotypic and phenotypic polymorphism. The efficiency of mass selection is expressed by the so-called genetic gain (CG) which, mathematically, is given by the relationship (Dudley and Moll, 1969):

$$CG = K \cdot h^2 \cdot i$$

in which:

K is an index of the selection differential whose value is inversely proportional to the selection pressure;

h² = heritability of the character pursued;

i = selection deviation calculated as follows;

I = the average character of the chosen elites: the average of character in the population under selection.

In acacia, the positive mass selection, applied to free fertilized plus trees (fig.3) or to trees plus artificially pollinated, is followed by negative mass selection applied in the form of thinings (eliminations) in the populations of seedlings resulting from seeds. The plantations thus obtained may be used as seed producers necessary for the production of forest saplings intended for afforestation. Depending on the effects on the genetic structure of the populations, the following types of mass selection are distinguished:

Stabilizing selection involves the elimination of extreme variations and the maintenance of genotypes with the highest representativeness in the population, which have the greatest capacity for adaptation and survival.

Directional selection favors the group of extreme genotypes (plus variants or minus variants) which leads to the displacement of the average population towards the favored group.

Fig 3. Trees Plus, Săcuieni Forest District, Bihor County.

Disruptive selection favors one or two optimal phenotypes over intermediate ones. Gradually, the population splits into subpopulation, some very close to the optimal, others very close to the minimum.

In forest species, including acacia, mass selection, positive and negative, also takes place in the form of cultural selection. The works of care for the acacias by applying cleanings and thins along with favoring the development of some trees from the most typical and vigorous drajons are, in fact, forms of mass selection. The mass selection, at the acacia, beyond its value in the improvement of this species, has an equally high value in the realization of the stands (orcharges) seed sources. In Romania, the identification of the seed source stands or the creation of new stands of this kind, started after 1960, reaching that, after a few years, to have about 65,000 ha of such stands (Bumbu and Catrina, 1982).

Clonal selection involves the multiplication of valuable individuals, chosen in the selection process, by organs of vegetative propagation (cuttings, drajons, altoaie, etc.). The resulting clones are tested in comparative crops, the most valuable being used in the establishment of seed-producing stands (plantations). In acacia this type of selection is very common due, first of all, to the ease with which this species can multiply vegetatively. At the level of all forest species, the application of clonal selection has led to so-called clonal forestry. (Libby and Ahuja (1993), Enescu (2002), Savatti and Savatti Jr. (2005) analyzed, in detail, the characteristics of clonale forestry, the benefits and disadvantages of this type of forestry, mentioning the fact that, in species such as acacia, where vegetative propagation is easy to achieve, at moderate costs, the benefits are much higher than the disadvantages.

The assisted selection of molecular markers allows the acceleration and efficiency of the selection process by diminishing its probabilistic character (GALLAIS, 1990). In principle, this type of selection involves the "binding" of a phenotypic character to a certain molecular marker, easy to highlight, at any age of the plant, by analyzing proteins, enzymes, DNA, RNA, etc. For forest trees this aspect is vital if one takes into account the very long time required to carry out genetic analysis using conventional methods. In addition, for the trees where it is possible to obtain intraspecific hybrids, the selection assisted by markers allows the choice of the combinations with the best chances to exteriorize a positive trans-heteroside of wood production and wood quality. It is also not to be neglected that, unlike conventional selection, whose efficiency is directly proportional to the size of heritability (h^2), the selection assisted by markers allows significant genetic gains in characters with small and very small heritability (Baptism, 1994).

Discussing the selection methods applicable in the improvement of acacia does not mean that all these methods have been and are used with the same frequency. In this respect, we consider that the presentation of a few examples can be edifying. As a rule, clonal, individual or mass selection was applied, depending on the characteristics that had to be phenotypically exteriorized by the new cultivar (Bongarten, 1992; DeGomez, 2011). A number of over 30 monoclonal and multiclonal cultivations were homologated and launched into culture during that period. Subsequently, nrcs (National Resources Conservation Service, USDA) concentrated acacia breeding in four universities located in areas with great extent of these species: Georgia, Michigan, Kentucky and Maryland, for the common acacia, red acacia and viscous acacia, and Arizona, for the Mexican acacia.

The improvement methods used were diversified (the selection of the half-sib and full-sib families, the selection of artificially induced mutations and polyploids, the exploitation by selection of somali variability, the transfer of genes mediated by biological, physical and chemical vectors), the results materializing in an impressive number of new cultivation (over 70), not only at *Robinia pseudoacacia* but also at the other three species of acacia related to the common acacia: *R. hispida* (Wandel, 1989), *R. viscosa* (Isley and Peabody, 1984), *R. neomexicana* (Isley and Peabody, 1984).

In Hungary, the first acacia improvement programme was initiated in 1960 and had as its main objective the selection of new clones with higher characteristics in terms of quantity and quality of production of industrially usable wood (Rédei et al., 2008). In several plantations, previously obtained from seed, three groups of individuals have been identified with these characteristics, in each group being nominated trees plus, resulting in a total of 40 such trees (Keresztesi, 2013). Vegetative material from these trees was used for their multiplication by grafting, the clones obtained being tested, in comparative cultures, at the Gödölfi resort.

At the age of exploitation, five of the most productive clones were homologated as new cultivation under the names: Jászakisári, Kiscsalai, Nyírsági, Úllői and Szajki (Keresztesi, 1994). Because, in Hungary, the areas with optimal pedoclimatic conditions for the acacia culture are quite limited, the acacia has come to occupy large areas in areas with suboptimal conditions.

The production of wood and its quality, in those areas, is far below what the new acacia clones produced in the areas of maximum favorability, therefore, the next improvement program, at the acacia, had as main objective the selection of new productive clones, with quality wood and which are able to tolerate changes in ecological conditions. The result of this new selection cycle resulted in 12 new clones, recommended for approval and introduction into culture (Rédei et al., 2002).

The acacia improvement programs, in the following stages (1983; 1996), used as initial material for selection inter and intraspecific hybrids, populations obtained from cuttings irradiated with Co60, 136 polyploid forms. The comparative orientation cultures (6-10 years), with the best half-sib and full-sib families, with mutants and/or tetraploid forms were organized in eight forest districts, with different pedoclimatic conditions, on a total area of 120 ha. The comparative long-term competition cultures (15-20 years) occupied over 300 ha and were organized in three research stations placed in totally different areas in terms of the degree of favorability for the acacia culture.

The results of these programmes resulted in the homologation of seven new acacia cultivation (until 1996) and the submission of homologation proposals for five other valuable new clones (after 1996) (OSVÁTH-BUJTÁS and RÉDEI, 2007). Unfortunately, in the specialized literature in Romania there is little data on the improvement programs carried out at the acacia tree and their results.

The results of short-term programs (1972-1975) were published by BÎRLĂNESCU et al. (1977) and, fortunately, the authors also refer to the results of previous periods, without delimiting these periods in time. One thing is certain about these programmes: they were part of a National Programme on forest conservation and development between 1976 and 2010. According to the authors quoted, in the period before 1972, some notable results were obtained in our country in the improvement of the acacia tree, among which they mention:

- identification and selection of 29 plus trees that have been vegetatively multiplied, the respective clones being used in the creation of the first 15 ha of acacia plantations
- identification of a new variety of acacia for the flora of Romania, *R. pseudoacacia*, var. *oltenica*, differentiated both morphologically and productively from the common acacia;
- the creation of 11 intraspecific acacia hybrids in which var. *oltenica* was one of the parental forms;
- selection of acacia forms of beekeeping interest.

The lack of large-scale provenance studies was compensated, in our country, by studies of behavior of acacia stands in different resorts. In this regard, it is worth mentioning the 16 experimental blocks with acacia stands of different ages installed by ICEF in 1955; 1956, in six forest districts: Ianca, Săcuieni, Calafat, Lehliu, Miteeni and Craiova. The observations and measurements made with a periodicity of three years, in these experimental blocks, allowed the formulation of some interesting conclusions regarding the increases in height, in basic diameter and the peaks of the increases (Armășescu et al., 1969). It was found that, at the same age of the stand, the

respective characters varied significantly from one resort to another, which reveals the importance of the environment and interaction, *genotype* × *the environment* in the phenotypic manifestation of the respective characters.

In recent years, in most countries with large acacia areas (China, USA, Hungary), the study in comparative cultures of the provenances of different origins is increasingly used to highlight clones / families with superior characteristics for one or more improvement objectives. We mention, in this respect, the studies of interfamilial variability of the intensity of photosynthesis and the growth of trees made in the USA (Mebrahtu and Hanover, 1989), the regional comparative crops in China with acacia clones for fodder (Zhang et al., 2013) and those from Canada and Hungary, for determining the variability of the quality of wood at the different acacia origins (Stringer, 1992; Rédei, 2008).

Probably one of the most interesting studies of origin is the one reported by Liesebach et al, (2004) in which, at the Institute of Genetics and Improvement of Forest Trees in Germany, 18 seminal descendants (families) of acacia, coming from the USA, Germany, Slovakia and Hungary, were characterized with the help of enzymatic markers.

The results were surprising by the way they differentiated these origins: a high variability, at the enzymatic level, was reported within the six populations from Hungary, combined with a very low interpopulation genetic variability. On the contrary, the eight German populations showed a low intra-population genetic variability at the enzymatic level, while the interpopulation variability showed very high values.

The authors conclude that, for Europe, a general valid model of evolution of variability cannot be given at the acacia tree, because it certainly depended, in each country, on the way of multiplication predominantly used in obtaining seedlings for afforestation made with this species.

The analysis of these results indicates that, in the early period of the acacia improvement in Romania, it was started, as in the USA and Hungary, with the clonal individual selection, which implied the identification of plus trees in the stands with an obvious variability of the traced characteristics, their vegetative multiplication followed by the testing of clones in plantings specially established for this purpose to obtain the seed source stands. Also from the work of the authors quoted above we learn that, in the period before 1972, intraspecific hybrids had already been obtained in which, certainly, the selection was applied in the descendants of F1 half-sib and full-sib followed by the vegetative multiplication of elites and the testing of clones in comparative cultures.

According to the data presented by Enescu (1975), by 1960, 79 plus trees had been identified, whose clonal descendants were tested in comparative cultures at the Experimental Station Craiova. According to the

same author, in our country, the first artificial hybridizations, at the acacia, were made by Bîrlănescu et al. in 1969, and the first works of artificial induction of polyploidy, through treatments with colchicine and/or with physical mutagenic agents, were carried out by Leandru et al., in 1971. The most significant results, from the point of view of acacia improvement, of the short-term program 1972-1975, reported by Bârlănescu et al. in 1977, are:

- Identifying and choosing new plus trees, which increased the number of plus trees introduced as clones, in plantations, to 66 of which 59 were clones obtained in our country.
- The choice of 50 new clones of beekeeping interest, which were to be tested alongside similar clones from Hungary and Bulgaria.
- Performing the first tests with clones from half-sib (maternal) descendants that proved that, due to hybrid vigor, as early as the age of 4-5 years, the clones of hybrid offspring significantly exceeded the control (common acacia).

In the current conditions, wooden resources must be well preserved. In rural areas, for the afforestation of degraded lands, acacia would be a solution to cover the needs of the population with firewood, along with other environmental advantages. In this regard, European funds can be accessed or the relationship between the citizen and the public institution can be encouraged at the level of the administrative decision. In certain situations, environmental protection in the name of the proper functioning of the community justifies restrictions on the exercise of certain rights, such as that relating to the protection of property. (Timofte et al.,2010)

In Romania, very little research has been done related to the genetic determinism of these characteristics on which the productivity of the acacia depends, to the greatest extent. A special mention deserves the phd thesis elaborated by Ciuvăţ (2013) which, based on the analysis of a large number of acacia stands, aged 1-4 years, from south-western Oltenia, elaborates allometric equations for the estimation of the total biomass and its components according to the biometric characteristics of the measured copies. Beyond the value of these data for the needs of the respective doctoral thesis, they could constitute a good database for calculating the heritability of the respective characters characteristic of the respective populations or as a resultant of the individual measurements.

CONCLUSIONS

Unfortunately, so far, in the literature I have not found any paper that attests to an oligogenoic genetic determinism for any of the elements of productivity or quality, in acacia. The small number (1-3)/large number (11-23) of leaflets in the leaf seems to be determined by a single major gene, and this finding can, indirectly, serve to improve productivity. If the parental

forms had as a genetic marker the large/small number of leaflets in the leaf, the hybrid individuals can be easily identified and then processed by selecting the hybrids with the highest level of trans-heterosis.

If it is accepted that var. *rectissima* would be more correct to be called *cultivar* and not *variety*, we do not see why the same rule would not apply in the taxonomic framing of var. *oltenica*, given that it was originally extracted as a subpopulation of lime. *rectissima*.

Regardless of the taxonomic category in which var. *oltenica* is or will be classified, we consider that it has superior productivity and quality characteristics, very similar to those of lime. *retissima* and a good adaptability to the pedoclimatic conditions of the premontane area in the south-west of the Apuseni Mountains. Based on these considerations, we recommend the extension of the Oltenian variety into *culture*, along with the *rectissima* variety in the above-mentioned area.

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**PHYTOCENOSIS OF THE *JUNIPERO-BRUCKENTHALIETUM*
PLANT ASSOCIATION WITH *BRUCKENTHALIA SPICULIFOLIA*,
JUNIPERUS SIBIRICA AND *VACCINIAS BIULINIUM* AS ARCTIC-
ALPINE, CIRCUMPOLAR, CARPATO-BALKAN DOMINANT
SPECIES IN THE WESTERN CARPATHIANS – BIHARIA MASSIF**

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Abstract

The phytocenoses of the Junipero-Bruckenthalietum association develop in forest sites with mountain relief consisting of high peaks, peaks and moderate to steep slopes ranging between 8° and 25°, exposed to sun, and strong and cold winds. The lithological substrate consists of siliceous rocks on which grow various soils such as humus soils and lithosols which are depleted of humus, rich in skeleton, with stone blocks on their surface, called rankers.

The floristic index of the plant association totals a number of 44 species, which shows a high biodiversity, considering the relief and the pedo-climatic conditions with impact on vegetation.

The phytocenoses of the Junipero-Bruckenthalietum association are dominated by hemicryptophyte species (65.90%), followed by phanerophyte ones (11.35%), and with regard the geographical area of the association, Eurasian species predominate (25%), followed by circumpolar ones (22.72%); endemic species share equals the Central European ones (i.e. 13.63%). With regard the ecological factors, in terms of soil moisture mesophilic species are dominant (40.90%), considering temperature, microthermal species predominate (56.81%) while regarding the chemical reaction of the soil, euriionic species are ranked first (25%). The karyotype spectrum shows that polyploids are dominant (59.09%), followed by diploids (34.09%). These meadows have a high ecological value because they host eight (8) rare, endemic, endangered species, enclosed in the Red lists.

The study of this association found in the surveyed territory, together with the analysis of bioforms, floristic elements, ecological indices, and along with the economic analysis and interpretation of cytogenetic characteristics, provides important information on habitat conditions, the economic, ecological and scientific importance of phytotaxa found.

Key words: phytocenoses, bioforms, floristic elements, ecological indices, karyotype

INTRODUCTION

In this paper, on the study of common juniper brushwood with alpine heath within the Biharia Massif, in addition to traditional phytocenological scientific information of the Central European School, flora inventory, the analysis of spectrum of bioforms, phytogeographic elements, diagram of ecological indices and genetic karyotypes, we aim at broadening the scope and interdisciplinary approach, the assessment of the

scientific value, and the sustainable management of the phytocenoses of the association, and of the protection and conservation measures for the species concerned. This association brings together subshrub and tree brush grown into the natural habitat of Community interest; Southeastern Carpathians spike heath (*Bruckenthalia spiculifolia*) and common juniper (*Juniperus sibirica*), code, R3107. Correspondence: Natura 2000: 4060 Alpine and Boreal heaths; EMERALD: 31.46 *Bruckenthalia* heaths; PAL.HAB: 31.4632 Carpathian *Bruckenthalia* heaths; EUNIS: F2.2632 Carpathian *Bruckenthalia* heaths (Doniță et al. 2005).

The aim of this research is to develop a floristic, phytocenological, ecological, cytogenetic, economic, syndynamic and eco-productive study of shrublet having *Bruckenthalia spiculifolia* and *Juniperus communis* ssp. *Alpina* as dominant species.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

We carried out our research in Western Carpathians (Apuseni Mountains) - the Biharia Massif. The biological material we were interested in consists of Southeastern Carpathians spike heath (*Bruckenthalia spiculifolia*) and common juniper (*Juniperus sibirica*) shrubs, which sporadically widespread in forests sites with mountain relief (altitudes ranging between 1,674 m and 1,832 m), consisting of high peaks, peaks and moderate to steep slopes ranging between 8° and 25°, exposed to sun, and strong and cold winds. The lithological substrate consists of siliceous rocks on which grow various soils such as humus soils and lithosols which are depleted of humus, rich in skeleton, with stone blocks on their surface, called rankers.

We carried out seven (7) phytocenological surveys in the most representative phytocenoses. In the association table (see Table 1) we enclosed all the species found by us, and classified in the corresponding coeno-taxonomic units (i.e. suballiance, alliance, order, classes), consistent with the constant (K), and according to the indications of the renowned authors (Borza et Boșcaiu, 1965), (Cristea et al., 2004), while observing the criteria of the ecological and floristic systems elaborated by Tüxen (Tüxen, 1955), and Braun-Blanquet (Braun-Blanquet, 1964), and based on the information of some more recently published works belonging to the various authors (Coldea et al., 1997), (Oberdorfer, 1992), (Borhidi, 2003), (Sanda et al., 2008), (Chifu et al., 2014). The quantitative criterion we followed in the research of phytocenosis is the abundance and dominance of species, according to the system developed by Braun-Blanquet (Braun-Blanquet et Pavillard, 1928), with the establishment of constancy classes (K = I-V). The phytocenosis of the *Junipero-Bruckenthalietum* association was analysed, and characterized ecologically, phytocenologically cytogenetically

based on the association table (see Table 1) and the histograms with reference to the distribution of bioforms, floristic elements, ecological indices and genetic karyotypes.

We identified and described the association based on the floristic criterion, with the help of characteristic, indicator, dominant and differential species. The name of the association is in accordance with the provisions established by the International Code of Phytosociological Nomenclature (Weber et al., 2000).

The information on the value of ecological indices, bioforms, floristic elements are presented according to works elaborated by various (Sanda et al, 2003), (Meusel et Jäger, 1992), (Cristea et al., 2004), (Burescu et Toma, 2005). Data on species' karyotype was taken over from dedicated literature too (Majovsky et Murin, 1987), (Sanda et al., 2003), (Ciocârlan, 2009), (Moore, 2009).

In order to appreciate the economic value of plants studied, we used the information from the publication "Flora României" (1952-1976) (*Romania's Flora – 1952-1976*), as well as data from another paper (Ciocârlan, 2009), to which we added our observations and findings regarding the use of plants by the locals.

To determine the status of rare, vulnerable, endangered, endemic species we used the "Red Lists" prepared by various authors (Boşcaiu et al., 1994), (Oltean et al., 1994), (Dihoru et Negrean, 2009), and the European Red Lists of Vascular Plants (Bilz et al., 2011).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This association was reported in Romania, namely in the following locations: Sebeş Valley by Borza (1959); in Țarcu, Godeanu, and Cerna Mountains by Boşcaiu (1971); in the Iezer-Păpuşa Mountains by Alexiu (1998); and in Retezat Mountains by Coldea (1993). We found this association in the middle third of the mountain slope between the mountain peaks Cucurbăta Mare and Cucurbăta Mică, on Cucurbăta Mare Peak and Bisericuța Hill, all belonging to the Biharia Massif in the Western Carpathians (Apuseni Mountains).

The floristic inventory (see Table 1) of these shrublet and brushwood encompasses 44 species, which represents a high biodiversity in this area taking into account the pedoclimatic and relief conditions. The characteristic and dominant species of the association is *Juniperus communis* ssp. *Alpina* with a coverage of 83.92%, ADm and maximum value of constant ($K = V$) while the differential and characteristic species for the association *Bruckenthalia spiculifolia* achieves a low coverage of only 0.42%, ADm, but a maximum value of constant ($K = V$).

Table 1

Junipero – Bruckenthalietum Horvat, 1936

Bioform	Fl. element	M	T	R	G	Survey no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	K	ADm
						Altitude AMSL	1832	1817	1816	1780	1775	1748	1674		
						Exposure	SV	V	V	SV	SV	V	S		
						Slope (°)	18	12	14	8	20	25	13		
						Vegetation cover (%)	90	90	90	100	100	100	100		
						Surveyed area (m ²)	400	400	400	400	800	800	400		
						Car. ass.									
mPh	Cp-A-a	2.5	1.5	4	D	<i>Juniperus communis</i> ssp. <i>alpina</i>	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	V	83.92
nPh	Carp-B	2.5	2.5	1.5	P	<i>Bruckenthalia spiculifolia</i>	+	+	.	+	+	+	+	V	0.42
						Junipero- Bruckenthalion									
Ch-nPh	Cp	0	2	1	D	<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	2	3	3	3	3	4	1	V	33.57
Ch-nPh	Cp-Bo	3	2	1	D	<i>Vaccinium vitis-idaea</i>	+	+	1	1	+	+	.	V	1.71
H	Ec	0	0	0	D	<i>Laserpitium krapfii</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.50
H	End	0	2.5	0	D	<i>Campanula serrata</i>	+	.	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.42
TH	Carp-B	3.5	2	2	P	<i>Campanula abietina</i>	+	+	II	0.14
						Junipero- Pinetalia mugii									
H	E	3.5	2.5	2.5	P	<i>Homogyne alpina</i>	.	+	+	+	+	+	.	IV	0.35
H	Eua	4	2.5	1.5	P	<i>Calamagrostis villosa</i>	+	+	.	II	0.14
H	Ec	3.5	2.5	0	P	<i>Knautia dipsacifolia</i>	.	+	I	0.07
H	Eua-A-a	3.5	2	4	P	<i>Hieracium aurantiacum</i>	+	I	0.07
						Vaccinio - Piceetea									
H	Cp	0	0	1	P	<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	1	+	+	+	+	+	.	V	1.71
MPh	E	0	0	0	D	<i>Picea abies</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.5
G	Eua	4	2.5	4	DP	<i>Veratrum album</i>	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	II	0.14
Ch-nPh	Cp-Bo	0	0	1	P	<i>Vaccinium gaultherioides</i>	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	I	0.07
H-G	Cp-Bo	3	2	2.5	D	<i>Moneses uniflora</i>	+	I	0.07
G	End	3.5	2	4	P	<i>Ranunculus carpaticus</i>	+	I	0.07
H	Eua	4	3	3	D	<i>Hypericum maculatum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	.	+	V	0.42
Ch	End	2.5	2	4	P	<i>Thymus bihoriensis</i>	+	+	.	.	+	+	+	IV	0.35
H	Eua-Cp	0	0	1.5	D	<i>Nardus stricta</i>	1	2	.	.	3	.	.	III	8.57
H	End	2.5	2	0	P	<i>Campanula rotundifolia</i> <i>ssp. polymorpha</i>	+	+	.	.	+	.	.	III	0.21

Table 1 (continuation)

Biof.	Fl. element	M	T	R	G	Survey no	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	K	ADm
H	Alp-Carp-B	2.5	3	4	P	<i>Achillea distans</i>	.	+	+	.	.	+	+	III	0.28
G	Alp-Carp-B	2	0	4	D	<i>Scorzonera rosea</i>	.	.	+	+	+	.	+	III	0.28
H	E	3	2.5	3	P	<i>Arnica montana</i>	.	.	+	+	.	.	.	II	0.14
H-Ch	Eua	2	1	3	P	<i>Antennaria dioica</i>	.	.	.	+	.	.	+	II	0.14
H	Eua	0	0	0	P	<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	.	.	P	+	+	.	.	II	0.14
H	Eua	0	2	2	P	<i>Luzula sudetica</i>	+	.	.	I	0.07
Th-TH	Ec	2.5	2.5	4	P	<i>Gentianella amarella</i>	+	I	0.07
H	Cp	3	3	3	P	<i>Gnaphalium sylvaticum</i>	+	I	0.07
H	End	3.5	2	2	DP	<i>Viola declinata</i>	+	I	0.07
Quercu – Fagetea															
H	Carp- B	3	2	2.5	P	<i>Senecio papposus</i>	.	+	I	0.07
H	Cosm	4	2.5	0	P	<i>Athyrium filix-femina</i>	+	.	I	0.07
H-Ch	Ec	3	0	4	D	<i>Lamium galeobdolon</i>	+	.	I	0.07
H	Eua	3	2.5	0	D	<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	.	.	D	.	.	.	+	I	0.07
H	End	4	2	3	D	<i>Leucanthemum waldsteinii</i>	+	I	0.07
Molinio- Arrhenatheretea															
H	Cp	3	0	3	P	<i>Luzula campestris</i>	+	.	+	+	+	+	+	V	0.42
H	Eua	4	3	0	P	<i>Molinia caerulea</i>	.	+	+	II	0.14
H	E	3	2	0	P	<i>Alchemilla vulgaris</i>	+	I	0.07
Epilobietea angustifolii															
nPh	Cp	3	3	3	DP	<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	+	+	.	.	.	+	+	III	0.28
mPh	Carp-B-Sudet	4	2	2	D	<i>Salix silesiaca</i>	.	.	.	+	.	.	.	I	0.07
Betulo- Adenostyletea															
H	Ec	4	2	4	P	<i>Gentiana asclepiadea</i>	.	.	+	I	0.07
H	Eua	3.5	3	3	P	<i>Senecio nemorensis ssp. jacquinianus</i>	+	.	I	0.07
Varia syntaxa															
H	Cp	4	1.5	0	P	<i>Epilobium anagallidifolium</i>	.	+	.	+	.	.	.	II	0.14
TH	Ec	3	0	3	D	<i>Silene italica ssp. nemoralis</i>	+	I	0.07

Place and date of surveys: 1 - 3 Cucurbăta Mare peak (03.08.2018); 4 - 6 The middle third of the slope between Cucurbăta Mare and Cucurbăta Mică peaks (03.08.2018, 05.08.2018); 7 - Biserițu Hill (04.08.2018).

Along with the two characteristic species of the association, there are present other species belonging to the basic coenotaxa of the association, namely the **Junipero-Bruckenthalion** (*Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*, *Laserpitium krapfii*, *Campanula serrata*, *Campanula abietina*), order JUNIPERO-PINETALIA MUGI (*Homogyne alpina*, *Calamagrostis villosa*, *Knautia dipsacifolia*, *Hieracium aurantiacum*), class **VACCINIO-PICEETEA** (*Deschampsia flexuosa*, *Picea abies*, *Veratrum album*, *Vaccinium uliginosum* ssp. *microphyllum*, *Moneses uniflora*, *Ranunculus carpathicus*), but also transgressive species belonging to the following classes: **NARDO-CALLUNETEA** (*Hypericum maculatum*, *Thymus bihoriensis*, *Nardus stricta*, *Campanula rotundifolia* ssp. *polymorpha*, *Achillea distans*, *Scorzonera rosea*, *Arnica montana*, *Antennaria dioica*, *Potentilla erecta*), **QUERCO-FAGETEA** (*Senecio papposus*, *Athirium filix-femina*, *Lamium galeobdolon*, *Fragaria vesca*, *Leucanthemum waldsteinii*), **MOLINIO-ARRHENATHERETEA** (*Luzula campestris*, *Molinia caerulea*, *Alchemilla vulgaris*), **EPILOBIETEA ANGUSTIFOLII** (*Rubus idaeus*, *Salix silesiaca*) and **BETULO-ADENOSTYLETEA** (*Gentiana asclepiadea*, *Senecio nemorensis* ssp. *jacquinianus*).

The bioforms (see Figure 1 below) of this association are dominated by hemicryptophytes (65.90%), followed at a great distance by phanerophytes (11.35%), cameophytes (9.09%) and geophytes, the latter having an equal share with terophytes (i.e. 6.81% each). Becoming familiar with the types of bioforms is important because it highlights the predominant orographic characteristics of the habitat exerted on plants by biotic and abiotic factors.

Fig. 1 Spectrum of the bioforms of the *Junipero-Bruckenthalietum* association
 Legend: MPh = Megaphanerophytes; mPh = Mesophanerophytes; nPh = Nanophanerophytes; Ch = Chamaephytes; ; H = Hemicriptophytes; G = Geophytes; TH = Annual terophytes; Th = Biannual therophytes.

With regard the geographical area and the current distribution of the species (see Figure 2 below), the phytocenoses of the *Junipero-Bruckenthalietum* association are dominated by the Eurasian species (25%), followed closely by the circumpolar ones (22.72%), the Central-European and endemic (13.63% each), the European and Carpatho-Balkan species (9.09% each), the Alpine-Carpatho-Balkan (4.54%) and finally by the cosmopolitan species (1.27%). Knowing the shares of phytogeographic elements provides us with information on the richness and diversity of the gene pool, the geographical interferences triggered by the migration of plant species over time.

Fig.2 Spectrum of floristic elements from the *Junipero-Bruckenthalietum* association
 Legend: Cp = Circumpolar; Eua = Eurasian; E = European; Ec = Central European;
 End Carp = Endemit-Carpathian; Carp-B = Carpathian-Balkan; Alp-Carp-B = Alpine-Carpathian-Balkan; Cosm = Cosmopolitan.

The analysis of ecoforms (see Figure 3) shows that, in terms of soil moisture, mesophilic species (40.90%) are dominant, followed by mesohygrophiles in equal share with the eurhydrous species (20.45% each), the last being xero-mesophilic species (18.17%). With regard the temperature factor, the microthermal (56.81%), followed by the eurythermal (22.72%), micro-mesothermal (13.63%) and hekistothermal (6.81%) species are dominant. Finally, considering the chemical reaction of the soil, the euriionic species are dominant (25%), followed by the weakly acid-neutrophilic (22.72%), acid-neutrophilic (20.45%) species, while the acidophilic and strongly acidophilic species are ranked last (15.90% each).

Fig.3 Diagram of ecological indices for the *Junipero-Bruckenthalietum* association

The karyotype spectrum (see Figure 4 below) shows high share of polyploid species (59.09%), as against diploid (34.09%) and diplo-polyploid (6.81%) species. The value of the diploid index is 0.57.

Fig. 4 The karyotype spectrum of the *Junipero-Bruckenthalietum* association
Legend: D = Diploids; P = Polyploids; DP = Diplo-polyploids

These phytocenoses enjoy a high conservative value, being rare communities in sparse habitats, and being included in and protected by the Emerald Network of Natural Protection Sites (Donița et al., 2005). At the same time, these shrublet and brushwood are of high scientific importance since they host endemic species e.g. *Thymus bihoriensis*, *Campanula serrata*, *Campanula rotundifolia* ssp. *polymorpha*, *Ranunculus carpaticus*, *Viola declinata*, *Leucanthemum waldsteinii*, rare species e.g. *Scorzonera rosea*, *Gentianella*, *Micropella*, species with high economic value e.g. *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*, *Picea abies*, *Rubus idaeus*, but also decorative species marking the alpine and subalpine landscape e.g. *Campanula abietina*, *Athyrium filix-femina*.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The phytocenoses of these juniper bushes (*Juniperus communis ssp. Alpina*) with spike heath (*Bruckenthalia spiculifolia*) have a high conservative value, being rare plant communities in sparse habitats
2. With regard the spectrum of bioforms, hemicytopytes are dominant (65.90%), followed at great distance by phanerophytes (11.35%), and cameophytes (9.09%).
3. Regarding the geographical area, the Eurasian species are dominant (25%), followed closely by the circumpolar ones (22.72%).
4. In terms of the ecological indices, with regard moisture the most numerous are the mesophilic species (40.90%), with regard temperature the dominant species are microthermal ones (56.81%), and with regard the chemical reaction of the soil the eurionic species are dominant (25%).
5. The analysis of chromosomal karyotypes highlights the dominance of polyploid species (59.09%), as against to diploid (34.09%) and diplo-polyploid (6.81%) ones.

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ECOLOGY OF EUROPEAN BEECH STANDS POPULATED WITH *SYRINGA JOSIKAEA* IN THE WESTERN CARPATHIANS, ROMANIA

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Abstract

The European beech stands populated with *Syringa josikaea* growing in the Western Carpathians, Remeți Forest District, Management unit V Iadului Valley, compartments 66A, 70A, 74, 78B, and 82A were studied with regard to the ecology of plant populations subordinated to the association *Pulmonario rubrae* - *Fagetum* (Soó 1964) Täufer 1987 - *syringetosum josikaeae* L. Burescu 2018. The analysis of the ecological categories of European beechstands with Hungarian/Transylvanian lilac (*Syringa josikaea*), shows us that hemicriptophytes (52.54%), and phanerophytes (28.78%) are the dominant in terms of biological forms, the spectrum of phytogeographic elements include the dominance of Eurasian species (32.20%) accompanied by European species (20.33%), followed by Central European (20.33%), Carpathian-Balkan (6.77%), and circumpolar (6.77%). *Stenochore* Alpine (3.37%), Balkan (1.69%), and endemic (1.69%) species are rare. Populations of cosmopolitan species (5.08%) entered the territory under the influence of zoo-anthropogenic factors.

With regard to the analysis of the influence of ecological factors (moisture, temperature, soil chemical reaction) the phytocenoses of the association *Pulmonario rubrae* - *Fagetum syringetosum josikaeae* have a spectrum ranging from mesophilic (55.92%) to mesohygrophilous (25.41%), from micro-mesothermic (47.45 %) to microthermal (42.36%), and from acid-neutrophilic (37.28%) to weak acid-neutrophilic (22.03%). Considering the chromosomal karyotype as the basic element, cytogenetic analysis highlights the dominance of diploids (44.06%) closely followed by polyploids (42.37%).

The European beech stands populated with *Syringa josikaea* have a high conservative value specific to an endemic habitat found only in the Apuseni Mountains.

Key words: phytocenoses, beech forests, ecological categories, genetic categories.

INTRODUCTION

The European beech stands populated with *Syringa josikaea* grow on irregular and very strong slopes (i.e. 33-45°) with a predominantly eastern orientation, made of crystalline shale rocks with rocklands, talus and scree on surface in a proportion ranging between 30 and 40%, on superficial skeletal soils belonging to dystic cambisols, acid-neutrophilic, oligobasic, moist types of soil. At the base of the slopes on a very narrow alignment bordering the riverbed of the Iadului Valley, shrublets of *Syringa josikaea* (Transylvanian or Hungarian lilac) grow. We decided to carry out ecological, phytocenological and cytogenetic surveys on these beech forests since they grow in a critical habitat of community interest called 91V0 –

Dacian beech forests (*Symphyto-Fagion* NATURA 2000) which shelter rare, threatened, endangered and at risk of extinction species including *Syringa josikaea* which is a Carpathian tertiary relic and endemic species.

There are forest communities protected within a Botanical nature reserve i.e. ROSCI 0262 included in the Sites of Community Importance (SCIs). Research works on beech stands ecology in the field has not been carried out so far, except studies on the flora and vegetation carried out by Rațiu (1965, 1967), and Rațiu et al. (1984). In previous dedicated publications and based on well-argued criteria, we subordinated the population of *Syringa josikaea* to *Pulmonario rubrae* - *Fagetum* coenosis (Soó 1964) Täuber 1987 - *syringetosum josikaeae* L. Burescu (2018), even if other authors as Sanda et al. (1999) subordinated it to the *Carici brizoides* – *Alnetum* association, while Chifu et Irimia (2014) subordinates it to the *Telekio speciosae* - *Alnetum incanae* coenosis. Ecological and genetic research on beech forests mixed with conifers has been conducted recently in the Western Carpathians by L. Burescu (2013, 2015, 2017, 2018). Research works on virgin forests in Romania with high conservation values, other than the Hungarian/Transylvanian lilac, were conducted over time by Abrudan et al. 2006, Bândiu and Doniță (1988), Bândiu et al. (2001), Biriș (2004), Biriș et al. (2005), Chifu and Ștefan (1992), Chifu et al. (2014), Doniță and Biriș (2001), Giurgiu (2001), Radu (2001), Stăncioiu et al. (2008).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study material consists of beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica*) populated with *Syringa josikaea* mixed with conifers (*Abies alba*, *Picea abies*) located in the Iadului Valley basin, Management unit V Iadului Valley, Forest district Remeți, with the following compartments: 66A Iadolina Waterfall with a surface of 8.7ha, aged 130 years old, located at altitudes ranging between 750 and 950 m; 70A Iadolina Waterfall with a surface of 3.0ha, aged 150 years, located at altitudes ranging between 710 and 800 m; compartment 74 Iadului Valley- Dealul Mare Hill with a surface of 37 ha, aged 120 years, located at altitude ranging between 640 and 1000 m; compartment 78 B Iadului Valley – Savoii with a surface of 4.0 ha, aged 70 years, located at altitudes ranging between 610-800 m; compartment 82 A Iadului Valley- Vâlcei, with a surface of 8.8 ha, aged 140 years, located at altitudes ranging between 590 and 880 m.

In the surveyed forest areas we carried out the floristic inventory, and five phytocenological survey, and the plant species we found were registered in the Association table (see Table 1 below) according to the

Braun - Blanquet scale (1964) and the constant“K” (frequency in the territory).

We analysed the European beech stands populated with *Syringa josikaea* from ecological, phytosociological, and cytogenetical standpoints based on the tables prepared and we highlighted the distribution within the studies phytocenoses of the ecological categories of live forms, phytogeographical elements (geoelements), ecoforms (ecological indices: moisture, temperature, chemical reaction of the), and genetic categories by chromosomal karyotype.

The classification by the types of live forms was made according to the Raunkiaer system (1937) improved by Braun-Blanquet (1964), and by the types of phytogeographic elements according to Meusel et Jäger (1962).

The analysis of the composition of phytocenoses of the European beech stands mixed with *Syringa josikaea* shrublets by categories of ecological indices was made after the works of the authors Csűrös et al. (1967), Beldie, Chiriță (1967), Sanda et al. (1983, 2003) who adapted the values of the ecological indices for the species from Central Europe performed on a 1 to 9 scale according to Ellenberg (1979) to the pedoclimatic conditions of Romania, using a 1 to 6 scale.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The floristic inventory of European beech stands populated with *Syringa josikaea*, the *Pulmonario rubrae-Fagetum* association (Soó 1964) Täuber 1987, *Syringetosum josikaeae* L. sub-association Burescu 2018 gathers 59 cormophyte plants (see Table 1) of which four species i.e. *Fagus sylvatica*, *Pulmonaria rubra*, *Abies alba*, and *Syringa josikaea* which are specific to the association and sub-association aforementioned, while 37 species are characteristic and differential for the basic coenotaxa of the coenosis *Symphyto-Fagenion*, *Symphyto cordati-Fagion* (eight species), *Fagetalia sylvaticae* coenosis (11 species), *Quercu-Fagetea* (18 species). A number of 13 species are transgressive from other associations namely *Vaccinio-Piceetea* (six species), *Betulo-Adenostyletea* (five species), and *Alnetea glutinosae* (two species) which proves a rich floristic biodiversity (see Table 1).

The tree layer with a general coverage of 60% is dominated by *Fagus sylvatica* accompanied by *Abies alba*, *Picea abies*, *Sorbus aucuparia*, *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Ulmus glabra*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Betula pendula*, and *Pinus sylvestris*.

Table 1

European beech stands ecology in the association *Pulmonario rubrae - Fagetum* (Soó 1964), Täuber 1987 - *syringetosum josikaeae* L. Burescu 2018

Bio	Phyto. Elem.	M	T	R	2n (karyotype)	Survey no.	1	2	3	4	5	K
		Ecological indices										
						Compartments	66A	70A	74	78B	82A	
						Altitude (m)	750	710	640	610	590	
						Exposure	E	E	E	NE	E	
						Slope (%)	45	45	33	41	40	
						Tree height (m)	28	18	25	18	18	
						Tree diameter (cm)	50	60	60	80	100	
						Tree canopy density	06	05	08	07	06	
						Grass layer coverage (%)	30	40	50	40	35	
						Surface (ha)	8.7	3.0	37	4.0	8.8	
MPh	E	3	3	0	D	<i>As. Fagus sylvatica</i>	3	2	5	4	3	V
H	Carp-B	3.5	2	2	D	<i>As. Pulmonaria ribra</i>	+	+	.	.	+	III
MPh	Ec	4	3	0	D	<i>As. Abies alba</i>	+	2	.	.	.	II
mPh	End	3.5	2.5	4	D	Subas. <i>Syringa josikaea</i>	1	1	+	+	2	V
<i>Symphyto - Fagenion, Symphyto cordati - Fagion</i>												
MPh	Ec	3.5	3	3	P	<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V
G-H	E-M	4	2	3	D	<i>Festuca drymeja</i>	.	.	+	+	+	III
H	Carp-B	3	0	0	D	<i>Hieracium transylvanicum</i>	+	.	+	.	.	II
H	Ec	3	2.5	4	D	<i>Veronica urticifolia</i>	.	.	.	+	+	II
Ch	Ec	3.5	2	0	D	<i>Saxifraga cuneifolia</i>	.	.	.	+	1	II
H	E	3.5	3.5	3.5	P	<i>Polystichum aculeatum</i>	+	1	.	.	.	II
H	Ec	4	2.5	4	D	<i>Aconitum vulparia</i> ssp. <i>lasianthum</i>	.	+	.	.	.	I
H	Carp	4	2	3	D	<i>Leucanthemum waldsteinii</i>	.	+	.	.	.	I
<i>Fagetalia sylvaticae</i>												
nPh	Eua	3	2.5	3	P	<i>Rubus hirtus</i>	1	3	.	+	+	IV
H-G	Eua	3.5	3	4	D	<i>Asarum europaeum</i>	+	+	.	+	+	IV
G-(H)	E	3.5	3	5	P	<i>Mercurialis perennis</i>	.	+	+	+	.	III

Continuation Table 1												
Bio	Phyto. Elem.	M T R Ecological indices			2n (karyotype)	Survey no.	1	2	3	4	5	K
H	Eua (C)	2	3	2	P	<i>Calamagrostis arundinacea</i>	1	+	.	.	2	III
G	Eua	3	3	0	P	<i>Galium odoratum</i>	.	.	+	+	+	III
H-Ch	Ec	3	0	4	D	<i>Lamium galeobdolon</i>	+	.	.	.	+	II
H	Eua	3.5	3	3	P	<i>Senecio germanicus</i>	+	.	.	.	+	II
H-G	Cp	4	3	3	D	<i>Oxalis acetosella</i>	+	.	+	.	.	II
Th	Eua	4	3	4	D,P	<i>Impatiens noli-tangere</i>	.	.	.	+	+	II
Th-TH	Cosm	3.5	3	3	P	<i>Geranium robertianum</i>	.	+	.	.	+	II
Th	E	2.5	3	2	P	<i>Galeopsis tetrahit</i>	.	+	.	.	.	I
<i>Quercus-Fagetea</i>												
H	Cosm	4	3	0	P	<i>Dryopteris filix-mas</i>	+	+	.	+	+	IV
mPh	Balc	3	3	3	D	<i>Corylus avellana</i>	.	+	+	1	1	IV
mPh	Eua	3	2.5	0	P	<i>Spiraea chamaedryfolia</i>	+	+	.	2	1	IV
MPh	E	3	3	3	P	<i>Carpinus betulus</i>	.	.	+	1	+	III
H	Cp	3	3	0	D,P	<i>Poa nemoralis</i>	.	+	.	1	1	III
H	Cosm	4	2.5	0	P	<i>Athyrium filix-femina</i>	+	+	.	.	+	III
MPh	Eua	4	3	3	P	<i>Ulmus glabra</i>	+	+	.	.	.	II
MPh	Eua	3	2	2	P	<i>Betula pendula</i>	+	+	.	.	.	II
mPh	Eua	3	3	4	D,P	<i>Salix capraea</i>	.	+	.	+	.	II
nPh	Ec	3	2.5	3	P	<i>Rosa pendulina</i>	.	.	.	+	+	II
H	E	3.5	3	3	D	<i>Pulmonaria officinalis</i>	.	.	.	+	+	II
H	Ec	3.5	2	3	P	<i>Doronicum austriacum</i>	+	+	.	.	.	II
H	Eua	3	3	0	D	<i>Campanula persicifolia</i>	.	+	.	+	.	II
H	E	2	3	4	CN	<i>Sedum telephium ssp. maxima</i>	.	.	.	+	+	II
G	Ec	2.5	3	3	P	<i>Galim schultesii</i>	.	+	.	+	.	II
H(G)	Eua	3	0	4	D	<i>Melica nutans</i>	.	+	.	.	.	I
H	Eua	4	3	3	D,P	<i>Eupatorium cannabinum</i>	.	+	.	.	.	I
H	Eua	4	2	0	D-P	<i>Filipendula ulmaria</i>	+	I
<i>Vaccinio -Piceetea</i>												
MPh	E	0	0	0	D	<i>Picea abies</i>	+	1	.	1	+	IV

ContinuationTable 1												
Bio	Phyto. Elem.	M T R Ecological indices			2n (karyotype)	Survey no.	1	2	3	4	5	K
MPh	E	3	2.5	2	D	<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	+	.	+	.	+	III
H	E	2.5	2.5	2	D,P	<i>Luzula luzuloides</i>	.	+	+	+	.	III
MPh	Eua	0	0	0	D	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	+	+	.	.	.	II
mPh	Alp(E)	3	2	3	D	<i>Lonicera nigra</i>	+	.	.	.	+	II
H	Ec	3.5	2.5	2	D	<i>Luzula sylvatica</i>	+	I
<i>Betula - Adenostyletea</i>												
H	Ec	4	2	4	P	<i>Gentiana asclepiadea</i>	.	+	.	.	+	II
G	Alp-Carp-B	3.5	2	3.5	P	<i>Doronicum columnae</i>	.	.	.	+	+	II
H	Eua	4	2.5	0	D	<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	.	.	.	+	+	II
H	Eua	4	2.5	0	D	<i>Heracleum sphondylium</i>	+	I
H	Ec	2.5	3	3	P	<i>Digitalis grandiflora</i>	.	+	.	.	.	I
<i>Alnetea glutinosae</i>												
H	Cp	3.5	2	3	P	<i>Dryopteris cristata</i>	.	+	.	.	+	II
Ch-nPh	Eua	4.5	3	4	P	<i>Solanum dulcamara</i>	+	I
<i>Variae syntaxa</i>												
G	Eua(M)	2	3	4	D	<i>Polygonatum odoratum</i>	.	.	+	+	+	III
MPh	E(M)	3	3	3	P	<i>Sambucus nigra</i>	.	.	.	I	+	II
H	Cp	2.5	2	3	D	<i>Solidago virgaurea</i>	.	+	.	+	.	II
H	Carp	2.5	2	0	D,P	<i>Campanula rotundifolia ssp. kladniana</i>	.	+	.	.	+	II
H	Cosm	3	0	4	P	<i>Asplenium trichomanis</i>	.	+	.	+	.	II

In one survey there were found the following: *Lonicera xylosteum* (1); *Senecio doria* (1); *Fragaria vesca* (2); *Salix elaeagnos* (5).

Location: 1. Compartment 66A - Iadolina Waterfall, 27.08.2012; 2. Compartment 70A Iadolina Waterfall, 27.08.2012; 3. Compartment 74 – Iadului Valley, Dealul Mare Hill, 27.08.2012; 4. Compartment 78B – Iadului Valley, Savoii, 27.08.2012; 5. Compartment 82A- Iadului Valley; Vâlcei sub Cruce, 27.08.2012.

The thickening of the canopy of the trees is between 0.5-0.8, the diameters of the tree trunks ranges between 50 and 100 cm and the height thereof reaches sizes between 18 and 28 m at ages between 120 and 150 years. The layer of shrubs with a general coverage of 5% consists of *Syringa josikaea*, *Corylus avellana*, *Spiraea chamaedryfolia*, *Salix capraea*, *Sambucus nigra*, *Lonicera nigra*, *Rosa pendulina*, *Salix elaeagnos*, which we included in the sub-association *syringetosum josikaeae*, holotypus hoc loco: see Table 1, survey no.5.

The grass layer cover between 30-50% and consists of 43 species of which *Pulmonaria rubra*, *Festuca drymeja*, *Asarum europaeum*, *Dryopteris filix-mas*, *Athyrium filix-femina*, *Poa nemoralis*, *Calamagrostis arundinacea*, *Galium odoratum*, *Mercurialis perennis*, *Rubus hirtus*, *Luzula luzuloides*, *Polygonatum odoratum*, *Hieracium transsylvanicum*, *Polystichum aculeatum*, *Doronicum austriacum*, *Gentiana asclepiadea*, *Senecio germanicus*, *Galium schultesii*, and others are encountered with a higher frequency (see Table 1).

Analysis of beech phytocenoses with *Syringa josikaea* within Management unit V Iadului Valley, Remeți Forest District, Bihor county, in terms of the ecodiversity of live forms shows the dominance of hemipterophytes (52.54%) accompanied by phanerophytes (28.78%), geophytes (10.16%), terophytes (5.08%), cameophytes (3.37%) these being the ecological categories best adapted to a temperate-continental climate (see Table 2 below).

Table 2

Ecodiversity of bioforms in beech with *Syringa josikaea*, Apuseni Mountains

Bioforms	Ph of which			H	G	Ch	Th	Total species
	MPh	mPh	nPh					
Species no.	10	5	2	31	6	2	3	59
Percentage %	16.94	8.47	3.37	52.54	10.16	3.37	5.08	100%

Legend: Ph = phanerophytes (woody plants); MPh = megaphanerophytes; mPh = mesophanerophytes; nPh = nanophanerophytes; H = hemipterophytes; G = geophytes; Ch = cameophytes; Th = annual terophytes.

The analysis of the phytogeographical elements (geoelements) by geographical area shows the dominance of the Eurasian species (32.20%), closely followed by the European ones (20.33), Central European (20.33%) and at a distance by the circumpolar (6.77%), Carpathian (6.77%), and cosmopolitan (6.77%) species. Stenochore species are rare and occur in small percentages such as Alpine (3.37%), Balkan (1.69%), and endemic (1.69%) (see Table3 below).

Table 3

Distribution of phytogeographic elements in European beech stands mixed with *Syringa josikaea* from the Apuseni Mountains

Phytogeographic elements	Eua	E	Ec	Cp	Carp	Cosm	Balc	Alp	End	Total sp.
Species no.	19	12	12	4	4	4	1	2	1	59
Percentage %	32.20	20.33	20.33	6.77	6.77	6.77	1.69	3.37	1.69	100%

Legend: Eua = Eurasian; E = European; Ec = Central European; Cp = circumpolar, Carp = Carpathian, Cosm = cosmopolitan; Balc = Balkan; Alp = alpine; End = endemic.

The analysis of ecological indices (ecological factors) in terms of moisture for the European beech stands phytocenoses mixed with *Syringa josikaea* highlights the preponderance of mesophilic species (55.92%) followed by mesohygrophilous (25.41%) and xeromesophilic (15.24%) ones. With regard to temperature, most species are moderately thermophilic (47.45%) and microthermal (42.36%).

The chemical reaction of the soil stimulates the development of acid-neutrophilic (37.28%), euriionic (27.11%), and weakly acid-neutrophilic (22.03%) species and to a lesser extent the acidophilic ones (11.86%).

Table 4

Ecological indices of phytocenoses of the association *Pulmonario rubrae* - *Fagetum*, sub-association *syringetosum josikaeae*, Apuseni Mountains.

Ecological Indic.	Values types	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5	0	Total sp.
M	Species no.	3	6	19	14	14	1	-	2	59
	Percentage %	5.08	10.16	32.20	23.72	23.72	1.69	-	3.37	100
T	Species no.	13	12	27	1	-	-	-	6	59
	Percentage %	22.03	20.33	45.76	1.69	-	-	-	10.16	100
R	Species no.	7		22		13		1	16	59
	Percentage %	11.86		37.28		22.03		1.69	27.11	100

Legend: M = moisture; T = temperature; R = chemical reaction of the soil; H (2-2.5) = xeromesophilic species; H (3-3.5) = mesophilic species; H (4-4.5) = mesohygrophilic species; H (5) = hygrophilic species; H (0) = euryhelic species; T (2-2.5) = microthermal species; T (3-3.5) = mesothermal species; T (0) = eurythermal species; R (2) = acidophilic species; R (3) = acid-neutrophilic species; R (4) = weak acid-neutrophilic species; R (5) = neutro-basophilic species; R (0) = euriionic species.

The distribution of genetic categories by chromosomal karyotype (see Table 5) in the phytocenoses of the European beech stands with *Syringa josikaea* indicates the preponderance of diploid species (44.06%) which are the repository of the gene pool necessary for evolution, closely followed by polyploid species (42.37%) containing genes for land colonization and adaptation to extreme living conditions in a habitat with steep slopes, with rocklands, talus and scree subjected to strong winds, heavy snow and critical temperatures.

Table 5

Genetic ecostructure of European beech stands with *Syringa josikaea* from the Apuseni Mountains, Romania.

Genetic categories	Diploids (D)	Poliploids (P)	Diplo-Poliploids (DP)	Unknown karyotype (CN)	Total species
Species no.	26	25	7	1	59
Percentage %	44.06	42.37	11.86	1.69	100

Relevance

European beech stands with *Syringa josikaea* (Hungarian/Transylvanian lilac) are rare in Romania and are included in a natural forest ecosystem of community interest for they contain endangered species, which is why they must be protected in special protected areas, Doniță et al. (2005), Gafta, Mountford coord. et al. (2008), banning any felling of trees that could impact the already so fragile stability of these relict, endangered forest ecosystems.

Only special conservation works will be carried out in these forests, to ensure the protection and permanence of rare, endangered, endemic, relict species.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Through our study, we found 59 cormophyte species, of which a number of six species are rare, relict, and endemic, and one an endangered one.
2. European beech stands with *Syringa josikaea* are dominated by hemicryptophytes (52.54%), and phanerophytes (28.78%) which is a manifestation of the belonging of the surveyed territory to the temperate-continental climate of the Apuseni Mountains.
3. Regarding the geographical area, most species are Eurasian (32.20%) followed closely by European (20.33), Central European (20.33%) and in small percentages by Carpathian (6.77%), and circumpolar (6.77%) species. Stenochore species are few and occur in insignificant percentages i.e. Alpine (3.37%), endemic (1.69%), and Balkan (1.69%) species.

4. As a reaction to the action of edaphoclimatic factors, European Beech stands with *Syringa josikae* manifest a mesophilic (55.92%), mesothermal (47.45%), and acid-neutrophilic (37.38%) nature.
5. Cytogenetic analysis of phytocenosis plants highlights the share of diploid species (44.06%) that store the gene pool necessary for evolution, polyploid ones (42.37%) containing genes that favour adaptation to pedo-climatic conditions of the habitat and colonization of geographical space.
6. Based on the analysis of the floristic composition of the beech stands phytocenosis and taking into account the characteristic and differential species we separated a new sub-association gathering the *Syringa josikae* shrublets in *-syringetosum josikaeae*, which we subordinated to the basic *Pulmonario rubrae – Fagetum* association.
7. Five tables enclosing scientifically processed statistic data support the paper, which is documented with data from a bibliography comprising 29 scientific titles.

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THE EFFECTS OF THE EMERGENCY ORDINANCE NO. 119/2021 IN TERMS OF THE FIGHT AGAINST FORESTRY CRIME

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Abstract

Even if, from an overall perspective, the amendments brought to forestry crimes by Law no. 197/2020 were necessary and useful, their non-correlation with the special legislation on forestry contraventions generated certain unpleasant particular situations in which the same act was susceptible to be classified as both a crime and a misdemeanor.

Compared to the principles governing criminal law (criminal law more favorable and in dubio pro reo) starting with the date of entry into force of Law no. 197/2020 respectively 11.09.2020 there was a real risk that, on certain crimes, their perpetrators benefit of a favorable legal regime.

Emergency Ordinance no. 119/2021 has the merit to correlate the Law no. 46/2008 on the Forestry Code with the Law no. 171/2010 on the establishment and sanctioning of forestry contraventions and, as a consequence, to remove the possibility for forest criminals to benefit from a more favorable sanctioning regime.

Key words: special legislation, forestry code, forestry contraventions

INTRODUCTION

Even if, from an overall perspective, the amendments brought to forestry crimes by Law no. 197/2020 were necessary and useful, their non-correlation with the special legislation on forestry contraventions generated certain unpleasant particular situations in which the same act was susceptible to be classified as both a crime and a contravention.

Reported to the principles that govern criminal law (criminal law more favorable and in dubio pro reo) starting with the date of entry into force of Law no. 197/2020 respectively 11.09.2020 there was a real risk that, on certain crimes, their perpetrators to benefit of a favorable legal regime.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Materials used in drafting this work are composed of web sites, legislation. The methods used are legal, namely the formal method, the historical method, the comparative method, the logical and sociological method, the analytical method. The use of these methods has the role of performing a systematic analysis of the information from the studied sources in order to elaborate the points of view and the conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Emergency Ordinance no. 119/2021 has the merit to correlate the Law no. 46/2008 on the Forestry Code with the Law no. 171/2010 on the establishment and sanctioning of forestry contraventions and, as a consequence, to remove the possibility for forestry offenders to benefit from a more favorable sanctioning regime.

Against the background of the constant decrease of the areas covered with forest vegetation and of the alarming increase of the criminal phenomenon in the forestry field, the fight against the crimes in this sector has become a constant preoccupation of the authorities.

In this context, the forestry legislation has undergone, in a relatively short period of time, a series of changes meant, on the one hand, to transpose the community legislation and, on the other hand, to stop the illicit timber business. Several institutions were involved with a role in ascertaining forestry contraventions and crimes and with bringing them before the investigation / criminal prosecution bodies.

One of the most important and useful changes was the one regarding the elimination of the minimum threshold value, the achievement of which was conditioned by the existence of forestry crimes. Since the entry into force of the old Forestry Code, in their quasi-unanimity the existence of forestry crimes has been conditioned by a value of the lesion caused of at least 5 times higher than the average price of one cubic meter of wood per foot at the date of committing the act or as the case may be at the date of its finding.

Below the value mentioned above, the deed was not classified as a crime but only as a simple contravention, with all the legal consequences that flowed from it. The experience of the 30 years since the entry into force of the old Forestry Code has proved that taking advantage of the existence of the minimum value of the lesion, there were enough people who constantly committed forest crimes with a lesion, counted for each act in part, under the one required by law so that the deed can be classified as a crime.

In the context mentioned above, as it results from the explanatory memorandum¹ that accompanied the draft law², modifications were considered in order to facilitate the possibilities of classifying an act as a forestry crime.

¹ http://www.cdep.ro/pls/proiecte/upl_pck2015.proiect?idp=18415

² Draft Law for the amendment and completion of Law no. 46/2008 - Forestry Code (PL-x no. 356/2020 at the Chamber of Deputies)

By Law no. 197/2020³, the necessary amendments were made, in the sense that both in the case of the crime of illegal cutting of trees and in the case of theft of trees, the condition of the existence of a prejudice of a certain minimum value was removed.

Specifically, after the entry into force⁴ of the amendments introduced by Law no. 197/2020, the Forestry Code has the following content regarding the two crimes:

Unlawful cutting of trees⁵ from the national forest fund, regardless of the form of ownership, constitutes a forestry crime and is punished as follows:

- a) with imprisonment from 6 months to one year or with a blind, **if the value of the lesion caused is up to 5 times the average price of one cubic meter of wood per foot** at the date of finding the deed;
- b) with imprisonment from one to 3 years, if the value of the lesion caused is between the limit provided in let. a) and at most 20 times higher than the average price of one cubic meter of wood per foot at the date of finding the deed;
- c) with imprisonment from 2 to 7 years, if the value of the lesion caused is at least 20 times higher than the average price of one cubic meter of wood per foot at the date of finding the deed

Theft of trees⁶ felled or broken by natural phenomena or of trees that have been cut down or uprooted, from forests, forest protection curtains, from degraded lands that have been ameliorated by afforestation works and from forest vegetation outside the national forest fund, as well as of any other specific products of the national forest fund constitutes a crime and is punished as follows:

- a) with imprisonment from 6 months to one year or with an fine, if the value of the lesion caused is up to 5 times the average price of one cubic meter of wood per foot at the date of finding the deed;
- b) b) with imprisonment from one to 3 years, if the value of the lesion caused is between the limit provided in let. a) and at most 20 times higher than the average price of one cubic meter of wood per foot at the date of finding the deed;

³ Law 197/2020 for the amendment and completion of Law no. 46/2008 - Forestry Code, Official Gazette 823 of 2020.09.08

⁴ 11 September 2020

⁵ Article 107 para. (11) Forestry Code of 2008 (Law no. 46/2008) - Republishing, Official Gazette 611 of 2015.08.12

⁶ Article 109 para. (11) Forestry Code of 2008 (Law no. 46/2008) - Republishing, Official Gazette 611 of 2015.08.12

- c) with imprisonment from 2 to 7 years, if the value of the lesion caused is at least 20 times higher than the average price of one cubic meter of wood per foot at the date of finding the deed

Starting with that moment, at least theoretically any unlawful cutting or theft of trees should have been a crime, without the value of the lesion to be relevant in terms of legal classification of the deed (eventually in terms of judicial individualization of punishment). This was, moreover, the intention of the legislator and the main motivation of the amendments introduced by Law no. 197/2020.

Even if, from an overall perspective, the amendments brought to forestry crimes by Law no. 197/2020 were necessary and useful, their non-correlation with the special legislation on forestry contraventions generated certain unpleasant particular situations in which the same act was susceptible to be classified as both a crime and a contravention.

Reported to the principles that govern criminal law (criminal law more favorable and in dubio pro reo) starting with the date of entry into force of Law no. 197/2020 respectively 11.09.2020 there was a real risk that, on certain crimes, their perpetrators to benefit of a favorable legal regime. Specifically, modifying the content of the objective side of forestry crimes and leaving unchanged Law no. 171/2020⁷ on establishing and sanctioning forestry contraventions, the legislator generated a complicated situation in the sense that, on a lesion of *up to 5 times the average price of one cubic meter* the act of unlawful cutting or theft of trees was, at the same time, both the objective side of a crime and that of a contravention.

Specifically, on the lesion interval of up to 5 times the average price of one cubic meter of wood per foot, the text of the two infractions was identical to that of the following two contraventions:

- a) *cutting*⁸, breaking or uprooting *trees*, without right, as well as destroying or damaging trees, seedlings, Christmas trees or shoots from *the national forest fund* or cutting, breaking or uprooting trees, without right, as well as destruction or damage of trees on lands with forest vegetation outside the national forest fund, *if the value of the lesion, established according to the law, is up to 5 times the average price of one cubic meter of wood per foot*;
- b) *b) theft*⁹ or misappropriation *of trees cut with or without right*, of seedlings, Christmas trees or shoots from *the national forest fund or of Christmas trees* from specialized crops or theft or appropriation of trees cut with or without right from lands with

⁷ Official Gazette 513 din 2010.07.23

⁸ Law no. 171/2010, art. 8 para.1 letter a)

⁹ Law no. 171/2010, art. 8 para.1 letter b)

vegetation outside the national forest fund, if the value of the damage, established according to the law, *is up to 5 times the average price of one cubic meter of wood per foot*

Emergency Ordinance no. 119/2021 has the merit to correlate the Law no. 46/2008 on the Forestry Code with the Law no. 171/2010 on the establishment and sanctioning of forestry contraventions and, as a consequence, to remove the possibility for forestry offenders to benefit from a more favorable sanctioning regime.

Observing the legislative non-correlation, the legislator proceeded to the amendment of Law no. 171/2010, in the sense of amending the legal text of the two contraventions mentioned above, as follows:

- a) cutting, breaking or uprooting of trees, without right, as well as the destruction or damage of trees from the forest vegetation *outside the national forest fund*.
- b) b) theft of *seedlings or shoots* that have been cut or uprooted, from forests, forest protection curtains, from degraded lands that have been ameliorated by afforestation works, if the value of the lesion caused is up to 5 times the average price of a cubic meter of wood on the foot at the date of committing the deed.

CONCLUSIONS

As can be noticed, after the amendments introduced by **Emergency Ordinance 119/2021**¹⁰, in the case of unlawful cutting, the deed constitutes a contravention only if it has as object trees from the forest vegetation outside the national forest fund. Regarding the theft of trees, after the appearance of the Emergency Ordinance 119/2021, the deed will no longer be considered a contravention, any misappropriation without right, regardless of value, will be circumscribed to the objective side of the forest theft crime.

Emergency Ordinance no. 119/2021 has the merit to correlate the Law no. 46/2008 on the Forestry Code with the Law no. 171/2010 on the establishment and sanctioning of forestry contraventions and, as a consequence, to remove the possibility for forestry offenders to benefit from a more favorable sanctioning regime.

The discussion remains open regarding the facts, of the nature of those described above, which were committed in the period elapsed since the entry into force of Law no. 197/2020, ie 11 September 2020, until the appearance

¹⁰ Emergency Ordinance 119/2021 for the amendment and completion of Law no. 171/2010 regarding the establishment and sanctioning of forestry contraventions, Official Gazette 952 from 2021.10.05

of the amendments introduced by GEO no. 119/2021 respectively 5 October 2021.

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NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE INDUCTION HEAT TREATMENT OF THE CONICAL DRILL

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Abstract

This paper proposes an analysis of the induction hardening method of the conical drill. In the case of the conical drill the heating analysis needs solution in the thermal diffusion problems coupled with eddy currents case.

Keywords: Numerical simulation, Electromagnetic field, Electromagnetic field coupled with thermal, conical drill.

INTRODUCTION

The conical drill is used for digging seedlings

The drills used to dig holes for planting seedlings must meet very different conditions, which condition their construction:

The cutting area of the drill must have optimal linear and angular parameters, depending on the terrain conditions in which it is worked.

The drill must have such a construction that the dislocated soil should be evacuated freely, and should it remain in the pit, it should not prevent its advance and withdrawal.

The construction of the drill must ensure easy sharpening, or if possible self-sharpening of cutting edges is possible

During the work, the drills should not cause the walls of the excavated pits to be pressed, nor the mixing of the detached layers of earth, when this is required

The conical drill must have a homogeneous structure to respond to imposed requirements.

We must verify that the B-H relation is dependent on temperature, passing from iron-magnetic environment form to air. In this case, we observe that the eddy's current problems and thermal diffusion are strongly coupled in the Curie point zone.

As we know the B-H relation is linear and the magnetic permeability is adjusting according to the highest effective value of the magnetic induction (Leuca, Arion, Cheregi, Horge, 2007).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the simulation we use FLUX 2D software package.

The magnetic field problem can be solved by reduced to the determination of a potential vector with a single component, which verifies an similar equation of the scalar potential.

The coupled of thermal diffusion problems with eddy currents is the main problem of every hardening method.

For a better analysis of the results we need to find the result of eddy currents problem (power density) and temperature (thermal capacity and thermal conductivity) (Leuca, Cranganu-Cretu, Arion, Tarcau, 2002)

In the analysis of this case we must solve the electromagnetic problem with a parallel – plane structure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The numerical simulation with FLUX 2D software (FLUX 2D – tutorial) allows to determining accurately the relationship between the used frequencies, the desired treatment depth and also the power density.

The desired treatment depth is very important to make a complete map of the hardening process.

Fig. 1. The conical drill

Fig. 2. The temperature in point A

Fig. 3. The temperature in point B

Fig. 4. The temperature dependence of the equivalent heat transfer coefficient in this case

CONCLUSIONS

The numeric simulation of the hardening process is a complex problem because the non-linear problems of eddy currents is provide from non-linear relation of **B-H**.

The non-linear of thermal problem provide from dependence with temperature of thermal parameters (T. Leuca, M. Arion, G. Cheregi, I. Horge, 2007).

The thermal transfer to the surface of the workpiece is characterized by a convection coefficient with the value $\alpha = 20 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{°C}$ and by a radiation coefficient (characteristic of the thermal transfer by radiation) $\varepsilon = 0,75$ by which the dependence of the thermal transfer coefficient α_e it's a function of temperature

After the simulation process we observe that the coupled of two problems result from strong dependence of relation **B-H** with temperature.

Through proposed heat treatment we get a homogenous structure.

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*FLUX 2D – tutorial.

REALIZATION OF A GEOGRAPHICAL INFORMATIC SYSTEM FOR INACCESSIBLE FOREST FUND

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Abstract

Modern geomatic technologies, which are currently used, offer the possibility for various users to propose and adopt efficient technical solutions in the fields of activity related to the activities carried out.

The various activities within the forestry sector involve the use of cartographic products, such as landscaping maps (forestry), in analog and / or digital format, as appropriate, depending on the available logistics.

The use of specialized computer programs for the exploitation of cartographic products related to the forestry sector, in analog and / or digital format, contributes considerably to the adoption of technical solutions related to current activities: regeneration and management of stands, recovery of forest products, monitoring the health of trees, forest fund guarding, forest management certification, etc.

The development and use of a computer system and the database of accessible stands, using the program MapSys 10.0, offers the possibility to specialists in the forestry sector, to opt for the variety that ensures a superior technical and economic efficiency.

Key words: geomatic technologies, geographic information system, accessible stands, database, digital forest map, forest thematic map.

INTRODUCTION

The Geographic Information System (GIS) is a technical and organizational set of people, equipment, rules, regulations, methods and working algorithms, with the main objectives of collecting, verifying, validating, storing, displaying and processing geographic data (Chrisman, Nicholas, 1998).

GIS is the computer system that connects a database that operates with geometric-spatial elements, with another database that operates with attributes of information, which is contained in the first database (Clarke, Keith, 1997).

The first database refers to graphical representations of the terrain, coordinate systems, the position of the characteristic points in relation to different reference systems, etc.

The second database is an alphanumeric, textual database, which contains tables in which the attributes of the graphic elements registered in the first database are stored.

The main objectives of GIS are the analysis and study of these data, of the relationships that are established between them, in order to obtain new information to substantiate the decision-making process.

Geographic information systems are represented by a set of programs, which process the spatial information contained in the maps, under spatial (technical, positioning), economic, legal aspects (Chezan et. al. 2006).

The valorization of wood products represents for a series of forestry units the predominant (basic) activity, as a result for the forest management of the objectives related to this activity, it is necessary to meet a series of conditions regarding the infrastructure (Iovan, 2020) - respectively the accessibility of the forest stands (Irimie, 2021).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The case study was carried out within the Production Unit (P.U.) III Galbena, Sudrigiu Forest District (F.D.), Bihor Forest Administration (F.A.), in the stands 44A, 44B, 44C, 45A, 45B, 46A, 46B, 47A, 47B, 47C, 47D, 48A, 48B, 48C, 49A, with a total area of 174.48 ha.

Photo.1 - Location of the case study (extract from the forest map at a scale of 1: 20000, of the Production Unit III Galbena, Sudrigiu F.D., Bihor F.A.

The stands in the analyzed and studied plots have a reduced accessibility, as a result, the extraction (capitalization) of the possibility of main products (Irimie, 2021), established by the forest management in

force, cannot be realized at present, due to the lack of an adequate infrastructure - forest roads (Iovan, 2020).

In order to carry out the case study, an appropriate bibliographic documentation was made, using in this context specialized treatises and elaborations (forest management and forest map of the production unit elaborated in 2014), scientific articles and specialized software.

In the field, observations were made on the itinerary and in the stationary one, respectively, and the recording on digital support of the images from the field (Crainic, et. al., 2018).

The main elements used to create the computer system and the database are represented by the forest management and forest map related to the Production Unit III Galbena, at a scale of 1: 20000 (which were developed in 2014) and the MapSys 10.0 program.

In order to be able to use the forest map properly, it was georeferenced (associating a system of relative coordinates) with the MapSys 10.0 program, using the Helmert transformation method - with common points (Marton, 2007).

The transformation method used involves the use of common points (in the two coordinate systems - the map and the spreadsheet, respectively), which have known coordinates (Crainic, 2021, Crainic et. al. 2018, Sabău, 2010, Sabău, Crainic, 2006).

The sequence of work steps (technological flow) corresponding to the creation of the database is as follows:

- scanning the map;
- obtaining the raster;
- vectorization of the raster;
- obtaining the related vectors and polygons;
- completion of topology;
- collection of attributes;
- creating thematic layers;
- creating the database;

The block diagram for obtaining vectors, polygons, thematic maps and the database using the corresponding raster is shown in Figure 1.

To build the geographic information system with MapSys 10.0, several steps are required, which are as follows:

- opening the work schedule;
- setting the working parameters;
- saving the initial elements in a new work;
- import of the raster (landscaping map);
- implementation of the coordinates of the known points for the four transformation points;

Fig.1 - Block diagram of obtaining GIS products by using raster data - respectively the layout map of the Production Unit III Galbena, Sudrigiu F. D., Bihor F. A.
 -initialization of the raster orientation on four common points of known coordinates;
 -realization of orientation (raster georeferencing);

- verification of the oriented raster;
- setting the thematic layers (layers);
- realizing the vectorization of the desired raster;
- obtaining the vector;
- completion of topology;
- solving non-closing errors;
- referring the topology;
- implementation of identifiers from layer 2;
- referring the topology;
- collection of attributes;
- initializing the construction of the database;
- adaptation of the database to the collected attributes;
- implementing attributes in the database;
- verifying the elements in the database;
- making thematic maps;
- verification of thematic maps;

Photo. 2 - Georeferencing the raster on four common points, with the program MapSys 10.0

-archiving thematic maps using the pdf extension.

The functions in the Raster menu of the MAPSYS 10.0 program allow the efficient use of scanned maps and plans or orthophoto images, for

the purpose of vectorizing them or for viewing them in combination with existing graphic or topological elements (Marton H., 2007).

In order to associate a coordinate system to the raster related to the landscaping map used, its georeferencing was performed, by Helmert transformation, using for this purpose four common coordinate points in the two coordinate systems - table 1.

Table 1

The inventory of the coordinates of the common points used for the georeferencing of the arrangement map at a scale of 1:20 000, related to the Production Unit III Galbena, Sudrigiu F.D, Bihor F.A.

Nr. crt.	X(m)	Y(m)	Z(m)	Observații
1	10 000,000	10 000,000	855,000	puncte comune
2	22 200,000	10 000,000	795,000	puncte comune
3	22 200,000	23 100,000	922,000	puncte comune
4	10 000,000	23 100,000	1022,000	puncte comune

The coordinates of the common points used for georeferencing were determined graphically, from the landscaping map at a scale of 1:20 000, adopting for this purpose a local system of rectangular coordinates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The realization of the geographical information system related to the forest fodder from the presented location, supposes the opening of a new work in the MAPSYS 10.0 program and the completion of the previously presented stages, within the methods and the way of work, which were proposed - figure 1.

As a result, the vector related to the analyzed and studied plots was obtained, using for this purpose the raster (scanned landscaping map, in digital format) relatively oriented (georeferenced) - photo. 3.

It is found that there is a correlation between the surface of the plots in the plot description and the one calculated analytically from the vector obtained, for the forest fund analyzed and studied.

In the present case study, the main attributes are represented by the number of the plot (planning unit) and their accessibility, aspects that are analyzed and studied.

The plots that are not properly accessed will be marked separately on the generated thematic map, in order to be able to analyze and study carefully, with an optimal efficiency, in order to establish appropriate technical solutions.

The establishment of the location related to the transport installations from the studied inaccessible exploitable stands is made on the obtained vector, and the length of the routes will be determined analytically,

adding the lengths of the alignments materialized by the characteristic points of detail.

Photo. 3 - The vector related to the analyzed and studied plots

Obtaining optimal solutions involves the analysis of several possible scenarios (variants), analyzing (combining) in this sense the field data with the planimetric elements identified on the raster used and implicitly on the vector generated by the vectorization process.

Photo. 4 - The vector equipped with the corresponding attributes, in the MAPSYS 10.0 program

aza de date Tabel Interogare Extras

DB	NR	IDLN	IDTX	NRCAD	SUPRAFATA	PERIMETRUL	Z	Parcela	Accesibilitatea
	31	108	98	Suprafata n...	11222.4514	457.49	0.000	NP 2	Suprafata neproduct
	9	7	71	Arboret ina...	318754.7385	2959.26	0.000	49 A	Arboret inaccesibil
	15	24	102	Arboret ina...	78866.7035	1935.12	0.000	47 A	Arboret inaccesibil
	22	42	75	Arboret ina...	144946.9002	2470.89	0.000	48 A	Arboret inaccesibil
	23	46	101	Arboret ina...	12141.3354	566.47	0.000	48 C	Arboret inaccesibil
	25	63	90	Arboret ina...	37962.6561	1250.92	0.000	48 B	Arboret inaccesibil
	27	73	69	Arboret ina...	255923.9019	3875.02	0.000	43 B	Arboret inaccesibil
	30	106	100	Arboret ina...	3170.4504	240.92	0.000	47 D	Arboret inaccesibil
	6	5	95	Arboret acc...	99552.2931	1697.67	0.000	46 B	Arboret accesibil
	7	5	94	Arboret acc...	98750.5171	1522.62	0.000	45 B	Arboret accesibil
	21	40	87	Arboret acc...	44808.9624	1063.25	0.000	58 B	Arboret accesibil
	24	48	84	Arboret acc...	258664.0565	2701.78	0.000	58 A	Arboret accesibil
	26	65	89	Arboret acc...	16087.0114	774.98	0.000	57 B	Arboret accesibil
	32	116	88	Arboret acc...	8812.2231	494.67	0.000	56 B	Arboret accesibil
	33	117	82	Arboret acc...	253758.6771	3070.56	0.000	55 B	Arboret accesibil
	11	11	6	7	56508.1413	985.31	0.000	NP 1	Suprafata neproduct
	20	39	57	59 B	243667.7751	2051.97	0.000	59 B	Arboret accesibil
	35	157	56	59 A	175928.8223	2550.84	0.000	59 A	Arboret accesibil
	37	179	60	56 A	174428.7198	1967.98	0.000	56 A	Arboret accesibil
	36	169	33	55 A	226547.3591	2321.29	0.000	55 A	Arboret accesibil
	8	7	38	51	95313.2608	1378.07	0.000	51	Arboret accesibil
	10	11	37	50 B	273408.6276	2875.72	0.000	50 B	Arboret accesibil
	16	-31	67	50	94525.2098	1383.04	0.000	44 B	Arboret inaccesibil
	28	99	54	47 C	7940.2962	367.09	0.000	47 C	Arboret inaccesibil
	19	-38	53	47 B	221098.6873	2610.65	0.000	47 B	Arboret inaccesibil
	14	18	50	46 A	383789.4704	2965.10	0.000	46 A	Arboret inaccesibil
	4	3	45	44 D	372786.0462	3470.50	0.000	44 D	Arboret inaccesibil
	2	1	47	44 C	10065.0728	488.31	0.000	44 C	Arboret inaccesibil
	3	3	46	44 A	58671.3151	1290.29	0.000	44 A	Arboret inaccesibil
	18	32	42	43 A	71486.5410	1786.76	0.000	43 A	Arboret inaccesibil
	5	4	28	29	139174.1739	2657.10	0.000	45 A	Arboret inaccesibil
	13	16	9	10	311836.6151	3363.08	0.000	57 A	Arboret accesibil
	34	120	3	4	73637.9008	1378.35	0.000	50 A	Arboret accesibil
	12	12	2	3	442357.9657	2772.78	0.000	52	Arboret accesibil

Photo. 5 - The database created in the MapSys 10.0 program, for the analyzed plots

The attributes collected from the georeferenced site, for the analyzed and studied plots, were automatically implemented in the textual database - photo. 5, which can be interrogated as needed.

Photo. 5 - Thematic map of the accessibility of the stands, made in the MAPSYS 10.0 program, for the analyzed plots

Also, in the MapSys program, the thematic map of the accessibility of the stands in the analyzed and studied plots was generated, using for this purpose the thematic layers Polygon, Plots and Accessibility, which were activated simultaneously.

The thematic map - photo 5, thus obtained can be used in digital format at the desired scale, can be archived or as the case may be and / or can be printed in an appropriate graphic format, depending on the scale adopted.

The content elements related to the thematic map of the accessibility of the studied stands can be established, respectively implemented according to the need, taking into account the beneficiary's requests.

Photo. 6 - Thematic map of the accessibility of the stands, made in the MAPSYS 10.0 program, for the analyzed plots, at a scale of 1: 25000, set for printing

The surface of the plots that vectorized was determined by the analytical method, and is found in the tabular records in the textual database, and can be used in digital and/or analog format - photo 6, as appropriate, depending on the logistics used.

The small differences between the surface in the plot description and the one determined by the analytical method, following the vectorization process, are due to the working technology that was used.

Photo 5 shows the thematic map of the accessibility of the stands within the Production Unit III Galbena, Sudrigiu Forest District, Bihor Forestry Administration, where the case study was carried out. From the analysis of the thematic map it can be observed the location of the accessible stands, of the inaccessible ones and respectively of the non-productive land surfaces.

CONCLUSIONS

The implementation of geomatic technologies in the various positioning and design activities in the forestry sector, offers the guarantee of efficient, optimal technical solutions, in order to sustainably capitalize on forest resources.

The development of information systems related to the activities within the forestry sector offers the possibility for the field and office staff to adopt efficient solutions, in order to solve the various problems that involve the positioning of the details on the areas with forest vegetation.

The use of digital technologies for obtaining and / or exploiting cartographic products (in analog or digital format) facilitates the achievement of performances in establishing technical solutions related to the forest management and accessibility of the forest fund.

The use of raster data and, implicitly, vector data in geomatic technologies, ensures a high accuracy of the spatial positioning of the details in the forestry sector and the obtaining of multipurpose cartographic products.

The need to implement modern geomatic technologies for positioning and making high-accuracy digital mapping products in current activities within state and/or private forestry units is imperative, given the current trend of global digitization of all productive activities.

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DEVELOPMENT OF CALCULATION PROGRAMS AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF DISPLACEMENTS IN WOODEN BEAMS USING THE DIRECT INTEGRATION METHOD AND THE MOHR METHOD

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Abstract

This paper presents the numerical calculation programs designed by the author to determine the displacements of the sections of a wooden bar using the direct integration method and the conjugate bar method (Mohr). At the base of the realized programs was the Matlab numerical calculation software. For a good example of the two methods approached, the model considered for performing the calculations was the console bar.

Key words: numerical integration, Mohr method, beam, deflections.

INTRODUCTION

In order to achieve a physical model of the bar body considered, the author considered as valid some simplifying hypotheses, among which we mention:

- the isotropy of the material was considered both in the longitudinal plane parallel to the body fibers, and in the transversal plane, perpendicular to the fibers (Catariu, Kopenetz, 2001, Ciofoaia, Curtu, 1986);
- the hypothesis of small displacements was considered valid.

The section of the considered body is rectangular and constant along its entire length, fact for which the stiffness at bending of the body is constant. The methods that have been applied by the author are the direct integration method and the Mohr method.

This paper by the author consists in the realization and validation of analytical calculation methods (direct integration method and Mohr's method), using numerical analysis by developing programs in Matlab. The initial, geometric and physical-mechanical data of the material are the following:

- $I = (b_0 \cdot h^3) / 12$ [mm⁴]
- $E = 0.1 \cdot 10^5$ [N/mm²]
- $L = 1000$ [mm];
- $F = 100$ [KN]
- $b_0 = 200$ [mm], the width of the beam
- $h = 300$ [mm], height beam

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The programs made by the author are based on the known theoretical mathematical elements of the methods used. (Fetea, 2010), (Goia, 2000), (Ille, 1981). The designed program is presented below following (Gheorghiu, Hadar, 1998), (Muntenu Gh, Metoda Elementelor Finite 1998):.

```
% Numerical analysis of bars using the method of direct integration and al
conjugate beams %

% E, Young modulus [N/mm^2];
% I, the moment of axial inertia of the plane section [mm^4]
% L, length of bar [m];
% F, external force [N];
% h, section height [mm]
% b0, maximum width of the bar [mm];
% bX, bar width in section X [mm];
% VA, reaction force in the clamped section A [N];
% MA, bending moment from clamped section A [Nmm];
F=10^5
L=1000
b0=200
h=300
E=.1*10^5
I=(b0*h^3)/12
% Determining the reaction vertical force and the clamped moment;
VA=F
MA=F*L
% Expression of the bending moment on the interval [0,1000][mm]
syms x F MA
M(x)=-MA+VA*x
% Determining the expression for rotating the section by first integrating the
differential equation
syms v(x)
ode = diff(v,x) == (MA-VA*x)
vsol1(x) = dsolve(ode)
% Determining the expression of the section displacement by the second
integration of the differential equation
syms v(x) MA VA
Dv = diff(v);
ode = diff(v,x,2) == (MA-VA*x)
cond1 = v(0) == 0
```

```

cond2 = Dv(0) == 0
conds = [cond1 cond2]
vSol2(x)=dsolve(ode)
for x=0
    C1 = - MA*x + (VA*x^2)/2
    C1
end
for x=0
    for C1=0
        C2=(VA*x^3)/6 - (MA*x^2)/2 - C1*x
        C2
    end
end
end
% The general expression of displacements axis (Missir-Vlad, Ioana, 2002):
x=0:100:1000

VA=F
F=100000
MA=F*L
d=((F*x.^3)/6 - (MA*x.^2)/2)/(E*I)
plot(x,d)
x=0:100:1000
VA=F
F=100000
MA=F*L
rot = (x.*MA - (VA*x.^2)/2)/(E*I)
plot (x,rot)

```

Applying the direct integration method and by running the programs developed by the author using the Matlab numerical program, the following data were determined regarding the displacements of the points in the sections considered for $x = 0: 100: 1000$ and the rotations of the wooden beam sections:

Fig.1 Displacement diagram by Integration method

Table 1

Displacements values along the beam using Integration method

x	0	100	200	300	400	500	600	700	800	900	1000
d	0	0.1074	-0.414	-0.900	-1.540	-2.314	-3.200	-4.174	-5.214	-6.300	-7.4074

Fig.2 Rotations diagram by integration method

Table 2

Rotations values along the beam using Integration method

x	0	100	200	300	400	500	600	700	800	900	1000
rot	0	0.0021	0.0040	0.0057	0.0071	0.0083	0.0093	0.0101	0.0107	0.0110	0.0111

Fig.3 Bending moments diagram using Mohr method

Table 3

Bending moments values along the beam using Mohr method

x	0	100	200	300	400	500	600	700	800	900	1000
y	100	90	80	70	60	50	40	30	20	10	0

Fig.4 Diagram of the fictitious moment on the fictitious bar

Table 4

Fictitious bending moments values along the fictitious beam using Mohr method

x	0	100	200	300	400	500	600	700	800	900	1000
y	0	3.33	6.33	8.33	10.3	13.3	15.3	18.3	23,3	28.3	33.3

Fig.5. Diagram of the fictitious shear forces on the fictitious bar

Table 5.

Fictitious shear forces values along the fictitious beam using Mohr method

x	0	100	200	300	400	500	600	700	800	900	1000
y	0	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50

Fig.6 Displacements values along the real beam using Mohr method

Table 6

Displacements values along the beam using Integration method

x	0	100	200	300	400	500	600	700	800	900	1000
d	0	-0.1074	-0.4148	-0.9000	-1.5407	-2.3148	-3.2000	-4.1741	-5.2148	-6.3000	-7.4074

Fig.7 Rotations diagram on the real beam using Mohr method

Table 7

Rotations values along the real beam using Mohr method

x	0	100	200	300	400	500	600	700	800	900	1000
rot	0	0.0021	0.0040	0.0057	0.0071	0.0083	0.0093	0.0101	0.0107	0.0110	0.0111

CONCLUSIONS

As conclusions regarding the application of the two methods we can deduce the following:

1. The author's own contributions are given by the development of calculation programs for the wooden structure using the Matlab numerical programs;

2. The direct integration method is a faster method to apply for situations of structures with any type of support, but a simpler load in terms of external forces. For a small number of external forces acting on the structure, the number of integration constants to be determined by applying the boundary and / or boundary conditions is small;

3. Mohr's method is more laborious in terms of computational algorithm, requiring more time to solve problems; Mohr's method does not require the determination of integration constants;

5. It is found that the determined values of displacements and rotations using the applied methods are the same, which indicates the correctness of the elaboration of the calculation program and of the application of the two methods.

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ABOUT TESTING SEATS FOR DURABILITY AND STRENGTH

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Abstract

This paper presents the testing of chairs for durability and strength important operation that highlights its effectiveness, thus demonstrating the usefulness of the chairs which means not only the design, color or wood used but also strength, durability, comfort and relaxation.

Key words: Chair, Durability, Strength

INTRODUCTION

The chair is a piece of furniture subjected to very strong forces. It is not just about supporting the weight of people but also about resisting countless settlements and lifts, at different forces when the seat is left on its back or in front, remaining with only two feet on the ground. All these are tests that a prototype seat must pass in order to enter production.

That is why hard, resistant wood is used for the chairs. The most used wood is beech, being very good for the manufacture of curved elements (steam bending or with the help of high frequency currents).

However, chairs are also made of oak, ash, but also softwood. Several types of wood can be used to build a chair. However, care must be taken not to make the joints subjected to high forces between hardwood and softwood, and the legs should always be made of hardwood. Softwood can be used for arms or parts of the backrest that are less stressed. (<https://revistadinlemn.ro/2018/11/06/detalii-tehnice-pentru-scaune-din-lemn-confortabile-si-sigure/>)

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The seats under test are of the "BERTIL" type made at S.C. Plimob.

The structure of the seat is characterized by the existence of elements with different rigidities as well as with joint nodes that in exploitation are not always perfectly rigid. The different rigidity of the component elements is determined either by their different dimensions and materials, or by the type and nature of the joining elements (wood plugs fixed with adhesive, metal or plastic elements, etc). In the following, the nodes are considered perfectly rigid. A detailed treatment of the problem in case of considering

the joints in the knots as elastic is presented in the specialized works. (Curtu, 1976, 1977)

Fig. 1 General loading of a seat element (Curtu et al., 1981)

The method of displacements was used to deduce the size of the bending moments in each node. (Curtu et al., 1981). In this respect, considering the general load of a seat element as in figure 1, it results after performing the calculations, the values of the bending-reaction moments in the form

$$\left. \begin{aligned} M_A &= \frac{2EI}{l} (2\varphi_a + \varphi_b - 3\Psi) - \frac{2\Omega}{l^2} (3b - l) \\ M_B &= \frac{2EI}{l} (\varphi_a + 2\varphi_b - 3\Psi) + \frac{2\Omega}{l^2} (3a - l) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1.1)$$

where l is the length (opening of the element), in cm; Ω – the surface of the diagram of bending moments produced by the forces on it, the element being considered as a simple beam resting on the ends; a și b – distances from the ends to the center of gravity of the surface Ω , in cm; φ_a și φ_b –

rotations (angular displacements) of the average fiber in supports A and B, in rad. $\Psi = \Delta/l$ settling angle, Δ being the unevenness of point B with respect to A, in cm. From relation (1.2) follows the following expression for the rotations φ_a și φ_b :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \varphi_a &= \frac{M_A I}{3EI} - \frac{M_B I}{6EI} + \Psi + \Omega \frac{b}{l} \\ \varphi_b &= \frac{M_B I}{3EI} - \frac{M_A I}{6EI} + \Psi - \Omega \frac{a}{l} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1.2.)$$

For the general case of the seat structure, they were obtained with the displacement method, general expressions of bending moments. nts in each node, the following system of equations with the unknowns was finally obtained. $\varphi_B, \varphi_C, \varphi_D, \varphi_E$ și Δ :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} 2(k_{BD} + k_{BC})\varphi_B + k_{BC}\varphi_C + k_{BD}\varphi_D - 3\left[\frac{k_{BD}}{h_2} + \frac{k_{BC}}{l_{BC}}\left(\frac{h_3}{h_2 + h_5} + \frac{h_6}{h_4 + h_7}\right)\right]\Delta &= P_3 \frac{h_8 h_9^2}{l_{BC}^2} \\ k_{BC}\varphi_B + 2(k_{BC} + k_{CE})\varphi_C + k_{CE}\varphi_E - 3\left[\frac{k_{BC}}{l_{BC}}\left(\frac{h_3}{h_2 + h_5} + \frac{h_6}{h_4 + h_7}\right) + \frac{k_{CE}}{h_4}\right]\Delta &= P_1 h_1 - \frac{P_3 h_8^2 h_9}{l_{BC}^2} + P_7 h_{12} \\ k_{DB}\varphi_B + 2(k_{DE} + k_{DB})\varphi_D + k_{DE}\varphi_E - 3\frac{\Delta}{h_2} k_{DB} &= F_H h_5 + \frac{h_3 h_5}{h_2 + h_5} + P_5 \frac{h_{20} h_{11}^2}{l_{DE}^2} \\ k_{EC}\varphi_C + k_{ED}\varphi_D + 2(k_{EC} + k_{ED})\varphi_E - 3\frac{k_{EC}}{h_4} \Delta &= G_H h_7 - G_V \frac{h_6 h_7}{h_4 + h_7} - P_5 \frac{h_{10}^2 h_{11}}{l_{DE}^2} \\ k_{BD} h_2 l_{CE}^2 \varphi_B + k_{CE} h_4 l_{BD}^2 \varphi_C + k_{BD} h_2 l_{CE}^2 \varphi_D + k_{CE} h_4 l_{BD}^2 \varphi_E - 2(k_{BD} l_{CE}^2 - k_{CE} l_{BD}^2) &= \frac{1}{3} l_{BD}^2 l_{CE}^2 (P_1 + P_6) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1.3)$$

In these equations by k were noted the rigidities of each element of the seat structure relative to the rigidity of the AC element, respectively in the general case

$$k_{xy} = k_{yx} = \frac{\left(2E_{xy} \frac{I_{(xy)}}{l_{xy}}\right)}{\left(2E_{AC} \frac{I_{AC}}{l_{AC}}\right)} \quad (1.4)$$

For Example

$$k_{BC} = \frac{\left(2E_{BC} \frac{I_{BC}}{l_{BC}}\right)}{\left(2E_{AC} \frac{I_{AC}}{l_{AC}}\right)}$$

Solving the system of equations (1.3) we obtain the values of the rotations φ_B , φ_C , φ_D , φ_E and the settlement Δ , which introduced in the expressions of the moments result their values. Knowing the maximum values of the bending moments determines the maximum tension $\sigma_{\max} = \frac{M_{iY \max}}{I} = \frac{M_i}{W}$ and compares with the admissible one.

The advantage of the presented method consists in the possibility of studying a wide range of constructive variants of chairs and choosing the optimal one. [11]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Testing furniture for strength and durability is used to provide an overview of testing methods

Static arm load ISO 7173 pct. 7.3 and 7.4

Fig 2 Static arm load

The seat is fixed to prevent the chair from moved. The specified force is applied horizontally, without impact, for a duration of 10 seconds against the inside of the armrest at the point where the risk of damage is highest.

The force is applied vertically, without impact, for a duration of 10 seconds against the top side of the armrest at the point where the risk of damage is highest.

The durability test for seat and backrest ISO 7173 pct. 7.5 and 7.6

The chair is placed with the legs against stop-pers to prevent it from sliding. The specified force 950 N and 330 N respectively simultaneously applied to seat and back for the specified number of cycles without impact.

The basic requirements are 25000 cycles without degradation: visible cracks, ruptures with deformations greater than the specified maximum values, weakening of rigid joints (which cannot be corrected by restricting the hardware). 50.000 cycles are required for high requirements.

Fig. 3 The durability test for seat and backrest

The “BERTIL” type seat has been factory tested on a seat test bench

Fig. 4 Test bench

Fig. 5 Backrest test view

Fig. 6 Seat test view

Fig. 7 Simultaneous seat and backrest test view

Static load in the back and static load in the side ISO 7173 pct. 7.7 and 7.8

The legs opposite the applied force are placed against stoppers to prevent the furniture from sliding. The specified force is applied horizontally and without impact, for 10 seconds to the centre of the seat edge.

Fig. 8 Static load in the back and static load in the side

Impact test against the seat ISO 7173 pct. 7.10

The legs are placed against stoppers to prevent the furniture from sliding.

A weight is dropped from the specified height in the centre of the seat with c.a 180 mm in front of the backrest.

Fig. 9 Impact test against the seat

Bearing capacity of frame SS 839622

The original position of the seat frame is measured. The load is applied to the seat.

After 15 minutes the position is measured and the load is removed and the position is measured once more and the deflection with and without load are calculated.

Fig. 10 Bearing capacity of frame

Measuring of resilience characteristics SS 839508 pct. 3.7

After 100 cycles a load is applied to the seat in the steps of 4 and 200N. For each load the measurement is noted. This measuring is repeated for each test level. The difference in F value between the first measurements (100 cycles) and the following is used in evaluating the result.

Fig. 11 Measuring of resilience characteristics

CONCLUSIONS

Testing the seats for durability and strength is particularly important because it shows a clear situation of the products made.

If they do not meet the requirements, they can be improved, retested and put back into the production cycle..

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ALLEY CROPPING, AS A MODEL OF SYSTEM ADAPTED TO CLIMATE CHANGE

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Abstract

The realization of the alley cropping for the first time in Romania was made in order to promote this type of agroforestry system applied with succes, both at European and global level, in order to improve the microclimatic conditions, to increase the agricultural production and to diversify the overall production of the system. Increasing the percentage of surfaces occupied with forest vegetation, especially in the south of the country or in plains and hilly areas, where it is poorly represented, increasing biodiversity, carbon sequestration, landscape are objectives, which are in addition to those mentioned above. Alley cropping is the cultivation of different crops (cereals, vegetables, forage, even horticultural species) between widely spaced rows of forest trees. Trees are placed within agricultural cropland systems. The installation, with an experimental character, of the alley cropping within the Ogoru Farm and the Fundulea National Institute for Agricultural Research and Development, from Calarasi County, are the first attempts to achieve this type of agroforestry system in our country.

Keywords: alley cropping, agroforestry system, forest species, crops, microclimate, protection

INTRODUCTION

More and more specialists are looking for solutions to the major problems facing humanity: climate change, pollution, decreased biodiversity, greenhouse gases and so on (Dumitraș, 2008, Osmanski, 2020). As a solution to adapt agricultural systems to climate change some farmers in our country introduce forest vegetation, most often in the form of forest shelterbelts (strips of 5-7 rows of trees), to protect agricultural crops from the effects of strong, dry or very hot winds. Another way to associate agricultural crops with forest species is to place trees in agricultural land in the form of a single row of trees, repeated at much shorter distances than in the case of forest shelterbelts, performing both ecological and economic functions (Hodge, et. al., 1999, Mosquera-Losada, et.al., 2018, Nair, 1990). It's all about alley cropping, an innovative agroforestry system in terms of land use (Quinkenstein et al., 2009). In this sense, two experimental blocks were installed at the Ogoru Farm in Lehliu and within the National Institute for Agricultural Development Research (NIADR) Fundulea in which the agroforestry system - alley cropping was introduced.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In order to achieve this type of agroforestry system, respectively the introduction of a single row of trees within the agricultural crops, the site conditions were analyzed. Also, the type of soil was established (Dănescu, et al., 2010 a), the climatic conditions and the existing forest vegetation in the area were analyzed. The characterization of the climatic conditions was made following the documentation from specialized works (***, 1960, ***, 1983) and the interpretation of the climatic data taken from a weather station installed within NIADR Fundulea. The forest vegetation in the area was determined and analyzed through research conducted on the route.

Within the experimental space, all planted seedlings were inventoried and measured (spring and autumn) to calculate the alive seedlings after planting and maintenance percentage, average height and growth during the vegetation period, as indicators of the development of forest species in agricultural crops. Observations were also made on the health of the seedlings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The plain area of our country, included mainly in agricultural land (<https://insse.ro/cms/>) must cope with climate change and the introduction of forest vegetation is a solution to mitigate their negative effects. The alley cropping system, proposed to be carried out, involves the introduction of trees in a row, which are repeated at distances that vary from one farm to another, depending on their production objectives, agricultural crops developing in the intervals delimited by trees (Mihailă E., et al., 2010).

It is considered to mitigate the negative effects of conventional agriculture by reducing soil fertility, pollution of surface and ground water and loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services, while maintaining a high level of production of agricultural crops and obtaining additional production of forest vegetation products (fig.1) (Quinkenstein et al., 2018, Vityi et al., 2018).

The characteristics of forest species and the optimal distance between rows of trees are the main elements that are taken into account when designing alley cropping (Sinclair, 1999). As regards the characteristics of forest species, the choice is made of those species which compete as little as possible with agricultural crops, in terms of light and nutrients (Jose et al., 2000. Rudebjer et al., 2001).

The rows of trees are placed at different distances, taking into account that agricultural work should not be hindered. If timber production is pursued in an alley cropping system, the recommended number of trees per hectare is

50 - 100, which corresponds to a distance between rows of trees of 33 m and a distance of 4 m between trees per row or 25 m between trees rows and 6 m between trees per row (Van Lerberghe, 2017).

Fig.1. The scheme of an agroforestry system versus an agricultural system in terms of the functions they perform (Quinkenstein ș.a., 2018)

In order to ensure a constant long-term agricultural production, it is necessary to increase the distance between the rows of trees, research conducted in this regard showing that a distance of 25 m between rows will allow to obtain a good agricultural production 20 years, after which the shade produced by trees affects agricultural crops (Workman et al., 2003). Within the agricultural farm, respectively the NIADR Fundulea, obtaining high and constant agricultural productions are long-term objectives so that it was established that the distance between the rows of trees should be greater.

Following the site conditions analysis (Dănescu, et al., 2010 b) and taking into account on the one hand the option of farmers from Ogoru Farm, respectively the rapid growth of forest species (to fulfill ecological functions in a short time) for the realization of the alley cropping system were chosen Siberian elm and hazelnut at Ogoru farm and Siberian elm at NIADR Fundulea. At the Ogoru Farm, in the autumn of 2019, three rows of Turkestan elm and two rows of hazelnut trees were installed on an area of approximately 38 ha, spaced, starting from the perimeter hedge, in the southwestern part of the farm, at 136, 120, 90, 125 and 100 m (fig.2).

Fig.2. Alley cropping (Siberian elm /Ulm/ and hazelnut /Alun/ - crops) at Ogoru Farm

The distance between seedlings in a row was 8 m for Turkestan elm and 4 m for hazelnut. A maize crop is installed between the rows of trees / shrubs, and a greenhouse has been built between the rows of hazelnuts since the fall of 2020.

At INCDA Fundulea, the experimental culture was installed in the spring of 2021. Its surface is about 9 ha and included three planting options: V1 - the distance between the rows of trees of 75 m and the distance between the seedlings per row of 4 m, V2 - the distance between the rows of trees of 50 m and the distance between the seedlings on row of 8 m and V3 - the distance between rows of trees of 100 m and the distance between seedlings per row of 6 m (fig.3). Siberian elm was planted between crops of wheat, corn, sunflower.

Fig.3 The experimental alley cropping device installed at at NIADR Fundulea

To stimulate the growth in height of the seedlings and to protect the stem against injury, the gnawing by wild animals (rabbits, deer, etc.) (Potter, 1991) were used protective tubes, with a height of 0.90 and 1.2 m, fixed with wooden stakes.

Fig.4. Row after plantation with trees in protective tubes (April 2021), NIADR Fundulea

Following the observations and measurements made, conclusions were drawn regarding the alive seedlings percentage and maintaining the seedlings, the height of the seedlings after each growing season. The percentage of the alive seedlings for the experimental device installed at the Ogoru farm in autumn 2019 was 78% (88% in Siberian elm and 69% in hazelnut). After the completion of the additions from autumn 2020, the percentage of maintenance in spring 2021 was 93 %. The percentage of dried specimens from the experimental device at Ogoru Farm is small, 8 % in the first year and 5 % in the second year after planting, with a higher number of dry specimens in the hazelnut, 21 in 2020 and 15 in 2021 compared to the Siberian elm, where 7 specimens were dried in 2020 and only one specimen in 2021.

As for the average height value of the seedlings on the rows of trees/shrubs, it is on all rows, except R5, lower in spring 2021, compared to autumn 2020 (Fig.5). This is explained by: i) the additions made in the autumn of 2020 in the case of the other rows where the height of the seedlings used for planting was less than that of the already existing seedlings, which influenced the value of the average height; and ii) reporting, in the spring of

2021, of a number of seedlings that had a broken or dry tip and, therefore, a lower height.

Fig.5. The average height of the Siberian elm (ULT) and hazelnut (AI) within the alley cropping system installed at the Ogoru Farm, spring (P) and autumn (T)

In terms of value, the average height of seedlings ranged from 59 to 124 cm in spring 2020, from 87 to 137 cm in autumn 2020 and from 74 to 127 cm in spring 2021. The variation of the average height is due to the variation of the seedlings height, from 5 - 10 cm in the case of seedlings that were broken or partially dried and which later sprouted, to 190 - 205 cm in the case of seedlings that developed constantly from planting so far. The largest increases was recorded, predictably, at the Siberian elm.

At the experimental device installed, in the spring of 2021, at NIADR Fundulea, the percentage of alive seedlings of Siberian elm was high, being for each experimental block of 96, 98 and even 100%. Regarding the average height on the rows of seedlings within the experimental variants, in the first part of the growing season, it varies within each row of the experimental blocks, the highest values per row being 98 cm, 97 cm in block V3, respectively block V2 and 88 cm in block V1 (Fig.6). The value of the average height for each experimental block varies from 97 cm in block V3 to 81 cm in block V1.

Fig. 6 The average height of the Turkestan elm from INCDA Fundulea

Benefiting in the beginning of the vegetation season in rich precipitation and warm temperatures, the Siberian elm seedlings from the experimental device installed at NIADR Fundulea registered large increases, some specimens exceeding 100 cm, reaching even 130 - 135 cm.

At the Ogoru Farm, some Siberian elm seedlings reach 200 cm after a growing season. The hazelnut seedlings, on the whole, also recorded increases, reaching heights of up to 160 cm.

To date, no diseases or pests have been reported in Siberian elm or hazelnuts in any of the experimental areas.

CONCLUSION

The installation of this type of agroforestry system, alley cropping, for the first time in our country, in agricultural farms in the south of the country, was done to analyze the effect of forest species on agricultural crops and on the microclimate.

After one, respectively two years from the establishment, it was found that the association between forest seedlings and agricultural crops within the alley cropping system was beneficial, the seedlings developing very well.

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ASPECTS REGARDING THE CINEGETIC FAUNA FROM COVASNA COUNTY

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Abstract

*County's fauna represents an important biodiversity and economic element. Hierarchizing species based on certain criteria helps us emphasize their importance in certain segments. These types of classifications use AHP models practiced in diverse domains, including biology sciences. Covasna's land fund occupies a surface of 370980 ha on which 34 game funds are displayed. We have selected 8 species from the species that comprise this county's fauna, namely bear (*Ursus arctos*), lynx (*Lynx lynx*), grouse (*Tetrao urogalus*), tree marten (*Martes martes*), jay (*Garrulus glandarius*), forest woodcock (*Scolopax rusticola*), trout (*Salmo trutta*), and chub (*Squalius cephalus*). According to the AHP hierarchy results, the most important game species from Covasna county are trout (*Salmo trutta fario*), chub (*Squalius cephalus*), and forest woodcock (*Scolopax rusticola*), while lynx is the least important one (*Lynx lynx*). The complexity of the 19 criteria used for this research attests to the fact that the results are surprising if we take into account the importance of some species.*

Keywords: AHP, Covasna, game fund, trout, chub

INTRODUCTION

Hunting was regulated in Transylvania from the year 1504 when serfs were prohibited to hunt certain species (Witting, 1941). This was not only absolute protection but also a means to reserve the entire game resource for the grand nobility, especially for their hunting parties.

Through previous experiences (Ciontu et al., 2018; Timis-Gansac et al., 2018; Ciontu et al., 2020; Crisan et al., 2020; Vechiu & Dincă, 2021) as well as in the economic context, we can create a hierarchy based on a set of criteria. This can be applied to products from the same category as well as to different products: tree species (Dinca et al., 2020; Timis-Gansac et al., 2020; Dinca et al., 2021), medicinal plants, forest fruits, species from the game fauna, mushrooms etc. AHP is a worldwide decision support model used in studying complex aspects involved in taking decisions. The system proved to be useful in numerous domains such as informatics (Rădulescu, 2015), viticulture (Buciumeanu et al, 2020; Vizitiu et al., 2020), and

biodiversity (Timis-Gansac et al., 2020; Dinca et al., 2020; Cantar et al., 2021). Furthermore, certain recommendations were also made regarding its usage and limits (Erdogan et al, 2017, Ishizaka & Labib 2009).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The case study was realized in Covasna County. Here, the relief is mainly mountainous, combined with intramountain basins. The county has 34 game funds with an average surface of 11495 ha (fig.1).

Fig. 1 Location of Covasna County (geodata source: landcorine.org and ancpi.ro)

The land fund surface amounts to 370980ha and is divided according to Table 1(source: insse.ro)

Table 1

Covasna County land fund

Usage category	Surface (ha)
Fields with agricultural usage	185939
Arable	83151
Meadows	60915
Hay fields	41281
Orchards and tree nurseries	592
Fields with non-agricultural usage	185041
Forests and other fields with forest vegetation	165161
Waters, sloughs	2971
Constructions	11195
Communication means	4795
Degraded and unproductive fields	919
Total	370980

As it can be seen in Table 1, we have a balanced distribution between agricultural and non-agricultural fields as both of them have almost equal surfaces. Amongst the non-agricultural surfaces, the largest percentage is occupied by fields covered by forest vegetation. These represent 89% and 45% of the land fund's total surface. This diversity of land usage ensures good conditions for the development of game fauna on the county's entire surface.

The fauna is represented by stag (*Cervus elaphus*), buck (*Capreolus capreolus*), boar (*Sus scrofa*), lynx (*Lynx lynx*), tree marten (*Martes martes*), wolf (*Canis lupulus*), fox (*Vulpes vulpes*), squirrel (*Sciurus vulgaris*), iepure (*Lepus europaeus*), ferret (*Putorius putorius*), grouse (*Tetrao urogallus*), jay (*Garrulus galdarius*), and magpie (*Pica pica*).

The fishing stock is composed of Olt river and Negru river, its affluent from the studied area, as well as interior streams from Întorsurii, Vrancei, Bodoc and Baraolt Mountains. The county also has affluents of Buzău river.

The fishing fauna with a game importance is represented by trout (*Salmo trutta fario*), barbell (*Barbus barbus*), chub (*Squalius cephalus*), minnow (*Phoxinus phoxinus*), and European bulhead (*Cottus gobio*) (Pișota et al, 1975).

Amongst the game interest species, we have chosen and analysed 8 species: bear (*Ursus arctos*), lynx (*Lynx lynx*), grouse (*Tetrao urogallus*), tree marten (*Martes martes*), jay (*Garrulus glandarius*), forest woodcock (*Scolopax rusticola*), trout (*Salmo trutta*), and chub (*Squalius cephalus*). The species were studied and used in an analytical hierarchy process (AHP), while the analyses were realized with the Expert Choice Desktop software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The alternative AHP classification for the 19 criteria taken into account for this study is rendered in Table 2.

Table 2

Criteria		AHP alternative ranking							
		Animal species							
		Ursus arctos	Lynx Lynx	Tetrao urogalus	Martes martes	Garrulus glandarius	Scolopax rusticola	Salmo trutta	Squalius cephalus
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8		
1	Harvesting period	3	2	1	4	8	7	5	6
2	Harvested quantity by one worker in 8 hours	1	2	3	4	7	5	6	8
3	Harvesting cost	4	3	5	6	1	2	8	7
4	Knowledge for harvesting	3	4	5	2	1	8	7	6
5	Tools needed for harvesting	2	1	3	4	5	6	8	7
6	Complexity of harvesting process	4	1	7	3	2	8	5	6
7	Development of the process of harvesting	1	2	5	3	4	6	7	8
8	Knowledge for recognition	1	2	5	7	3	8	4	6
9	Distribution range	7	1	2	4	8	3	5	6
10	Biotic threats	1	2	8	3	4	5	6	7
11	Abiotic threats	1	2	7	4	3	5	8	6
12	Perishability	1	2	6	4	3	5	8	7
13	Market potential	7	3	2	4	1	5	8	6
14	Market demand	7	1	2	4	3	6	8	5
15	Celebrity” of the product on the market	4	3	2	5	1	6	8	7
16	The price of raw product	8	7	4	5	1	2	6	3
17	The price of the derived product	5	6	3	7	1	2	8	4
18	Portfolio of derived products	5	3	2	4	1	6	8	7
19	Transport from the harvesting point to the storage centre	7	2	6	5	1	3	8	4

If we analyze the AHP results, the most important game species from Covasna county are trout (*Salmo trutta fario*), chub (*Squalius cephalus*),

and forest woodcock (*Scolopax rusticola*), while the least important one is lynx (*Lynx lynx*) (Figure 2).

Four species are grouped with similar values, namely bear (*Ursus arctos*), grouse (*Tetrao urogallus*), forest marten (*Martes martes*) and jay (*Garrulus galdarius*). They received minimum grades for certain criteria, even though for others they received a maximum score.

We can observe that trout species (*Salmo trutta fario* and *Squalius cephalus*) have obtained high scores, with a maximum of ones in 10 criteria in the case of trout.

Table 3

Data regarding the hunting effective and shares from Covasna County during 2021
(source: mmediu.ro)

<i>Species</i>	<i>Effective</i>	<i>Harvest</i>
Tetrao urogallus	501	0
Martes martes	565	72
Scolopax rusticola	unknown	37
Garrulus galdarius	unknown	307
Ursus arctos	454**	24*
Lynx lynx	65**	0

* derogations

**resulting from the centralization of 11 hunting funds in the period 2009-2011

In regard to game management, Table 3 presents the harvesting effective and shares approved for 2021. For species that were excluded from hunting during the last years (*Ursus arctos*, *Lynx lynx*), we have presented the last known effective and the number of samples that received shooting derogations.

Fig. 2 Ranking of the selected NWFPs

Grouse (*Tetrao urogallus*) is mainly presented in alpine areas and presents a rather high game interest. The effective estimated in 1968 were 10500 samples, with an annual harvest of 250 samples. In 1999, there were 7850 samples with an annual harvest of 180 samples (Micu, 2005). It is important to maintain this species effective by differentiating their coupling places through proper forest zoning (Negruțiu, 1983). Nowadays, Covasna County has an effective 501 samples.

Tree marten (*Martes martes*) is present in far areas as well as near cities, due to its varied nutrition. The numbers vary based on the presence of squirrels, their favorite nourishment. It was estimated that their population was between 9000-10000 samples during 1960-1970, with an annual harvest of 1200-1600 samples. 30 years later, their population has evolved to 16700 samples with an annual harvest of 340 samples (Micu, 2005). Our studied county records 565 samples.

Chub (*Squalius cephalus*) belongs to the secondary fish fauna from mountain waters and interferes with trout and barbell. Unlike trout, it has a small increase, while its meat is inferior from a culinary perspective. As it attacks fish saplings from poor waters, it is recommended to limit its reproduction (Witting & Cotta, 1955).

Even though it occupies the last place from our hierarchy, **Lynx** (*Lynx lynx*) is an animal with a rather large presence in our county. According to the 1969 evaluation, there were 931 samples at a national level, while Covasna County had between 50 and 100 samples (Geacu, 2007). Nowadays, the effectives are high, representing high importance in protected areas.

CONCLUSIONS

Even though our hierarchy's results place trout and chub at the top, it is advisable for them not to coexist together as one of them can go extinct due to a lack of sufficient food.

Lynx, an endangered animal from almost a century, is situated in the last place based on the studied 19 criteria. Being a solitary animal with an exclusive night activity (excepting mating season), it is rather hard to trace. The legislative context can play a decisive role in these evaluations for certain species that could have an advantage or a disadvantage.

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FOREST EDUCATION PROGRAMMES PROPOSED BY THE NATIONAL FOREST ADMINISTRATION-ROMSILVA IN PARTNERSHIP WITH SPECIALIZED UNIVERSITIES AND OTHER STAKEHOLDERS (2nd PART)

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Abstract

National Forest Administration-Romsilva consistently makes a sustained effort in maintaining and developing a policy of permanent awareness of the young generation on the importance and sustainable management of forests, ensuring their continuity for the future generations, combined with the need to use renewable forest products. The paper addresses two forest education programs proposed by National Forest Administration-Romsilva to preschool and primary school students.

Keywords: forest education, awareness, sustainable management, standing crop, biodiversity, target group

INTRODUCTION

The general **purpose** of these programs: to promote the specific activity of Romsilva National Forest Administration (the only administrator of the state forest fund - 48% of all the forests in Romania) and the role of the forestry staff in ensuring continuity and sustainable management of the national forest fund.

The activities proposed within the programs have the role of learning, informing, acquiring skills, awareness, sensitization, involvement and curiosity.

The **general objectives** had in view in the elaboration of the educational programs are: the transmission of the information in order to acquire the knowledge about the forest and the way of its administration; developing a proactive attitude towards the forest as an ecosystem and developing a responsible attitude of the civil society towards the environment; carrying out practical *indoor* and *outdoor* activities to set the knowledge and develop the skills of the target audience.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In order to implement these programs, it is necessary **to go through the following stages**: training the staff within the forestry departments connected to the target groups for each educational program; signing partnerships with school inspectorates / schools / children's palaces, museums, local authorities, NGOs, etc.; establishing the topics to be developed. The main topics addressed are described in detail in this paper for the two categories of target groups (preschoolers and children in primary school).

As well as the **working methodology**, the following steps will be considered: drawing up a calendar of activities; contacting the target groups; ensuring the logistics related to the activities; preparation of the teaching materials (power-point presentations, videos, cartoons, colorful pictures, stories, riddles, curiosities, interactive games, contests, etc.); indoor and outdoor activities (excursions on themed routes, guided field trips, practical demonstrations, interactive actions, team games, workshops, therapeutic walks in the forest (forest bathing), etc.); involvement in field volunteering with forestry specialists; monitoring the quantifiable results from both a quantitative (number of activities, meetings, etc.) and a qualitative (feedback questionnaires) point of view; dissemination of results in the local media and social networks, as well as the allocation of a budget at the level of the forest administration in order to implement the forestry-educational activities.

Program 1 - Little friends of the forest (addressed to the target group - kindergarten children);

Program 2 - Let's get to know the forest (target group – pupils in the primary school);

The **results** had in view after applying these programs are: *training the future generations to know general notions about forestry and to understand the role of the forester in ensuring the continuity of the forest; promoting the profession of forester and the fact that National Forest Administration-Romsilva is a reliable partner.*

One of the educational programs addressed to preschool students (kindergarten children) (Seghedin, 2019) is presented below.

Name of the program: P1 - Little friends of the forest (presentation made at the International Symposium - *Forests and Education. The activity of foresters in forest development and protection - a means of education in the spirit of respect for the forest*, 2019, Romanian Academy, Bucharest)

Target group: kindergarten children

Main competences: learning, information, skills, awareness, sensitization, involvement

Table 1

Program P1 - details

Secondary competences/ skills			
What should children feel?		What should children do?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - joy; - safety; - freedom; - communion and integration with nature / forest; - love for nature (animals, plants) / forest; - involvement; - accountability 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to be aware that someone is taking care of the forest; - to pass on educational messages to parents (education of parents through children); - to protect; - to use the wood products responsibly / to recycle; - to love animals and plants (games); - to be aware of the role of trees and the forest in human life; - to be curious about everything related to the forest; - to behave appropriately towards the forest. 	
Allocated time: maximum 25-30 minutes for actions organized in the classroom (presentations, games)			
Topics addressed in the P1 program:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the forest and what does a forester do? - How to grow a forest? (the path of a forest, from seed to tree); - Forest nursery - gardens for forest seedlings; - Species of animals, plants and trees. Curiosities about forest flora and fauna. 			
Locations	Didactic Methods	Sent Messages	Allocated Budget
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - forest administrations; - forest districts; - forest nurseries; - national and natural park administrations; - kindergartens; - museums; - cultural and educational centers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • experiments; • games, • riddles, • poetry, • conversations, presentations, • films, drawings / paintings on various topics • thematic excursions -Exhibits with the forest etc 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ <i>Know the forest!</i> ✓ <i>Love the forest!</i> ✓ <i>Protect the forest!</i> ✓ <i>Take care of the forest!</i> ✓ <i>The forest - man's friend!</i> ✓ <i>Support the continuity of the forest!</i> ✓ <i>Keep a civilized behavior in the forest!</i> ✓ <i>Do not set fire in the forest!</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Forest Administration-Romsilva infrastructure • purchase of educational materials (books, games, boards) transport, etc.

The **first theme** of the P1 program aims to convey to children information about **what the forest is and what is the role of the forester in the life of the forest?** This will be achieved through a series of activities specific to this age category, which are presented in a summarized manner below.

Table 2

The objectives and activities specific for P1 program

Objectives	Examples of activities
1. Transmission of information and acquisition of knowledge on: - What is the forest (classifications, examples); - The role and functions of the forest; - The importance and conservation of the forest.	- presentations * .ppt / video - maximum 3 minutes (forest = multiple source of resources), various drawings (differences between a coniferous and deciduous forest, cones, seeds, fauna, animal tracks), forest sounds (animals, birds, water, rain, storm, etc.).
2. Carrying out practical activities and workshops that contribute to the personal involvement of children in forest-related activities: -the importance and benefits of the forest in our life, what would our life look like without wood? -identifying the resources we can find inside the forest. Differences between tree species, classifications.	- dialogue - the composition of the forest, biodiversity, the difference between species, the human-nature relationship, what is a tree (component parts), the succession of seasons; stimulating the imagination, presenting curiosities, riddles, stories. -participation of children in team workshops, involvement in educational games, discovery of the forest through the senses;
3. Acquiring a responsible and friendly behavior towards the forest and trust with respect to the forestry staff. -who takes care of the forest (the duties of a forester and his role); -the importance of maintaining and increasing the forest area, maintaining the health of the forest; - harmful factors (biotic / abiotic); -how we behave in the forest; how we orient ourselves in the forest.	- hiking in the forest to observe and collect plant material of different species of plants, trees (seeds, cones, stalks, leaves, flora, bark); themed excursions; - experiments and any other alternative methods; - open-ended questions such as: "How does a deciduous forest differ from a coniferous forest? What are the differences between beech and oak leaves?"

Theme 2 will focus on how a forest is grown, following its development from the seed to the tree stage, comparing the stages of a human evolution with the stages of a forest evolution (by using representative images).

Table 3

Theme 2 - details

Objectives	Examples of activities
1. Transmission of information and acquisition of knowledge on: - What gives rise to a forest? (seed = basic element); - the stages of development of a forest (comparison between the stages of a person's life and the stages of development of a forest); - what does it mean to regenerate a forest? How is a forest regenerated (natural, artificial, mixed)?	Practical games, presentation of different types of forest seeds, stages of forest development, the role of the forester in ensuring the continuity of the forest. Drawing contest on the theme of forest regeneration.
2. Acquiring information on the need to regenerate a forest.	<p>The image contains two parts. On the left is a bar chart showing the growth of forest area in million hectares (m. ha) from 1930 to 2015. The bars represent the following values: 307 (1930), 322 (1950), 348 (1960), 442 (1970), 526 (1980), 564 (1990), 635.2 (2000), and 685.4 (2015). On the right is an illustration of human evolution, showing a sequence of figures from a small, crouching hominid to a modern human standing upright.</p>

Theme 3 aims to provide information about forest nurseries, about the role and contribution of nurseries to ensure the continuity of a forest.

Table 4

Theme 3 - details

Objectives	Examples of activities
1. Transmission of information and acquisition of knowledge on: - what is a forest nursery?; - what happens and what is the role of a forest nursery ?; - how does the forest nursery contribute to ensuring the continuity of a forest?	- Visiting a forest nursery to discover the stages of seedling development; - Demonstration from an employee on how to plant the seeds / how to transplant/ how to plant?
2. Acquiring information about the species found in a nursery and how long it takes for the seedlings to be planted.	

Photo 1: Photo from a forest nursery within the National Forest Administration -Romsilva

Photo 2 – Leaflet used in the afforestation actions

Theme 4 includes information on species of animals, plants and trees, involving presentations of the forest flora and fauna, including rare species of animals, social insects, plants and trees.

Table 5 Theme 4 - details

Objectives	Examples of activities
1. Transmission of information and acquisition of knowledge on: - forest flora and fauna.	-enumeration of the creatures from the forests specific to the area (min. 5 species from the flora and fauna of the area, using drawings, videos, riddles); - What animals and plants are protected in the area of activity of the forest administrations? Why do we have to protect plants, animals, trees?
2. Involvement of children in simple techniques for recognizing plant and animal species.	- Presentation of curiosities from the life of different species. Did you know that ...? Forest = animal house. Social insects (honey bees, red forest ant, wasps). About beekeeping, how to get honey? The little beekeeper's kit.
3. Educating the love for nature and respect for biodiversity and the integrity of habitats.	- organization of a contest for the recognition of flora and fauna species; contest - drawing plants or trees, leaf colors in different seasons, etc. - organizing practical activities in the field; presentation of some behavioral rules in the forest - to list the activities carried out by the forester for the care and protection of animals. Specify the shelter of each animal and its favorite food. - reciting poems about animals. Riddles.

Name of the program: P2 - Let's know the forest (Seghedin, 2019)

Target group: primary school children (0-IV)

Main competencies: learning, informing, skill acquisition, awareness, sensitization, involvement, curiosity, application in practice of the theoretical knowledge, development of civic sense.

Table 6

The objectives and activities specific for P2 program

Secondary competences			
What should children feel?		What should children do?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - joy - Safety - freedom, recreation - communion and integration with nature / forest - love for nature (animals, plants) / forest - involvement -accountability to the forest 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to be aware that someone is taking care of the forest - to pass on educational messages to parents (parent education through children), to protect, to use wood by-products / to recycle responsibly, to love animals and plants (games) - be aware of the role of trees and the forest in human life, - to be curious about everything related to the forest - to behave appropriately in the forest 	
Allocated time: maximum 40 minutes for actions that take place in the classroom (presentations, games)			
Themes addressed in the P2 program:			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the forest? Who takes care of the forest? The activity and the role of the forester in the care and development of the forest. - Forest regeneration. Stages of forest development. - Forest nursery - forest seedling source / seedling school - Species of animals, plants and trees. Curiosities about nature. 			
Deployment locations	Teaching methods	Messages sent	Quantifiable results
forestry departments, forestry districts, nurseries, national and natural park administrations, schools, kindergartens, museums, cultural and educational centers	-game elements, experiments, explanations, problematization, simple and interactive presentations (* .ppt); - teaching materials: forest seeds, cones, seedlings in different stages, plastic containers, exhibits representing the forest, animal mascots; videos, drawings / paintings on various topics, themed trips, visits to nurseries	<i>Know the forest!</i> <i>Love the forest!</i> <i>Protect the forest!</i> <i>Take care of the forest!</i> <i>Support forest regeneration! Plant now for Christmas!</i> <i>Keep a civilized behavior in the forest!</i> <i>Do not set fire in the forest!</i>	number of participants, number of educational institutions, number of articles / news, facebook views, number of proposed and developed projects, etc.

In 2019, within the National Forest Administration-Romsilva, the Open Doors Day program took place when 70 children were presented the activity of the institution, its employees and a series of practical *indoor* and *outdoor* educational activities took place (e.g. : my first herbarium - identification of tree species, leaf collection and herbarium elaboration; presentation of trout and some exhibits from the Posada museum (birds and naturalized animals from the country's forests), presentation of live pheasants - observation of their behavior in captivity, followed by the release of three pheasants), tasting of bee products produced by Neamț Forest Administration, drawings on asphalt and offering participation diplomas. This action had a positive impact among the children, who left with the desire to learn as much as possible about the forest and they also expressed their desire to spend as much free time in the forest fund. Simultaneously with the action carried out at the headquarters, the program was carried out at all 41 forestry departments and 22 national and natural parks subordinated to National Forest Administration-Romsilva.

This year, National Forest Administration -Romsilva elaborated and printed in a number of 13500 copies, the work - *Through the forest, the first steps - a forest education notebook* for preschool and primary school children, work disseminated to its units, in order to implement the two forest education programs presented above.

CONCLUSIONS

Considering the educational activities implemented over time among the two categories of target groups presented above, it was found that all children show involvement and a lot of curiosity in acquiring new knowledge in the forestry field. We can conclude that educational programs can only have a positive impact in acquiring a long-term forest awareness among the young generation, National Forest Administration-Romsilva demonstrating and wanting to maintain a permanent and transparent communication with all the stakeholders in implementing and developing all these initiated educational programs.

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REACTION OF SOME TAXONS OF DIANTHUS GENRE AT THE *EX SITU* CONSERVATION THROUGH *IN VITRO* MULTIPLICATION TECHNIQUES

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Abstract

Some species of *Dianthus* genre met in our country's spontaneous flora: (*Dianthus spiculifolius* Schur, *Dianthus serotinus* Waldst & Kit., *Dianthus diutinus* Kit.), were analysed botanically and zoologically and then, there was initiated a comparative study related to their *in vitro* reaction whith the purpose of their *in vitro* multiplication and conservation. The vegetal material was composed of young floral buds harvested from the areas of origin of the species, which were inoculated on the MS (1962) medium with a balanced content of phytohormones (an auxin and a cytokinin 0.5-1.0mg/l) or with natural extracts (corn germ extract), with the role of substituting the phytohormones. After 55 days of *in vitro* culture there were followed: the capacity of regeneration (%), multiplication, the radicular system and the *ex vitro* acclimatization capacity of the plants, and there were established the following: *D. spiculifolius* specie reaches the best values in the presence of Zeatin(D₁): 100% regeneration, 68% multiplication with an average of 48 neo-plantlets/explant, and acclimatization of over 50%. *D. serotinus* evolves good on the medium with the higher concentration of BAP-1.0mg/l (D₂): with 70% regeneration, 78% multiplication and about 27 neo-plantlets/explant, and acclimatization is of over 30%. The evolution of diutinus specie is similar but with values somewhat smaller than the ones obtained on serotinus. We recommend: Murashige-Skoog medium as a basal medium for all dianthus species; the presence of the cytokinins, especially Zeatin, in a moderate or small dose (0.5-1.0mg/l) is beneficial for *Dianthus spiculifolius* (but also BAP) alongside a small dose of auxin (0.5mg/l); serotinus has the best reaction also in the presence of a cytokinin in a moderate dose as well as diutinus (1.0mg/l BAP). We recommend a smaller dose of auxin for intensifying the vigour of the roots. From the present study it can be seen the possibility of maintaining *Dianthus* species in collections *in vitro* through an adequate technology but also by following the stages that ensure a high percentage of *ex vitro* acclimatization of the neo-plantlets, with the purpose of repopulating some natural habitats or protected areas.

Keywords: *Dianthus spiculifolius* Schur; *Dianthus serotinus* Waldst & Kit.; *Dianthus diutinus* Kit., apical tissue (meristem), conservation, zoological status, critically endangered (CR), *in situ*, *in vitro* multiplication, *in vitro* collections, *ex vitro* acclimatization, ecological reconstruction.

INTRODUCTION

Many species of *Dianthus* variety met in Romania's spontaneous flora, with scientific and ornamental value have aroused the interest of the researchers for their protection, being studied for the purpose of their *in vitro* multiplication and conservation (Zăpârţan, 1995, 2001; Cristea 2010; Holobiuc et al., 2010;

Laslo, 2011, Agud, 2016). There was even followed the initiation of photoautotrophic culture at some taxons of this genre, with a certain zoological status (Cristea 2004, 2010). Meanwhile there was developed the idea of initiating some *in vitro* collections made up of species endangered with extinction (Mavchan, et al., 2004), which are maintained in collections through subcultures repeated on simple mediums, in the absence of phytohormones, thus making the technique more advantageous (Sarasan et al. 2006). The species from the *in vitro* collections represent a very valuable biological material that if acclimatized could ensure the reconstruction of the area where they come from. This practice of replanting them in outside collections or even at their place of origin is practiced for decades at the Royal Botanical Garden from Kew – England (Fay, 1994). The purpose of the *ex situ* conservation is the protection of the vegetal genetic resources (Bajaj, 1986), but the need for the conservation of the botanical element was also extended on the basis of the advantages of some unconventional multiplication methods (Dodds, 1991; Agud, 2014a).

Botanical and zoological considerations of the studied species: *Dianthus spiculifolius* Schur. *Dianthus serotinus* Waldst & Kit., *Dianthus diutinus* Kit determined us to analyse them in a comparative manner under the aspect of their *in vitro* behaviour. *Dianthus spiculifolius* Schur. specie was seen on Romania's territory at the middle on the last century (Flora RPR), now being sporadically found only in Transylvania along some rivers and in a few points from the reservation Apuseni Mountains Natural Park (Western Carpathians). It is also seen in some sites from Bihor County (Galbenei and Sighiștelului Valley sites, and the site Pietra Bulzului); and also in Alba and Cluj Counties (Fig. 1). It is a geoelement „*Dacian-Pontic endemit with a restricted area and with very poor populations*”, with the zoological status of specie critically endangered (Coldea, Ghe. et al., 2008), of national interest, the Germplasm being conserved in botanical gardens and in gene banks (Olteanu, M. et al., 1994). The habitat of the specie is of a community interest, formed of alpine and subalpine calcified meadows, with small surfaces, conserved in its actual (*in situ*) form, through periodical monitoring of the perimeter of the site (IUCN <http://www.iucnredlist.org>). *Dianthus serotinus* Waldst & Kit. specie, *transilvanicus* Novák var., presents a scientific interest, also a Dacian-Pontic endemit (Dihoru and Dihoru, 1994) with a zoological status of critically endangered, with very small populations (Boșcaiu et. al., 1994). Located in a few points from Transylvania, in Olt River Gorge (Dihoru and Negreanu,

2009), Râpa Roşie and Lancrăm (Alba County), from where the vegetal material for the initiation of the *in vitro* culture was brought.

Fig. 1. Mapping areal of *Dianthus* species (*spiculifolius* and *serotinus*), on the Romanian territory (Dihoru and Negreanu 2009 p. 211)

The third specie, *Dianthus diutinus* Kit, is considered the specie the most endangered with extinction among all the species of *dianthus* variety. Rarely met in the area of Arad County and very rarely in Bihor, at the eastern limit of these areas, between the Criş Rivers (Ardelean, 1999). It is also known in Europe as an European endemit and Dacian-Pontic geoelement (Tutin at all.,1996), and some assert that it is “an endemic or rare specie in Serbia and Romania/*specie aliae*” ”(R. Soó, 1980). *Dianthus diutinus* Kit. is charted on Romania’s map in the spots marked in Fig. 2 (Dihoru and Negreanu, 2009), and alongside its botanical value the specie also has a distinguished ornamental value (Fig. 3).

Fig.2 Prevalence areal in Romania for *Dianthus* Kit. (Dihorul, Negreanu, 2009)

Fig.3. *Dianthus diutinus* Kit. *diutinus* general aspect of the plant (Bot.Ency.1997)

There are known *in situ* and *ex situ* conservation actions of the specie in some reservations on Crişul Alb river, acclimatized in the collections of some Botanical Gardens (Cristea, 2010), or the Germplasm in gene banks, similar to other species with severe zoological framing (Engelman, 1991), or with an economical value (Halmágyi and Butiuc-Keul, 2007). In our country, the concerns for the *in situ* conservation of the aboriginal flora dates from the middle of the last century, marked through the elaboration of some reference works (Flora, RPR, 1952-1974), through the creation of some books or red lists (Dihoru, Negreanu, 2009), and then through studies on the field (Täuber, 1980), through their charting on the map of the country in the existing places.

The final purpose of the technology of *in vitro* culture and multiplication of the plants either in the spontaneous flora, the species with an economical importance (agricultural, horticultural, medicinal, flavouring, etc.) or with an ornamental value is *ex vitro* acclimatization of the material obtained through the retracement of some binding steps, with different difficulty degrees, through which there can be avoided the state of shock (Laslo, 2013). The quality of the obtained plants is given by a good development and by their complete organization (Zăpârţan 2001), vigorous aerial organs, with a well developed radicular system and which is characteristic to the specie represents the essential condition for acclimatization, completed by the shading of the foliar system about a week from the direct protection of the solar rays (Agud, 2014b). Removing unfavourable conditions that can generate infections in the soil or in the atmosphere can be ensured through the initial disinfection at the level of the soil or even of the plant (Boxus, 1995), or by eliminating some infections through the technique of the molecular markers (Ng, 1999). The exchange of the vegetal material obtained *in vitro*, imposes adequate phytosanitary conditions, for ensuring an advantageous exchange of biologic material in the country and abroad (Badea, Săndulescu, 2001).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The species of *Dianthus* variety experimented by us: *Dianthus spiculifolius* Schur., *Dianthus serotinus* Waldst & Kit. *transilvanicus* and *Dianthus diutinus* Kit. var. multiplied *in vitro* from young floral bud harvested from the exemplars form some areas of spreading specified in Table 1 (*spiculifolius* from Bihor - Piatra Bulz Site; *serotinus* - Râpa Roşie and *diutinus* - Criş Valley).

Table 1

Sozological situation of *Dianthus* species conserved *in vitro*

Dianthus specie	Sozological status	Spreading of the specie	Situation of the specie /importance
<i>Dianthus spiculifolius</i> Schur.	CR	Sporadic in Transylvania in the following regions: Cluj, Alba, Bihor. In Buhor is sites as: Galbenei Valley, Sighistelului Valley, and in Piatra Bulzului	Dacian-Pontic geoelement with few and poor populations in the area of origin. Botanical, scientific value.
<i>Dianthus serotinus</i> Waldst&Kit.	CR	Sporadic in Transylvania and in Olt Gorge, isolated in Alba County (Râpa Roşie and Lancrăm)	Dacian-Pontic endemit, small but pure populations
<i>Dianthus diutinus</i> Kit.	CR	At the eastern limit of Alba and Bihor Counties (on the Valleys of Criş River)	European endemit, Dacian-Pontic geoelement

Vegetal material consisting of young floral bud was inoculated at the beginning of summer (during the first stage of flowering) on the MS (Murashige- Skoog, 1962) basal medium, from which there were composed variants with a balanced hormonal composition and with natural extracts (corn germs extract), with the role of substituting the phytohormones. The conceived variants of medium were based on our previous experiences on some of these species and are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Culture mediums for the *in vitro* multiplication of DIANTHUS species

Dianthus species	Var.	MB	ANA mg/l	BAP mg/l	Z mg/l	Additional additives (mg/l: g/l)
<i>DIANTHUS spiculifolius</i> Schur.	D ₀	MS	-	-	-	3 g/l CV
	D ₁	MS	0.5	-	1.0	-
	D ₂	MS	0.5	1.0	-	-
<i>DIANTHUS serotinus</i> Waldst & Kit.	D ₀	MS	-	-	-	-
	D ₁	MS	0.5	0.1	-	-
	D ₂	MS	0.5	1.0	-	-
<i>DIANTHUS diutinus</i> Kit.	D ₀	MS	-	-	-	-
	D ₁	MS	0.5	1.0	-	-
	D ₂	MS	0.5	-	-	5g/l EP

(MB= basal medium; MS = Murashige-Skoog; ANA = α naftil acetic acid; BAP = benzylaminopurine; Z = Zeatin; EP = corn germ natural extract; CV = vegetal coal)

Following the Table we can see the witness sample (D₀) which comprised the MS basal medium, and in the case of *spiculifolius* specie there was added 3g/l of vegetal coal and with the hormonal variants that comprised concentrations of 0.5mg/l ANA and 1.0mg/l BAP and Z: for *serotinus* there was experimented the same concentration of ANA and only BAP (0.1-1.0mg/l): in choosing these concentrations we started from the best results obtained at these

species Laslo, 2011; Agud, 2016). The variants in the case of *diutinus* specie comprised auxin ANA, then 1.0mg/IBAP and a variant with corn germ extract with the purpose of replacing BAP (Table 2).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After 55 days of *in vitro* culture there were followed the percentage of *in vitro* regeneration, of rooting (the value of the differentiated radicular system), the percentage of multiplication and the average of the number of regenerated neo-plantlets/explant. The percentage of acclimatized plants *ex vitro* is considered the most important parameter in the case of this type of experiments, because it has as a final purpose the conservation of the specie and the repopulation of the habitats where the species are found in extinction. Table 3 comprises the medium values and the percentages of the followed parameters for each specie, and in Figures 4 (a,b,c), 5 (a,b,c), 6 (a,b,c) we present in a comparative manner the values obtained at the three *dianthus* species.

Table 3

In vitro evolution of the bud detached from DIANTHUS species (after 55 days)

Dianthus species	Var.	%Rege.	% Root.	%Multiplication/ Average no. pl/expl.	% Acclim.	Bonification
<i>Dianthus spiculifolius</i> Schur.	D ₀	12	5	11 / 2	20	xx
	D ₁	100	15	98 / 48	50	xxxxxxxxxx
	D ₂	60	13	68 / 35	50	xxxxxxxxxx
<i>Dianthus serotinus</i> Waldst & Kit.	D ₀	9	3	8 / 2	15	xxx
	D ₁	28	12	18 / 10	25	xxxxxxx
	D ₂	70	14	78 / 27	30	
<i>Dianthus diutinus</i> Kit.	D ₀	10	2	5 / 2	8	xx
	D ₁	70	12	67 / 25	30	xxxxxxx
	D ₂	48	10	45 / 14	25	xxxxxx

A. *Dianthus spiculifolius*

B Dianthus serotinus

C. Dianthus diutinus

I. The capacity of regeneration and multiplication of the explants of dianthus floral bud.

There were analysed comparatively the regeneration capacity of the explants and their multiplication capacity (expressed percentually) at each of the three species. **Fig. 4a** presents the two parameters of *spiculifolius*, from where we can see very good values on D₁ (with 1.0mg/LZ), that reach up to 98% regeneration and 100% multiplication: good values on D₂ (with 1.0mg/IBAP), exceeding 60% on both parameters: on the witness sample (D₀) due to the presence of the vegetal coal, there are obtained smaller percentages of regeneration and multiplication (of 9 and 6 times), but we mention that they are better than on the other witness samples (where the coal is missing). The percentage values of regeneration and multiplication at *Dianthus serotinus* specie are presented graphically in **Fig. 4b**, from which we can see values under the ones of *spiculifolius* specie, but in this case also on the medium with a high dose of cytokinin D₂ (1.0mg/IBAP), there are obtained good values (78% regeneration, 70% multiplication), in exchange, on the small dose of cytokinin of 0.1mg/IBAP, D₁ medium (with 0.1mg/IBAP), the values are of about three times smaller (18% and respectively 28%). Regeneration and multiplication on the control sample at this specie are reaching only 8-9%. We can assert the need for the presence in the medium of a higher dose of cytokinin for the success of multiplication.

Following **Fig. 4c** we can see values of the regeneration and multiplication of *Dianthus diutinus* specie that are similar with the ones of *serotinus* specie on the medium with a moderate dose of cytokinin: on the variant D₁ (with 1.0mg/lBAP), there took place 78% regeneration and 70% multiplication. In the case of this specie corn germ extract proved to be efficient, for replacing the cytokinins in the medium; on D₂ medium (with 5mg/lGP) regeneration reaches up to almost 45-50%, and multiplication is of 48-50%. The values on the control sample are also small (10%), which determines us to assert the need for adding a cytokinin in the medium or for replacing BAP and Z, GP for obtaining the desired results.

Fig. 4 Capacity of regeneration and multiplication at *Dianthus* conserved *in vitro*, depending on the specie and on the composition of the medium (after 55 days)

(a. = *Dianthus spiculifolius*; b. = *Dianthus serotinus*; c. = *Dianthus diutinus*)

II. Number of neo-plantlets/explant:

The average of the number of neo-plantlets obtained on each *dianthus* explant (bud) is presented in **Fig. 5** in a comparative manner between the three species. We can see, in the case of this parameter too that *Dianthus spiculifolius* specie, on the medium with Zeatin (D₁), has the highest number of neo-plantlets generated from an explant, about 48 neo-plantlets/bud, followed by the variant with the medium dose of BAP (D₂), with about 35 neo-plantlets/bud. On the witness sample D₀ (MB+ 3g/lCV) the bud differentiates an average of only 2 neo-plantlets/explant: tall plants of about 10-12 cm, height stimulated by the presence of the vegetal coal.

The other two species *serotinus* and *diutinus* reach very close averages: 25-27 neo-plantlets/explant on the mediums with a high dose of BAP, and

barely 10 neo-plantlets on the small dose of BAP; and in the presence of 5mg/IEP over 14 neo-plantlets/bud (*Dianthus diutinus* on variant D₁). On the witness sample all species generate only about 2 neo-plantlets (without multiplication), which demonstrate the need for cytokinins, for obtaining a satisfactory number of neo-plantlets/explant.

Fig. 5. Average of the number of neo-plantlets obtained *in vitro* depending on the nature of the specie and on the composition of the medium (after 55 days)

III. Value of the radicular system (rooting %)

Knowing the direct relationship between the differentiation of a corresponding radicular system (as vigour and number of roots), the acclimatization capacity of the neo-plantlets in **Fig. 6 (a,b,c)**, and the presence of an auxin in the culture medium (in a moderate dose), we decided to present the two parameters together in order to conclude in a correct manner the results. In **Fig. 6a** is presented the value of the radicular system in relation with the percentage of acclimatization at *Dianthus spiculifolius*: on the mediums with auxin (0.5mg/IANA) the average number of roots/plantlet is of 10-12 roots, with 15% percentage of rooting/variant. We consider that the value of the radicular system is good in order to ensure a percentage of acclimatization of over 50%. The percentage values of the radicular system and the *ex vitro* acclimatization capacity at *Dianthus serotinus* and *Dianthus diutunus* are very close and are presented in **Fig. 6b and 6c** (with the presentation of the percentages in columns). The values are inferior to *spiculifolius* specie concerning the number of roots/neo-plantlet, and the percentage of rooting is of 12-14% and *ex vitro* acclimatization at half of the plantlets from outside (about 25-30%). We can see the beneficial role of auxin (ANA) in dose of 0.5mg/l, which in certain conditions must be supplemented up to even 1.0mg/IANA, so that the thin and frail roots differentiated *in vitro* (Photos A and B) to develop more vigorously.

Fig. 6 Percentage of acclimatization in relation to the percentage of rooting of *Dianthus* plants obtained *in vitro* (after 55 days)
(a=*Dianthus spiculifolius*; b. = *Dianthus serotinus*; c. = *Dianthus diutinus*)

CONCLUSIONS

1. The success of the acclimatization of the neo-plantlets obtained *in vitro* involves obtaining vigorous plants, completely conformed, with a well developed corresponding radicular system.
2. For a good *in vitro* regeneration and multiplication of the bud detached from *dianthus* species from the spontaneous flora is necessary the presence in the MS medium of a cytokinin (about 1.0mg/l -Z or BAP), and for a good radicular system an auxin (about 1mg/l ANA, AIA or AIB).
3. *Dianthus spiculifolius* specie reaches superior values (98% regeneration and 100% multiplication) towards the other two species: *diutinus* and *serotinus* (about 70-45%), values presented in Table 3.
4. The neo-plantlets obtained *in vitro* do not raise issues at their passing *ex vitro* if there are considered the stages of acclimatization and the phases of development of the bodies of the plants.

5. The study analysed the possibilities of maintaining the species of plants from the spontaneous flora in collections *in vitro*, establishing the binding stages that must be followed periodically: repeated passing, the rejuvenation of the vegetal material and the preparing of a fresh culture medium with adequate doses and phytohormones.
6. The good acclimatization involves obtaining vigorous plants *in vitro*, completely conformed, with a corresponding well developed radicular system (ensured by an auxin – about 1mg/l), the avoidance of the state of shock from the first days since their transfer outside due to some morpho sozological modifications.
7. Eliminating the risk of infections from the soil or atmosphere, through: the initial disinfection of the substratum of culture and even of the plantlets; then, a protection system (the shading of the foliar system) at the passing *ex vitro* with the reduction of hydration and of the effect of the direct solar rays.
8. The vegetal material obtained *in vitro* ensures an internal or international exchange of species, that imposes phytosanitary conditions for eliminating the danger of introducing the pathogens from one country to another.
9. The paper followed the establishment of a protocol that must be followed for ensuring a high percentage of acclimatization of the neo-plantlets obtained *in vitro*, having a particular purpose of repopulating some natural habitats or protected areas with the vegetal material obtained *in vitro*.

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SECONDARY, TERTIARY AND QUATERNARY SECTORS OF THE EUROPEAN MOUNTAIN AREA : A STATISTICAL STUDY

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Abstract

The article analyzes the current context of the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sector of the European mountain area. The analyzes develop the current context and a forecasting regarding mountain economy. According to EU statistics, in Europe, even in the context of COVID-19, production sectors, such as Agriculture, Industry and Construction, have declined in value, while the quaternary and tertiary sector has grown significantly. The authors of the study consider that the agri-food industry in correlation with the primary, secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors is the future of Europe, an idea taken from numerous studies that argue that humanity will go through an unprecedented agri-food crisis. The quantitative analysis have been realized on Eurostat data simulated in Excel and SPSS.

Key words: European mountain area; mountain economy; secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors

INTRODUCTION

The paper presents some aspects of the general situation of mountain entrepreneurship in Europe in the light of the dynamics of the Eurostat indices on business demography. The paper provides an analysis of industry, services and the quaternary sector through the Eurostat classification, for which the industry, construction and services sector, with the exception of insurance activities of companies (secondary and tertiary sectors). In order to verify the conjuncture presented in the paper, the following hypotheses were formulated: *Alternative hypothesis H1* - The probability of recession in the listed sectors is positively correlated with the central trends in these sectors (for those where there is an intensification of activity); in order to calibrate and support the second hypothesis, the zero hypothesis was formulated the following desideratum - *Null hypothesis H0* is the probability of recession in listed sectors is negatively correlated with the central trends in these sectors (for those where there is decreasing of activity).

The data confirm that mountain entrepreneurship is a defining dimension of scientific research on the mountain economy.

At the European level, the general situation of mountain entrepreneurship is ensured through defining business coordinates, such as

the population of active enterprises and the degree of employability in the mountain area.

Sectors performed in the study are Industry, construction and services, except for insurance activities of companies (Ix); Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (Ix1); Professional, scientific and technical activities, administrative and support activities (Ix2); Industry (except construction) (Ix3); Constructions (Ix4); Transport and storage (Ix5); Arts, entertainment and recreation, other service activities (Ix6); Accommodation and food services (Ix7); Information and communication (Ix8); Education, human health and social assistance (Ix9); Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities, except companies (Ix10).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The data presented in the paper show that the business demographics (population of active enterprises) in European mountain area have improved positively, in particular related to the increase in employability of start-ups (table 1 and 2).

For the calculation, the authors used different variables (years 2008 - 2018), SPSS returning all as valid (there were no invalidated data).

According to the data from the table, the demographics of mountain business in Europe could represent a huge potential for the development of the community space economy.

Table 1

Enterprises active in mountain Europe in 2018 -
Secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors (except agriculture)

	Ix	Ix1	Ix2	Ix3	Ix4	Ix5
Bulgaria	264.704	85.646	42.988	22.125	13.710	14.586
Czechia	185.908	33.902	30.809	35.425	31.674	6.508
Spain	2.365.033	534.423	415.731	143.392	306.610	136.662
France	1.186.561	218.526	201.936	79.084	171.840	32.613
Croatia	46.897	8.723	8.886	4.740	5.191	2.991
Italy	2.110.124	523.273	414.437	208.440	253.067	53.432
Austria	295.029	50.953	53.512	23.371	23.944	8.378
Poland	148.678	35.562	19.197	17.951	26.499	10.118
Portugal	269.240	58.401	55.722	25.514	26.386	5.821
Romania	275.467	86.569	37.241	30.500	27.071	25.827
Slovakia	307.725	62.372	51.905	51.163	69.635	10.698

	Ix6	Ix7	Ix8	Ix9	Ix10
Bulgaria	26.279	15.703	11.521	14.011	18.135
Czechia	14.508	10.782	5.435	7.850	9.015
Spain	210.618	211.498	43.497	184.993	177.609
France	100.173	90.964	32.100	181.802	77.523
Croatia	2.916	8.291	1.230	2.112	1.817
Italy	134.287	173.812	45.322	156.623	147.431
Austria	21.578	36.269	10.734	52.180	14.110
Poland	8.295	6.925	4.591	13.965	5.575
Portugal	20.812	26.660	2.650	36.370	10.904
Romania	21.918	15.073	11.386	10.263	9.619
Slovakia	15.177	11.037	10.415	10.667	14.656

Source: Authors according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data presented show that the demographics of business in mountain Europe have improved positively, especially in the context of increasing employability of start-ups. The central trend of the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors of the economy, during the analyzed period, shows that the population of the European mountain economy of active enterprises increased considerably from 2008 to 2018 (figures 1). This indicator, the population of active enterprises, presents a high degree of non-variability, which means that the results do not show a large deviation and are positive. Skewness shows a corresponding symmetrical distribution, which means that the mountain business environment begins to stabilize considerably in the analyzed period. Kurtosis has an agglomeration in some industries, ICT being specific to European mountain area.

In the analyzed period between 2008 and 2018, the total population of enterprises increased considerably in all countries. The turning point of this evolution was the development of the secondary and tertiary economic sector, in the first part of the analyzed time interval, ie 2008 - 2012, and of the quaternary economic sector, in the second part of the period 2012 - 2018, to the detriment of the primary economic sector.

Services, especially summer sales and entertainment, are based on the influx of capital during the summer, when European mountain area is visited by many tourists.

Fig. 1. Countries histogram for the Industry, Construction and Services sectors excluding insurance activities of companies
 Source: Authors according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

The increased variation of the analyzed index indicates a high volatility of the economy in mountain Europe. In the latter part of 2008-2018, the economy based its development on other resources, such as IT and food production.

In this context, agriculture should not be neglected and agricultural products should be processed locally for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors. Processed products must be distributed at higher prices than primary products, thus adding value to primary production.

Statistics for secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors, excluding insurance activities of companies (table 1 and figures 1), the indicator represented was Average working population, as follow 237,248.27 (Bulgaria), 197,927.71 (Czech Republic), 2,301,154.2 (Spain), 1,045,660.83 (France), 44,416.38 (Croatia), 2,139. 540.09 (Italy), 286,913.36 (Austria), 152,074.33 (Poland), 253,071.36 (Portugal), 22,349.91 (Romania), 262,552.27 (Slovakia), with Standard Deviations: 22,358.4 (Bulgaria), 38,037.46 (Czech Republic), 66,117,501 (Spain), 124,479,659 (France), 1,246,043 (Croatia), 35,840,137 (Italy), 13,659,231 (Austria), 4,336,484 (Poland), 11,884,912 (Portugal), 46,425,535 (Romania), 27,125,399 (Slovakia). H1 hypothesis has been validated.

At a first analysis, the distribution curves are relatively symmetrical on the central value, and the scores around the average are very concentrated, with the appearance of leptocurtosis, although the distribution is unimodal. Leptocurtosis is a statistical distribution in which points along the X-axis are grouped, resulting in a larger peak or a kurtosis larger than the curvature found in the distribution. Leptocurtosis can have an impact on how analysts estimate the value at risk (VaR). An investor who uses a normal distribution to estimate VaR may overestimate at low levels of significance, but may overestimate at high levels of significance if the return distribution is leptocurtic. This is the result of the leptocortical distribution having a thicker tail. The fat tail means that the risk comes from extraordinary events, and extreme observations are much more likely to occur. Therefore, conservative investors should avoid this type of return distribution.

Regarding specific sub-sectors from the analyzed economic sectors, statistics present increase for all the European mountain areas. Statistics related to the evolution of the field of activity *Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles* (table 1, figure 2) shows, mainly average values of 82,827.64 (Bulgaria), 561,775.18 (Italy), 51,836.73 (Austria), 60,643 (Portugal), 77,409 (Romania), 66,766 (Slovakia), with standard deviations of 4,747.31 (Bulgaria), 24,040,658 (Italy), 1,098,528 (Austria), 3,920,721 (Portugal), 12,693,011 (Romania), 3,422,343 (Slovakia); H1 hypothesis has been validated. *Secondary sector (excluding*

construction) (table 1, figures 1) show average values of 21,268.64 (Bulgaria), 222,065.18 (Italy), 23,527.45 (Austria), 24,589.64 (Portugal), 26,531.45 (Romania), 44,781.09 (Slovakia), having standard deviations of 964,682 (Bulgaria), 1,0658,087 (Italy), 723,048 (Austria), 1,174,249 (Portugal), 3,660,899 (Romania), 3,266,588 (Slovakia); H1 hypothesis has been validated. Statistics for *Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities, administrative and support activities* (table 1, figures 1) presents averages of 35,352.09 (Bulgaria), 393,396.55 (Italy), 52,420.55 (Austria), 47,699.73 (Portugal), 31,647.91 (Romania), 37,100.45 (Slovakia), having standard deviations of 5,661,148 (Bulgaria), 10,014.17 (Italy), 2,063.69 (Austria), 3,614,614 (Portugal), 8,162,452 (Romania), 9,154,217 (Slovakia); H1 hypothesis has been validated. Statistics for *Construction sector* (table 1 and figures 1) show - averages of 13343.82 (Bulgaria), 289242.45 (Italy), 22953.73 (Austria), 27495.82 (Portugal), 22625.82 (Romania), 55966.09 (Slovakia), having standard deviations of 780,698 (Bulgaria), 28615,948 (Italy), 1028,583 (Austria), 3900,296 (Portugal), 2996,174 (Romania), 7905,466 (Slovakia); H0 hypothesis has been validated. Statistics for *Transport and Storage sectors* (table 1 and figures 1) presents averages of 12,462.91 (Bulgaria), 58,331.27 (Italy), 8,762.45 (Austria), 5,976.45 (Portugal), 18,845.27 (Romania), 8,660.73 (Slovakia), having standard deviations of 1,543,081 (Bulgaria), 3,774,077 (Italy), 359.93 (Austria), 398.84 (Portugal), 5,262,442 (Romania), 1,120,484 (Slovakia); H1 hypothesis has been validated. Statistics for *Art, Entertainment and Recreation, other activities dedicated to services* (table 1 and figures 1) present averages of 20,828.64 (Bulgaria), 127,952.73 (Italy), 21,913 (Austria), 18,005.18 (Portugal), 13,623.91 (Romania), 11,628.36 (Slovakia), having standard deviations of 3,778,706 (Bulgaria), 3,320,696 (Italy), 1,397,259 (Austria), 1,308,409 (Portugal), 6,408.38 (Romania), 1,877,443 (Slovakia); H1 hypothesis has been validated. Statistics on *Accommodation and Food Service Activities* (table 1 and figures 1) show averages of 14,951.64 (Bulgaria), 165,570.82 (Italy), 38,573.18 (Austria), 23,433 (Portugal), 12,218.82 (Romania), 10,293.82 (Slovakia), having standard deviations of 201,140.35 (Bulgaria), 6,253,434 (Italy), 1,895,689 (Austria), 1,368,137 (Portugal), 2,591,518 (Romania), 671,853 (Slovakia); H1 hypothesis has been validated. Statistics for *Information and Communication* (table 1 and figures 1) show averages of 8,323.55 (Bulgaria), 42,540.27 (Italy), 10,086.91 (Austria), 2,110.73 (Portugal), 8,327.82 (Romania), 7,191.27 (Slovakia), having standard deviations of 2,144,565 (Bulgaria), 1,371.66 (Italy), 559,725 (Austria), 239,136 (Portugal), 2,527,372 (Romania), 1,868,763 (Slovakia); H1 hypothesis has been validated. Statistics for *Education, human health and social work activities* (table 1 and figures 1) present average of 12,587.82 (Bulgaria),

135,681.09 (Italy), 42,982.09 (Austria), 33,004.73 (Portugal), 8,261.64 (Romania), 10,750.45 (Slovakia), having standard deviations of 1,102,334 (Bulgaria), 13,305,708 (Italy), 8,576,096 (Austria), 1,572,964 (Portugal), 4,455,942 (Romania), 837,814 (Slovakia); H1 hypothesis has been validated. Statistics for *Financial and Insurance Activities, real estate activities* (table 1 and figures 1) present averages of 15401.55 (Bulgaria), 142982.55 (Italy), 13857.27 (Austria), 9913.09 (Portugal), 6838.27 (Romania), 9414 (Slovakia), having standard deviations of 2278,127 (Bulgaria), 7959.51 (Italy), 1638,002 (Austria), 504,891 (Portugal), 1898,701 (Romania), 2809.27 (Slovakia); H0 hypothesis has been validated. Statistics for *Financial and Insurance Activities, real estate activities* (table 1 and figures 1) present averages of 15401.55 (Bulgaria), 142982.55 (Italy), 13857.27 (Austria), 9913.09 (Portugal), 6838.27 (Romania), 9414 (Slovakia), having standard deviations of 2278,127 (Bulgaria), 7959.51 (Italy), 1638,002 (Austria), 504,891 (Portugal), 1898,701 (Romania), 2809.27 (Slovakia); H1 hypothesis has been validated.

According to the forecasting analysis, for created models - Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Spain, France, Croatia, Italy, Austria, Poland, Portugal, Romania and Slovakia, the population of active enterprises will increase considerably in Europe by 2028 (figure 2).

According to forecasting analysis, Bulgaria, Spain, France, Austria, Portugal, Romania and Slovakia will have considerable increases in the sectors analyzed for active enterprises, while the other countries moderate increases or decreases.

The perspectives for 2028 present the defining ascending mountain area both in terms of indicators regarding the population of active enterprises and those related to the degree of employability.

The development trends of mountain entrepreneurship will be supported by major investments made for this area, but also by ensuring the repopulation of mountain areas.

The fluctuations of the mentioned coordinates characterize the general picture of the mountain entrepreneurship. The results of the forecast study show that the economy of mountain areas, especially mountain entrepreneurship, has developed significantly in recent years.

Fig. 2. Forecast analysis for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors of the population of enterprises active in the mountainous area of Europe

Source: Authors according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

CONCLUSIONS

At the European Union level, the mountain area is considered to have a huge potential for organic farming and human health, the air-water-soil ecosystem of this area being less polluted than the other relief areas. This is, moreover, the reason why European countries have legislated on issues related to the mountain area, as no other country or group of countries outside Europe has specific mountain regulations. Europe believes in the development of the economy through the sustainability of mountain science. In this context, mountain entrepreneurship, especially for the population, is a permanent subject of studies and applications for the public and corporate governance of European countries.

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THE LEVEL OF AIR POLLUTION WITH NITROGEN DIOXIDE IN THE CITY OF ZALĂU IN 2020

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Abstract

This paper presents the level of air pollution with nitrogen dioxide for the year 2020. Air pollution is monitored by the Zalău Environmental Protection Agency through continuous measurements at the industrial type I automatic station, which is located in the municipality of Zalău, Meteorologiei St. The station is included in the National Network for Monitoring Air Quality.

Analysis of the air pollution level with nitrogen dioxide in Zalău for the year 2020 shows that the maximum permissible concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ was not exceeded. Higher values were recorded in January (33,411 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), November (19,930 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), October (19,050 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), February (18,838 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), March (17,561 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and 15,206 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in December. The highest nitrogen dioxide concentration was reached on 8 January 2020, 59.87 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Based on the results, it can be stated that the level of pollution with nitrogen dioxide in the municipality of Zalău is within permissible limits, the maximum permissible concentration was not exceeded.

Key words: maximum permissible concentration, monitoring, nitrogen dioxide, sampling point

INTRODUCTION

Nitrogen dioxide (NO_2) is a reddish-brown gas, with a strong and pungent odour. The main nitrogen dioxide pollution sources are internal combustion engines which burn fossil fuels and motor vehicle traffic (Măhăra, 1976; Ciulache, 2004; Moza, 2009; Köteles, Pereş, 2010). Means of transport have a significant contribution to the nitrogen dioxide emissions (Mănescu, et al., 1994; Dumiter, 2005; Gavrilescu E., 2008; Moza A. C., Köteles, 2010).

Exposure to this pollutant can result in breathing difficulties, respiratory tract irritation, and long term exposure to a small concentration can destroy pulmonary cells (Pereş et al., 2010, 2011; Köteles et al., 2016).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For this paper we have used the nitrogen dioxide pollution data provided by the Zalău Environmental Protection Agency. Nitrogen dioxide air pollution monitoring is performed through continuous measurements at the industrial type I automatic station located in the municipality of Zalău, Meteorologiei St. (apmsj.anpm.ro).

The results were obtained using mathematical and statistical methods, then they were presented in charts to show the nitrogen dioxide variability across time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Monthly evolution of nitrogen dioxide

Analysis of nitrogen dioxide concentration monthly evolution for the year 2020 shows that the highest value was recorded in January, $33.411 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, followed by the concentrations in November ($19.930 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), October ($19.050 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), February ($18.838 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), March ($17.561 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and $15.206 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in December. These values do not exceed the maximum permissible concentration of $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

The lowest values were recorded in May, $10.137 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, followed by June, $10.913 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, July, $11.400 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and August, $11.929 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Nitrogen dioxide monthly evolution at the Zalău Environmental Protection Agency sampling point in 2020

2. Evolution of maximum daily averages at the sampling point

Analysis of the daily nitrogen dioxide pollution level data in the municipality of Zalău shows that the maximum concentration of nitrogen dioxide was recorded on 8 January 2020 ($59.87 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). This value does not exceed the maximum permissible concentration of $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Higher values were recorded on 18 February 2020 ($43.30 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), followed on 24 October 2020 by a value of $35.04 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, then the value on 19 April, $31.39 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and on 23 December, $29.31 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Lower concentrations were recorded on 30 July, $15.84 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, on 10 June, $17.42 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and 18 August, $18.42 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Monthly maximum values recorded at the Zalău Environmental Protection Agency sampling point in 2020

CONCLUSIONS

The study conducted on the evolution of nitrogen dioxide in the municipality of Zalău for the year 2020 reveals that the maximum permissible concentration of $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ was not exceeded.

The highest concentration, $59.87 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, was recorded on 8 January 2020. Another higher value was recorded on 18 February 2020, that is, $43.30 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

The monthly evolution of the nitrogen dioxide pollution level in 2020 shows that the highest concentration of nitrogen dioxide was recorded in January, $33.411 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, followed by that of November, $19.930 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, then October, $19.050 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and February, $18.838 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, but these values do not exceed the maximum permissible concentration.

The highest concentrations of nitrogen dioxide are recorded in the cold season of the year, when the air temperature is low. From this it can be concluded that in the warm season of the year there are more active convective motions, which have an important role in air purification.

Higher air pollution values are recorded near high-traffic arterial roads, industrial waste landfills, in the area of uncontrolled waste dump sites etc.

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16. STAS 12574-87

ABSOLUTE EXTREME AIR TEMPERATURES IN THE AREA OF ORADEA, BIHOR COUNTY

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Abstract

The study of extreme air temperatures in the area of Oradea is based on data recorded at the Oradea weather station. The analysis of the thermal regime in the area of Oradea covered a period of 51 years. The data were extracted from the archives of the National Meteorological Administration (ANM).

The analysis of the air temperature regime was based on the extraction of extreme values (absolute minimums and maximums), which represent the possible variation limits of the element.

The absolute maximum air temperature at the Oradea weather station was 40.4°C, it was recorded on 20 July 2007. The annual absolute maximum occurs mainly in July, 41.7% of the cases, which means 24 years out of the 51 included in the study. The absolute minimum air temperature value was -22.5°C and it was recorded on 13 January 1987. The annual absolute minimum occurred in January in most years included in the study, with a frequency of 51%.

Key words: air temperature, absolute maximum, absolute minimum

INTRODUCTION

Located on Crișul Repede river, the city of Oradea lies in an area where the Bihariei Plain, Borșului Plain (parts of the Crișurilor Plains), Oradea Hills and Tășadului Hills (parts of the Crișene Hills) meet. The Crișurilor Plains and the Crișene Hills belong to a transition area from the Someșului Plain to the Silvano-Someșene Hills in the north, towards the Banatului Plain and Hills in the south, which result in a large diversity of geographical aspects (Posea, 1977; Berindei et al., 1977).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Analysis of extreme temperatures in the area of Oradea was conducted using data recorded in meteorological observation tables at Oradea weather station. The air temperature data used in the study were recorded over a period of 51 years (1970 – 2020) during instrumental observations performed at the weather station.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Air temperature is one of the most important climatic parameters which undergoes spatial-temporal changes as a result of the interaction of climatogenic factors (Pereş, Köteles, 2011, 2013, 2015).

The average of daily maximum values in Oradea calculated for a period of 51 years, 1970 – 2020, is 16.4°C.

The monthly averages of daily maximum temperatures are positive over the whole year, beginning with March the maximum temperature averages start to increase gradually, due to the increase in the intensity of solar radiation, the averages reach the highest values in July and August, after which they decrease gradually until December. In the period included in the study there were also months with negative averages of the maximum temperatures, in some of the winter months, but this did not happen on a regular basis. Thus, the lowest average of daily maximums was -3.2°C, it was recorded in February 1985. The highest average of daily maximums for winter months was recorded in February 1998, a value of 11.0°C.

The annual values of maximum averages fluctuated from one year to another, the lowest value being recorded in 1978, 14.0°C, and the highest one, 18.7°C, in 2000, which gives a multiannual amplitude of 4.7°C.

In the area of Oradea the average of multiannual thermal minimums is 5.9°C. The average of multiannual monthly minimum temperatures is negative from December to February.

The annual values of minimum averages fluctuated from one year to another, the lowest value being recorded in 1979, 0.5°C, and the highest in 2014, 8.1°C, which gives a multiannual amplitude of 7.6°C.

Absolute extreme air temperatures

Although they occur randomly, extreme temperatures have a significant practical and theoretical importance, as they show the possible limits within which temperatures can vary from the warm season of the year to the cold one (Costea M., 2014). These temperatures have a relative character, that is, they depend on the length of the monitoring interval and they are determined by the circulation of air masses, as well as the local conditions (Dragotă, Gaceu, 2002; Cristea, 2003; Köteles, Pereş, 2010).

Absolute maximum temperature

It represents the maximum value recorded during the entire monitoring period, at a certain moment. Just like the minimum temperature, it occurs randomly, showing the air temperature value which can be reached or even exceeded.

The absolute maximum temperature at the Oradea weather station was recorded on 20 July 2007, the value of 40.4°C (Table 1).

Table 1

Variation of monthly and annual absolute maximum temperatures in Oradea,
1970 – 2020

Month	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	Year
t°C	17.4	19.0	26.4	31.0	32.9	37.8	40.4	40.0	36.6	30.5	26.0	17.9	40.4
Date	07.01	25.77	22.74	30.12	28.00	23.00	20.07	21.00	07.08	01.12	08.97	09.06	20.07.2007

Source: data provided for processing by the A.N.M archives

At the Oradea weather station the annual absolute maximum temperature is recorded primarily in July, with a frequency of 47.1%, which means 24 years out of the 51 included in the study. A high frequency can be seen in August too, 43.1%, (22 years), the frequency in June is 7.8%, and in September 2.0% (Table 2).

Table 2

Absolute maximum values and the dates when they were recorded in Oradea (1970 – 2020)

Month	June	July	August	September
Annual absolute maximum (°C)	37.8	40.4	40.0	36.6
Date	23.2000	20.2007	21.2000	07.2008
Frequency (%)	7.8%	47.1%	43.1%	2.0%

Source: data provided for processing by the A.N.M archives

In the case of winter months, the absolute maximum temperatures are positive in each year. Thus, the absolute maximum value for the cold season was recorded in February, when the temperature in Oradea reached 19.0°C on 25 February 1977. The winter month with the highest number of years (26) in which the air temperature reaches the highest values is February, which gives a frequency of 51%, followed by December with a frequency of 39.2%.

In spring, the absolute maximum seasonal temperatures are recorded in most cases in May, with a number of 47 years out of the years included in the study, which gives a frequency of 92.2%. The highest air temperature value recorded in a spring month was 32.9°C, on 28 May 2000. In April, the absolute maximum values occurred in 3 years, with a frequency of 5.9%, and in March their frequency is 2%.

In autumn, the highest air temperatures are recorded in September, when they reach a frequency of 94.1% (48 years). In September the annual absolute maximum value, 36.6°C, is recorded on 7 September 2008. Maximum temperatures occur in October too, but with a much lower frequency, 5.9% (3 years).

A comparative analysis of the monthly absolute maximum air temperature values and of the monthly average values reveals that there are big differences between them, which shows that the absolute maximum values occur randomly.

The highest air temperature values were determined by the random invasion of the dry hot continental tropical air carried here as a result of the extension of the North African Anticyclone or that of the Arabian Peninsula (Ciulache S., 2002; Dumiter A. F., 2007; Moza A. C., 2009; Pereş A. C., et al., 2020).

Absolute minimum temperature

It represents the lowest air temperature value recorded during the monitoring period of the weather station.

In the case of the Oradea weather station, the absolute minimum air temperature value was -22.5°C , and it was recorded on 13 January 1987 (Table 3).

Table 3

Variation of monthly and annual absolute minimum temperatures in Oradea,
1970 – 2020

Month	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	Year
t°C	-22.5	-21.6	-16.0	-6.2	-0.6	1.9	6.1	4.4	-1.9	-12.1	-18.9	-21.2	-22.5
Date	13.87	23.83	05.96	09.97	01.76	04.77	20.96	26.80	29.70	13.71	29.95	25.01	13.01.1987

Source: data provided for processing by the A.N.M archives

The absolute minimum temperatures show negative values in the cold season and in the transitional one, while in the summer these values are positive. The values vary between -22.5°C , a value recorded on 13 January 1987 and 6.1°C , recorded on 20 July 1996.

In the summer, the absolute minimum value over the 51 years included in the study was recorded in June, that is, 4 June 1977, 1.9°C . The highest absolute minimum value of the summer occurred in July, that is, 20 July 1996, 6.1°C .

In wintertime, the absolute minimum occurred on 13 January 1987, -22.5°C , in February this value was -21.6°C , while in December the absolute minimum was -21.2°C (Table 3).

In spring, the absolute minimum was -16°C , it was recorded on 5 March 1996.

At the Oradea weather station, the annual absolute minimum was recorded primarily in January, with a frequency of 51%. Thus, in January during the 51 years included in the study the annual absolute minimum occurred in 26 years. In February and December the frequency is 19.6%, which means 10 years, while in November their frequency is 7.8% (Table 4).

Table 4

Absolute minimum values and the dates when they were recorded in Oradea, 1970 – 2020

Month	I	II	III	XI	XII
Annual absolute minimum (°C)	-22.5	-21.6	-16.0	-18.9	-21.2
Date	13.1987	23.1983	05.96	29.1995	25.2001
Frecquency (%)	51%	19.6%	2%	7.8%	19.6%

Source: data provided for processing by the A.N.M archives

The lowest thermal values occur due to the invasion of the cold Arctic air, carried by anticyclones: the East-European or the Scandinavian Anticyclone, synoptic situations during which the sky clears up, which favours nocturnal radiation, helped to a great extent by the snow (Măhăra Gh., 2001, 2006; Gaceu O., 2005; Pereş A. C., 2012; Pereş A. C., et al., 2019).

CONCLUSIONS

The absolute maximum temperature at the Oradea weather station was recorded on 20 July 2007, the value of 40.4°C. The annual absolute maximum is recorded mainly in July, with a frequency of 47.1%.

The absolute minimum air temperature value was -22.5°C, it was recorded on 13 January 1987. In the years included in the study, the annual absolute minimum was recorded primarily in January, with a frequency of 51%.

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